

Review

Recent progress in click-crosslinked bio-based hydrogels for biomedical applications

Ozlem Ipek Kalaoglu-Altan^{a,b,*}, Marco Sangermano^a^a Dipartimento di Scienza Applicata e Tecnologia, Politecnico di Torino, 10129 Torino, Italy^b Department of Textile Engineering, Istanbul Technical University, 34437 Istanbul, Türkiye

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Click chemistry

Biopolymers

Chemically crosslinked hydrogels

Biomedical applications

ABSTRACT

Hydrogels have emerged as versatile biomaterials owing to their high water content, tunable mechanical properties, porous structure and biocompatibility. Recent advancements in bio-based hydrogel design have focused on integrating renewable biopolymers with “Click” chemistry which are rapid, specific, and bio-orthogonal reactions that enable efficient crosslinking under mild conditions. This review summarizes the latest developments in click-crosslinked bio-based hydrogels, emphasizing mainly copper-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition, strain-promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition, thiol-ene, thiol-Michael, Diels-Alder, and inverse electron-demand Diels-Alder reactions. Particular attention is given to the shift from copper-catalyzed to metal-free systems to enhance cytocompatibility and in vivo safety. The review discusses how these click strategies allow precise control of hydrogel structure, mechanical integrity, and degradation behavior, facilitating their application in drug delivery, tissue engineering, wound healing, and regenerative medicine. Emerging trends including multifunctional and interpenetrating network hydrogels highlight the potential of click-crosslinked biopolymers as sustainable and customizable platforms for next-generation biomedical materials.

1. Introduction

Hydrogels are three-dimensional polymeric networks capable of absorbing and retaining large amounts of water, a property that, along with their tunable structure and permeability, makes them highly attractive for biomedical applications [1,2]. First introduced by Wichterle and Lim in the 1960s for the development of contact lenses, hydrogels have since found broad application across various medical disciplines [3]. They have been recognized as dynamic materials that interact with biological environments and actively influence cellular behavior. Their unique combination of characteristics include high water content, biocompatibility, biodegradability, hydrophilicity, porous architecture, and customizable mechanical properties [4,5]. These properties have led to their widespread use in drug delivery, tissue engineering, and regenerative medicine [6–12]. In drug delivery, hydrogels enable controlled and sustained release of therapeutic agents, either locally or systemically, and contribute in reducing dosing frequency, minimizing side effects, and protecting drugs from degradation [4,13–16]. In tissue engineering, hydrogels act as scaffolds that mimic the extracellular matrix (ECM), providing a hydrated 3D environment

that supports cell growth, guides cell fate, and promotes tissue regeneration [17–19]. Hydrogels have attracted significant attention in wound dressing applications because their highly hydrated and biocompatible polymer networks can maintain a moist wound environment, promote cell migration and tissue regeneration, and thereby accelerate the wound healing process [20]. Beyond these core areas, hydrogels have found applications in biosensing, bioimaging, soft robotics, tissue fillers, and as in vitro 3D disease models for high-throughput drug screening.

Significant progress has been achieved in hydrogel development through the use of synthetic polymers, largely due to the precise control they offer over chemical composition, consistent batch quality, and ease of production. However, they often lack features necessary for biological compatibility, such as cell adhesion sites. Recent efforts have shifted toward utilizing biological molecules, specifically biopolymers, to impart inherent biofunctionality to hydrogels. Natural polymers resemble native ECM and provide biochemical signals that enhance cellular responses and reduce immune reactions and they may require chemical modification to enhance properties. From an ecological standpoint, natural polymers are advantageous because they come from

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ozlem.kalaoglu@polito.it (O.I. Kalaoglu-Altan).<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reactfunctpolym.2026.106771>

Received 8 January 2026; Received in revised form 11 March 2026; Accepted 30 March 2026

Available online 17 April 2026

1381-5148/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

renewable sources, unlike fossil-based synthetic polymers [21]. Biopolymers are naturally occurring polymers derived from plant and animal sources, and they include polysaccharides and polypeptides. Common polysaccharides used in hydrogels include hyaluronic acid, chondroitin sulfate, heparin, dextran, alginate, cellulose, chitin, and chitosan [22–24]. Among polypeptides, materials like gelatin, silk fibroin, albumin, elastin, keratin, and engineered peptides are frequently employed [15,25,26]. These materials can provide beneficial characteristics to hydrogels, such as water affinity, biodegradability and cell-binding capabilities although they may suffer from limited mechanical strength. In response to these challenges, hybrid hydrogels have emerged, aiming to enhance their strength, drug release efficiency, and therapeutic effectiveness [6,27]. These hybrid hydrogels, featuring improved formulations, are particularly tailored for biomedical applications.

Hydrogels can be formulated either externally before application or directly within the body, such as through the injection of precursor solutions that gel in situ. The latter offers several benefits, including minimally invasive procedures, adaptable shaping due to the fluidity of the precursor, and the ability to incorporate cells or bioactive molecules [13,28]. To make hydrogels viable for real-world biomedical use, efficient and straightforward fabrication methods are crucial. Based on how their polymer chains are crosslinked, hydrogels are typically classified as either physically or chemically crosslinked or a combination of both [29,30]. Over the past decade, a variety of physical and chemical crosslinking methods have been developed for fabricating these materials. Physically crosslinked hydrogels are typically formed through interactions like ionic or hydrophobic forces, non-covalent forces like hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interactions, and host-guest chemistry under mild conditions but tend to be mechanically weak and lack long-term stability in biological environments [31]. In cases where less permanent structures are needed, physical crosslinking methods which allow properties like shear-thinning and time-dependent disintegration might be appropriate. In contrast, chemically crosslinked hydrogels, often formed through photopolymerization or enzymatic reactions, exhibit superior mechanical strength, durability, and stability. However, these chemical approaches may involve initiators or enzymes that raise toxicity concerns and can suffer from low specificity, potentially leading to unintended interactions with encapsulated drugs, proteins, or cells. To enable hydrogel formation, biopolymers typically require chemical modifications [32]. These modifications target reactive groups on the polymer backbone such as amines, hydroxyls, and carboxyl groups enabling a range of crosslinking strategies, including thermal, redox, photochemical, and simple mixing approaches. The mechanical behavior of the resulting hydrogels is influenced by the extent of biopolymer modification, the concentration used, the crosslinking chemistry, and the degree of network formation. For robust hydrogels, covalent crosslinking methods like free radical polymerization or click chemistry are often employed. On the other hand, reversible covalent interactions such as Schiff base formation or disulfide bonding can provide both stability and dynamic properties like self-healing [33].

Hydrogels can be applied in vivo either after purification and sterilization or directly in injectable form. For injectable applications, it is particularly important to avoid toxicity from leftover reagents, catalysts, or byproducts from the crosslinking process [34]. Moreover, fast and efficient gelation is necessary to ensure proper hydrogel formation at the site of application. Bioorthogonal crosslinking techniques offer a solution by enabling hydrogel formation without disturbing native biological processes [33]. These chemoselective reactions commonly known as click chemistry were first described by Barry Sharpless in 2001 and are characterized by high yield, specificity, and minimal purification requirements [35]. In recent years, click chemistry has emerged as a highly promising approach for hydrogel fabrication, thanks to its rapid reaction rates, excellent selectivity, and mild conditions [36–38]. This technique enables the creation of hydrogels with diverse structures and patterns. Its distinctive bioorthogonal nature makes the resulting

hydrogels exceptionally well-suited for incorporating bioactive components such as living cells, proteins, and therapeutic agents. Initial work focused on the copper-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition, notably demonstrated in hydrogel synthesis by Hilborn and Hawker in 2006 [39,40]. These reactions offer fast gelation and easy post-polymerization modification, which are highly appealing features. However, the use of metal catalysts in biomedical materials raises concerns, as even trace metal residues such as copper can compromise biocompatibility [41]. Although metal removal is relatively straightforward in soluble systems, it is far more challenging in crosslinked networks especially because triazoles can bind metals tightly, complicating purification.

To avoid these challenges, researchers have turned to metal-free click reactions such as strain-promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition, radical-mediated thiol-ene chemistry, and Diels-Alder reactions, which has enabled the formation of hydrogels with high efficiency and selectivity under mild conditions in the absence of toxic metal catalysts [42–45]. These reactions are particularly appealing for biomedical hydrogel fabrication (Fig. 1). Recent literature highlights this growing trend, with metal-free click chemistry becoming the preferred route for making biocompatible hydrogels [46–48]. Several advantages and drawbacks of the click reactions are listed in Table 1. Combining multiple polymer networks such as interpenetrating network (IPN) structures offers another layer of tunability to meet the requirements of specific applications.

In the context of hydrogel development, “click” chemistry has greatly expanded the possibilities for creating materials with custom structures and properties. Its user-friendly nature has also made hydrogel fabrication more accessible to researchers from diverse backgrounds. Rather than referring to a single reaction, “click” chemistry encompasses a broad range of highly efficient and selective chemical transformations. This review presents a selection of studies that uses various types of click chemistry reactions for the hydrogel synthesis for biomedical applications from the last decade (Fig. 2).

2. Click reactions in hydrogel synthesis for biomedical applications

2.1. Metal-catalyzed click reactions

2.1.1. Copper-Catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition (CuAAC)-based hydrogels

A modified form of the Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition, the CuAAC reaction involves copper-catalyzed coupling of azides and alkynes to form 1,2,3-triazoles [49]. In the presence of copper, the reaction proceeds rapidly and selectively, yielding only the 1,4-disubstituted isomer (Fig. 3A). These triazole products exhibit excellent chemical stability, making CuAAC a powerful tool for constructing hydrogel networks and other polymeric materials used in biomedical applications also due to its efficiency, selectivity, and biocompatibility under controlled conditions [50]. One of its main advantages in hydrogel synthesis is its ability to form strong, covalent crosslinks between polymer chains under mild, often aqueous, conditions which is ideal for biomedical applications such as tissue engineering, drug delivery, and wound healing. The high specificity of CuAAC allows precise control over network architecture, enabling the creation of hydrogels with tunable mechanical properties, and porosity. Moreover, the reaction can be spatially and temporally controlled, allowing for patterned or injectable hydrogels. The main immunological concern in CuAAC systems is the residual copper. Even trace Cu(I)/Cu(II) ions can promote reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation and inflammatory signaling and induce macrophage activation. Although triazole rings are generally considered bioinert, they are not naturally occurring motifs in mammalian tissues, and their long-term immunological neutrality remains incompletely characterized in chronic implantation settings. As the triazole linkages are highly chemically stable and resistant to hydrolysis, oxidation, and enzymatic cleavage under physiological

Fig. 1. Main biomedical application areas of bio-based hydrogels and click reactions used for their synthesis.

conditions, degradation typically proceeds through cleavage of the biopolymer backbone rather than scission of the triazole crosslinks. This can lead to slow bulk erosion and potential persistence of small triazole-containing fragments in vivo. Persistent crosslinked domains may promote fibrotic encapsulation if degradation is slower than tissue remodeling. Incorporation of hydrolytically labile esters or enzyme-sensitive peptide spacers is often necessary to tune degradation kinetics. Nonetheless, CuAAC remains a valuable method for developing structurally robust and functional hydrogels in both research and translational contexts.

Neffe and coworkers used CuAAC for a gelatin-based hydrogel formation using an alkyne functionalized gelatin which was crosslinked using a diazide, namely 4,4'-diazido-2,2'-stilbenedisulfonic acid or 1,8-diazidooctane in the presence of sodium ascorbate and CuSO_4 catalyst system [51]. The rigid 4,4'-diazido-2,2'-stilbenedisulfonic acid crosslinker resulted in hydrogels with Young's moduli of 50-390 kPa and swelling degrees of 150-250%, while the more flexible 1,8-diazidooctane yielded hydrogels with Young's moduli of 125-280 kPa and swelling degrees of 225-470%. Although CuAAC reaction is not favorable due to the toxicity of Cu catalyst, the fabricated gelatin hydrogels did not show cytotoxic properties. The presence of remaining free azide and alkyne moieties on the gelatin backbone and crosslinker also allows the further attachment of biomolecules through covalent bonding, which makes these multifunctional materials suitable for biomedical applications. Chitosan/hyaluronic acid hydrogels were also prepared through one pot triple network composed of triazole linkage, metal-coordination, and chitosan/hyaluronic acid polyion complexation [52]. Alkyne and azide-functionalized hyaluronic acid was crosslinked using CuAAC. The required Cu(I) catalyst is generated from Cu(II) in the chitosan-Cu complex upon addition of sodium ascorbate, leading to the solubilization of CS, and ionic gelation. The salt containing aqueous solution favors polyion complex formation of chitosan and hyaluronic acid without precipitation. These triple-network hydrogels showed biocompatibility based on studies with chondrocyte cells.

An interpenetrating hydrogel was prepared by using CuAAC and amine-anhydride click reactions in aqueous conditions [53]. The gel was

synthesized from alkyne-functionalized sodium carboxymethylcellulose, azide-modified chitosan, polylysine, and a ternary copolymer composed of maleic anhydride, acrylamide, and N-tert-butylacrylamide (Fig. 4). The results demonstrated that the IPN-Gel exhibited excellent dual responsiveness to temperature and pH. After 48 hours of incubation with a high concentration of the hydrogel without a chemotherapy drug, namely 5-Fluorouracil (5-Fu), both 4T1 cancer cells and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) maintained viability above 80%, indicating that the IPN-Gel itself is non-toxic. As the concentration of free 5-Fu and hydrogel/5-Fu increases, cell viability decreases. At the 24-hour mark, there is no significant difference in cytotoxicity between free 5-Fu and the hydrogel/5-Fu formulation for either cell type. However, after 48 hours, the IPN/5-Fu exhibits a notably stronger tumor-inhibitory effect compared to free 5-Fu due to the sustained release of 5-Fu enabled by the drug carrier system. This work presents a new and straightforward method for fabricating IPN-Gels and highlights their significant potential in drug delivery applications.

2.2. Metal-free click reactions

Metal-free click reactions have emerged as powerful tools in chemical biology and biomaterials science because they enable rapid and selective bond formation without the need for transition-metal catalysts [45,46]. Traditional click reactions such as copper-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition offer high efficiency and regioselectivity, but the presence of metal catalysts can cause cytotoxicity and interfere with biological processes, limiting their applicability in living systems. In contrast, metal-free click reactions, including strain-promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition, inverse electron-demand Diels-Alder, thiol-ene coupling, and related reactions proceed under mild, aqueous, and physiological conditions while maintaining high chemoselectivity and reaction efficiency. These reactions are often bioorthogonal, meaning they can occur in complex biological environments without perturbing native biochemical pathways. As a result, metal-free click chemistry has become particularly valuable for applications such as biomolecule labeling, hydrogel formation, drug delivery, and in vivo imaging. Their

Table 1
Advantages and drawbacks of click reactions

Click Reactions	Advantages	Drawbacks
CuAAC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very high efficiency Quantitative yields 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of cytotoxic Cu(I) catalyst Metal removal required for biomedical use
SPAAC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Copper-free Bioorthogonal Mild conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slower in biological media Strained alkynes expensive and hydrophobic Slower than CuAAC Side reactions with thiols Non-regioselective
Thiol-ene (Photoactivated)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fast High efficiency Spatial control via light 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cytotoxicity (radicals and photoinitiator) Light penetration limitations
Thiol-Michael	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mild conditions No catalyst needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensitive to pH Slower than radical thiol-ene Reactivity to thiols in vivo
Thiol-yne (Photoactivated)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher crosslink density than thiol-ene 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cytotoxicity (radicals and photoinitiator) Possible over-crosslinking
Thiol-yne (Nucleophilic)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rapid gelation Catalyst-free Proceeds under mild/basic conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slower kinetics Sensitive to pH Limited substrate scope compared to radical thiol-yne
DA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoids radicals Catalyst-free Mild conditions Thermally reversible Self-healing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relatively slow kinetics Requires elevated temperature for reversibility Equilibrium-controlled
iedDA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extremely fast kinetics Highly bioorthogonal No catalyst In vivo gelation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tetrazines may be unstable Strained dienophiles costly Possible gas release (N₂) affects network homogeneity
Schiff Base	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dynamic/reversible Self-healing and injectable systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not-bioorthogonal Hydrolytically unstable at physiological pH Relatively low equilibrium constant
Amino-yne	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No catalyst required Catalyst-free Mild conditions Stable linkages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possible reaction with biological amines Substrate-dependent May require activated alkynes Slower than classical click reactions
Oxime	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Faster and more stable than imine/hydrazone Suitable injectability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires aldehyde/ketone functionalization Aldehydes may react with biological amines Moderately reversible under acidic conditions
Hydrazone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dynamic and reversible Self-healing Tunable kinetics via pH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lower stability than oxime Slower gelation compared to oxime Hydrolysis at physiological conditions

high yields, minimal by-products, catalyst-free conditions, and excellent biocompatibility make them especially suitable for biomedical and polymeric material design.

2.2.1. Strain-promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition (SPAAC)-based hydrogels

The traditional CuAAC reaction is the most commonly used “click” reaction, but since copper ions are used as the catalyst, biological toxicity is a major drawback. To eliminate the cytotoxicity concerns associated with copper catalysts, Bertozzi’s team developed SPAAC, which uses strained cyclooctynes to react with azides (Fig. 3B) [54].

Fig. 2. Types of hydrogel fabrication mechanisms based on the click reaction chemistry.

Fig. 3. A) CuAAC, B) SPAAC reactions.

SPAAC offers a range of advantages that make it highly valuable in biological and materials chemistry. SPAAC proceeds under mild, catalyst-free conditions, often at room or body temperature, making it especially suitable for live-cell labeling, in vivo imaging, and drug delivery [55,56]. The reaction exhibits fast kinetics compared to uncatalyzed cycloadditions and provides excellent selectivity and bioorthogonality, meaning it reacts cleanly in complex biological environments without interfering with native biomolecules and it can be used in aqueous environments. SPAAC is also compatible with sensitive targets such as proteins, DNA, and antibodies, preserving their structure and function during conjugation. SPAAC displays long-term compatibility compared to CuAAC as the cyclooctyne rings used in SPAAC generally show excellent long-term stealth properties in vivo. Additionally, the reaction typically requires minimal purification, as it generates few byproducts and avoids metal contamination. These features make SPAAC especially appealing for applications where biocompatibility, simplicity, and efficiency are critical. However, SPAAC has some limitations, such as the high cost, bulkiness and hydrophobicity of the strained cyclooctyne reagents. Additionally, the reaction rate is generally slower than CuAAC. In some cases, off-target reactivity or poor solubility of the strained alkyne can affect the efficiency or specificity of the reaction. Despite these drawbacks, SPAAC remains a valuable tool in bioorganic and materials chemistry for applications where biocompatibility is critical. The absence of toxic metal catalysts allows SPAAC hydrogels to be safely used in vivo, enabling direct encapsulation of sensitive biological components like cells, proteins, or drugs. These hydrogels exhibit fast gelation kinetics, excellent bioorthogonality, and tunable mechanical properties, making them ideal for injectable systems, tissue engineering scaffolds, wound dressings, and drug delivery

Fig. 4. A) Preparation process, B) synthesis mechanism of polymers and IPN-Gel. Reprinted with permission from [53].

platforms. SPAAC produces triazole linkages similar in stability to CuAAC but eliminates metal catalysts. Degradation therefore depends primarily on backbone hydrolysis or enzymatic cleavage using enzyme-cleavable spacers.

Ramezani and coworkers introduced azide and dibenzocyclooctyne (DBCO) units to a citric acid-modified hydroxyethyl cellulose and obtained crosslinked hydrogels via SPAAC [57]. The hydrogels offered a swelling degree of around 650%, Young's modulus of around 10 MPa and tensile strength of 0.43 MPa, which were comparable with those of normal cartilage tissue. In vitro biological assays, such as MTT analysis, cellular attachment, histological staining, and real-time PCR confirmed the biocompatibility, chondrogenic ability, and bioorthogonal features of the hydrogels, which showed cell viability around 90%. These remarkable biological and mechanical properties similar with the native cartilage tissues make these materials amenable for cartilage tissue

engineering. Barrias and coworkers designed a hydrogel crosslinking strategy based on partial crosslinking of cyclooctyne-modified alginate with azide functionalized proline-valine-glycine-leucine-isoleucine-glycine (PVGLIG) peptides together with ionic crosslinking of the hydrogel [58]. Azido-RGD was also attached on the alginate via SPAAC in order to enhance cell adhesion (Fig. 5A). The incorporation of both RGD and PVGLIG which are sensitive to matrix metalloproteinase (MMP) in the alginate hydrogels were capable of producing their own pericellular ECM, expressed MMP-2 and 14, and secreted PVGLIG-degrading enzymes. Besides the high cell viability of the hydrogels, their biochemical and mechanical properties of were adjustable by the amounts of each component or crosslinking density, which is beneficial for use as 3D matrices in tissue engineering applications. Myung and colleagues presented an in situ hydrogels as corneal stroma substitute using SPAAC reaction. Collagen modified with azide and DBCO units

Fig. 5. Formation of A) cell adhesive MMP-sensitive alginate hydrogels, B) crosslinked collagen gel matrix formation by SPAAC, C) the hyaluronic acid and collagen-based IPN. Adapted with permission from [58–60].

was crosslinked through the bioorthogonal reaction to form collagen hydrogels which were then encapsulated with keratinocytes (Fig. 5B) [59]. The SPAAC-crosslinked gel was observed to be relatively more transparent than non-crosslinked gel. The storage modulus of the crosslinked hydrogels was around 81.05 ± 10.72 Pa which is reasonable for culturing rabbit keratinocytes. Eventually, the hydrogels allowed multilayered re-epithelialization of resident rabbit keratinocytes over their surface. In another study the same group demonstrated a simultaneously in-situ forming IPN through thiol-ene and SPAAC reactions by mixing thiolated hyaluronic acid, methacrylated hyaluronic acid, azido-modified collagen and dibenzocyclooctyne (DBCO)-modified collagen at the same time under ambient conditions without any other catalysts or initiators (Fig. 5C) [60]. The resultant hydrogel structures displayed high biocompatibility over 80% with good cell adhesive property. Ex vivo studies showed that the gels could fill the corneal wounds in rabbit corneas, restore the curvature of the cornea and form a smooth contour on its surface. In vivo studies also demonstrated that the prepared network hydrogels promoted epithelial overgrowth, and decreased myofibroblast activity in the injured stroma, making them promising for corneal wound healing applications.

The same group also prepared injectable, in situ-forming hyaluronic acid-collagen (HA-Col) hydrogel reinforced with bioorthogonally crosslinked nanoclusters in order to regenerate corneal defects [61]. Human serum albumin nanoclusters surface functionalized with DBCO moieties were used due to their high aqueous solubility, optical clarity, and drug-loading capacity and were loaded with prednisolone acetate as a model small-molecule drug and HGF as a representative growth factor. The hydrogel matrix was fabricated through the bioorthogonal SPAAC reaction between azide-modified collagen, azide-modified hyaluronic acid and DBCO-modified nanoclusters within minutes. Biocompatibility and the ability to support cell proliferation were confirmed using

primary human corneal epithelial cells. In rabbit corneal models, rapid re-epithelialization was observed both ex vivo and in vivo over the hydrogel surface, accompanied by expression of key epithelial and stromal markers (CD44, CK12, CK14, α -SMA, Tuj-1, and ZO-1) and the development of a stratified, multilayered epithelial structure. The hydrogel retained its structural integrity for at least 14 days and progressively remodeled into a transparent stromal-like tissue by 56 days, representing a promising therapeutic platform for deep stromal corneal repair. The conjugation of epidermal growth factor to the HA-Col hydrogel through a photo-cleavable linkage allowed the release the growth factor under mild intensity UV light ($2-5$ mW/cm², 365 nm), providing the proliferation and migration of corneal epithelial cells in vitro and in vivo, the remodeling of stromal layers, and anti-scarring effects, with minimal α -SMA and robust aldehyde dehydrogenase (ALDH3A1) expression (Fig. 6A) [62]. Proper differentiation of the regenerated epithelium following healing was assessed by examining the expression of the corneal epithelial marker CK12. The remodeled cornea demonstrated complete restoration of normal thickness and lamellar organization, with no evidence of epithelial hyperplasia. Normal differentiation of the regenerated epithelia after healing was evaluated by expression of the corneal epithelial biomarker, CK12.

More recently, they investigated the effect of reaction type on corneal wound healing via fabricating crosslinked HA-Col hydrogel by photochemistry and bioorthogonal chemistry [64]. For UV gel, methacrylated HA and methacrylated Col were crosslinked under UV light with an intensity at 2 mW/cm², while bioorthogonal gels were obtained as a result of SPAAC reaction between a DBCO-collagen and azide-hyaluronic acid. In vivo corneal wound studies in rats and rabbits demonstrated that HA-Col UV-crosslinked gels created a less supportive healing microenvironment for keratectomized corneal stroma compared with HA-Col click gels of identical composition. This difference was

Fig. 6. A) Schematic illustration of PC-HACol hydrogel treatment. B) CLSM images of sections of reconstructed tissues on day 25 after the treatments with ADSCxGels, N3[+]ADSC-loaded control gels, and N3[+]ADSC-loaded Matrigel. Scale bars: 50 μ m. Adapted with permission from [62][63].

attributed to the combined effects of UV irradiation, free radical generation, photoinitiator residues, and associated side products, all of which impose additional stress on resident keratocytes. Notably, the HA-Col click gel significantly accelerated corneal re-epithelialization, whereas the HA-Col UV gel did not enhance epithelial closure, likely due to ROS formation during UV curing. Corneas treated with the HA-Col click gel exhibited greater F-actin expression, while in the HA-Col UV group, F-actin filaments were predominantly localized to the basal region of cuboidal epithelial cells. Furthermore, the click-crosslinked gel markedly improved epithelial morphology and overall tissue quality. Within the stromal layer, HA-Col click treatment led to reduced myofibroblast formation compared to the UV-crosslinked counterpart. Consistently, after two months, the click gel group showed the lowest corneal opacity among all groups. At the two-month time point, corneal epithelial thickness in rabbits recovered to 101% of normal with the HA-Col click gel, compared to 92% with the HA-Col UV gel. Additionally, only trace amounts of click gel remained in the neo-stromal region, indicating effective matrix remodeling and turnover within the corneal tissue.

A hyaluronic acid-based hydrogel was also prepared via SPAAC between cyclooctyne and azide groups created on hyaluronic acid to fabricate tunable hydrogels [65]. By systematically analyzing the effect

of crosslinking density, a broad range of stable, rapidly forming hydrogels with tunable stiffness from 0.5 to 45 kPa was achieved in 1-15 minutes. These hydrogels exhibited high cell viability over 95% after 7 days and were successfully used for 3D culture of L929 fibroblasts and human adipose-derived stromal cells (hASCs). Additionally, these hydrogels allowed for customizable compositions through the incorporation of bioactive peptides or co-crosslinking with other glycosaminoglycans, such as chondroitin sulfate, making them highly adaptable for studying cell-material interactions. To showcase their potential, the impact of hydrogel composition and stiffness on hASC secretory behavior under inflammatory conditions was examined. Findings revealed that HA enhanced the release of various immunomodulatory factors, highlighting the platform's promise for future material-assisted cell therapies and advanced cell-material studies. Nagahama and co-workers applied metabolic glycoengineering to create cell crosslinked hydrogels and demonstrated that chemicals can be introduced into cell-surface glycans via covalent bonds in a bioorthogonal manner (Fig. 6B) [63]. These cell crosslinked hydrogel system could be adapted to create stem cell-integrated biohybrid materials for use in *in vivo* tissue engineering. DBCO-modified alginate was crosslinked with azide-containing human breast adipose stem cells for hydrogel production. The bio-orthogonal crosslinked hydrogels showed higher cell viability compared

to physically crosslinked samples, ranging from 86 to 94% for 7 days of cell culture. The effectiveness of covalent stem cell-integrated biohybrid materials for tissue regeneration was evaluated in a mouse model of severe skeletal muscle injury. Notably, tissues regenerated using the covalent biohybrid materials showed expression of MYH3, a key marker of muscle cell development, while tissues treated with conventional physical stem cell-loaded materials or Matrigel showed no such expression. This suggests that the covalent integration method promotes targeted stem cell differentiation within the body. Overall, these findings highlight the promise of covalent stem cell-integrated biohybrid materials for *in vivo* tissue engineering, offering both integration with host tissue and controlled differentiation.

Recently, Kim, Koo and coworkers developed a lacuna-mimic system composed of human-derived nasal septal chondrocytes (hNCs), tannic acid and click chemistry-based injectable hydrogel (Fig. 7) [66]. The hydrogel is composed through the SPAAC reaction between DBCO-gelatin, DBCO-4-arm polyethylene glycol (PEG) and azide-4-arm-PEG. Lacuna-mimic hNC clusters were fabricated as a result of the binding ability of tannic acid and the resultant clusters were encapsulated in a hydrogel. The hydrogel showed a swelling ratio of 260%, which was kept constant maintained for 3 days and decreased to 204, 185, and 163% at 7, 14 and 21 days, respectively. These findings indicate that hNCs can be effectively encapsulated within the hydrogel and remain stably retained *in vivo*. Importantly, encapsulation of lacuna-mimicking hNC clusters within the click-crosslinked hydrogel markedly enhanced collagen type II expression, reduced collagen type I levels, and upregulated Sox 9 expression, thereby promoting chondrogenic differentiation. In a rat osteochondral defect model, animals treated with lacuna-mimetic hNC clusters embedded in the click hydrogel demonstrated substantial defect filling and enhanced cartilage regeneration at both 4 and 8 weeks post-implantation. Histological and immunohistochemical evaluations further verified successful cartilage repair, as evidenced by elevated expression of collagen type II, connective tissue mucin, and glycosaminoglycans.

More recently, Myung, Heilshorn and colleagues introduced an IPN composed of two distinct types of collagen networks, each characterized by unique crosslinking methods and microstructures in order to facilitate the spreading of encapsulated cells while maintaining the structural stability of the gels [67]. The first network is a physically self-assembled fibrillar collagen structure that supports the spreading of embedded

human corneal mesenchymal stromal cells while the second network consists of an amorphous collagen matrix that is covalently crosslinked using bioorthogonal chemistry, between collagen-azide and PEG-DBCO. The stiffness of the resultant hydrogel, was higher than that of either physically self-assembled or SPAAC collagen on their own. All hydrogels displayed high cell viability over 90% over 5 days of human corneal mesenchymal stromal cells were encapsulation. The designed IPN hydrogel is not only fibrillar but it contains an amorphous, covalently crosslinked SPAAC collagen component that fills the void spaces between fibrils. The ability of corneal MSCs to locally reorganize collagen fibrils and spread within the IPN suggests that close-range interactions between cells and fibrils are preserved, supporting critical cellular functions. In another study they followed a different approach in order to fabricate bioorthogonally crosslinked collagen hydrogels that preserve their fibrillar network [68]. For this purpose, the group followed the strategy of modifying collagen with azides in the gel-phase, at 37 °C. The collagen matrix is formed through a sequential crosslinking process, in which the modified collagen first physically assembles into fibers and then is covalently crosslinked. via SPAAC reaction between a gel-phase azidized collagen and DBCO-PEG leading to a fibrillar SPAAC-crosslinked collagen networks which was favorable for high viability and spreading of encapsulated corneal MSCs. This approach strengthens the stability of the cell-laden collagen hydrogel against cell-induced contraction and enzymatic degradation.

2.2.2. Thiol-based reactions

2.2.2.1. Photoactivated thiol-ene reaction-based hydrogels.

Thiol-ene reactions, involving the addition of thiol groups to alkenes, are initiated by light or heat and yield highly selective, near-quantitative conversions (Fig. 8A) [69,70]. These reactions can occur in aqueous environments and offer excellent spatial and temporal control, making them ideal for tuning hydrogel architecture. Although ultraviolet light is commonly used to initiate these reactions, biocompatibility can be improved by adjusting light intensity and wavelength. Thiol-ene chemistry is already being explored in medicine, biomedicine, and materials science and proceeds through a stepwise chain-growth polymerization involving three main stages [71]. First, a thiyl radical reacts with the carbon in an alkene group. Next, the thiol group's hydrogen is abstracted by the resulting carbon radical, which is then converted back into a thiyl

Fig. 7. A schematic illustration of click hydrogel encapsulated hNCs clusters for cartilage regeneration. Reprinted with permission from [66].

Fig. 8. A) Thiol-ene, B) Thiol-Michael, C) Photoactivated thiol-yne, D) Nucleophilic thiol-yne reactions.

radical. Finally, the process ends with the coupling of radicals. This type of click reaction forms covalent bonds between thiol (-SH) groups and alkenes molecules with carbon-carbon double bonds such as vinyl, allyl, or norbornene derivatives. The thiol-ene reaction is known for producing materials with low shrinkage, reduced oxygen sensitivity, and rapid reaction kinetics. When multiple functional groups are present, a heterogeneous polymer network may form. The reaction conditions are mild, making it suitable for creating biocompatible hydrogels [72,73]. Various natural and synthetic polymers, including hyaluronic acid, gelatin, alginate, and PEG, can be modified with thiol or ene groups for this purpose. Photoinitiated thiol-ene chemistry is particularly effective for crosslinking in environments that are low in oxygen. This highly efficient and selective reaction resists oxygen inhibition and proceeds quickly, forming uniform hydrogel networks ideal also for bioprinting applications. These photocrosslinked, homogeneous hydrogels offer favorable conditions for encapsulating cells. Norbornene is widely preferred as the "ene" component in hydrogel systems due to its high reactivity and efficiency in thiol-ene photopolymerization [74]. Its strained cyclic structure enables rapid and efficient crosslinking with thiols under mild conditions, producing hydrogels with uniform network structures. Unlike acrylates, norbornene does not homopolymerize, allowing for precise control over gel properties and minimizing unwanted side reactions. Additionally, the thiol-norbornene reaction is bioorthogonal and cytocompatible, making it ideal for biomedical applications such as cell encapsulation, tissue engineering, and drug delivery. The resulting thioether bonds are chemically stable but can be engineered to be degradable. For example, thiol-norbornene hydrogels can be rendered degradable by using peptide crosslinkers that are sensitive to cell-secreted enzymes [75]. Photoinitiators and residual radicals can induce cytotoxicity if not optimized. Oxygen inhibition byproducts and unreacted thiols may influence redox balance and inflammatory responses. However, properly formulated thiol-ene hydrogels generally demonstrate favorable macrophage polarization profiles. They generally show reduced fibrosis compared to traditional free-radical polymerization because they minimize the formation of oxygen-inhibited layers and side products [76]. Because thioether crosslinks are non-reversible, degradation depends on the polymer backbone. Oxidative microenvironments such as wounds may accelerate degradation. Mechanical fatigue under cyclic loading requires further long-term study. Photoinitiator toxicity, residual radicals, light penetration control, and sterility validation under irradiation conditions pose regulatory challenges.

Lin and Greene used orthogonal thiol-norbornene photochemistry using gelatin-norbornene and PEG-thiol to fabricate modularly crosslinked gelatin-based hydrogels as 3D matrices to regulate hepatocellular

carcinoma cell behavior [77]. The modular gelatin-norbornene system enabled separate tuning of mechanical stiffness and biochemical cues. Huh7 hepatocellular carcinoma cells were encapsulated within heparin-functionalized GelNB hydrogels which enabled sustained release of hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) in vitro and reduced overall cellular metabolic activity while significantly improving CYP3A4 activity and urea secretion in encapsulated Huh7 cells. In another study of the group gelatin was dual-functionalized with norbornene and 4-hydroxyphenylacetic acid (HPA), enabling photochemical crosslinking via thiol-norbornene reactions and subsequent tyrosinase-triggered stiffening through HPA dimerization for a dynamic gelatin-hyaluronic acid hybrid hydrogel [78]. The results showed that both HA incorporation and dynamic matrix stiffening independently suppressed pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) cell proliferation, promoted phenotypic alterations consistent with enhanced migration and/or invasion in 3D. mRNA expression profiling further identified gene regulation patterns specific to HA inclusion, matrix stiffening, or their combination. They further modified GelNB with different secondary reactive moieties, including hydroxyphenylacetic acid or carbonylhydrazide for on-demand stiffening, boronic acid for adjusting gel viscoelasticity, and heparin for growth factor binding [79]. Albertsson and colleagues synthesized full interpenetrating hemicellulose hydrogel networks using O-acetyl-galactoglucosaminan (AcGGM) via either free-radical polymerization or a thiol-ene click reaction between thiolated AcGGM and PEG diacrylate [80]. All IPN formulations exhibited faster swelling rates compared to their corresponding single-network hydrogels. Rheological testing showed that AcGGM-based IPNs formed via free-radical polymerization and thiol-ene coupling possessed shear storage moduli about 2.5-5 and 35-40 times greater than single-network precursors, respectively. Starch-based hydrogels were also prepared via thiol-ene reaction using allyl and thiol-bearing starch molecules. The swelling capacity of the hydrogel decreased as the thiol-to-ene ratio was adjusted from 4:1 to 1:1 [81]. Increasing the ene content also led to a reduction in the degradation rate, which dropped from 33.3 wt%/h to 12.5 wt%/h. Additionally, the degradation behavior of the hydrogels was evaluated under varying concentrations of α -amylase. Results showed that higher α -amylase concentrations accelerated the degradation process.

Sedghi and coworkers fabricated biodegradable hydrogels utilizing the thiol-ene reaction between zwitterionic methacrylated chitosan and thiolated graphene oxide nanosheets (Fig. 9A) [82]. The graphene nanosheets could be uniformly trapped in the chitosan matrix and the resultant crosslinked hydrogels possessed improved mechanical properties with Young's moduli up to 32.8 kPa and tensile strength up to 166 kPa, flexibility and electrical conductivity up to 0.35 S/m leading to efficient strain-sensitivity. Moreover, hydrogen bonding between

Fig. 9. A) Formation of zwitterionic methacrylated chitosan/thiolated graphene oxide hydrogel, B) Schematic illustration of photocrosslinking and bio-functionalization of click NorPEC hydrogels via UV light photoinitiated thiol-ene reaction of di-thiol MMP-degradable peptide and norbornene groups on NorPEC. Adapted with permission from [82,84].

graphene and modified chitosan in addition to the electrostatic interaction between zwitterionic groups, modified chitosan and graphene oxide led to self-healing property. The response time and recovery time of the hydrogels as motion sensors were 0.14 s with repeatable cycles. The hydrogels did not show any cytotoxicity against L929 fibroblast cells. According to these remarkable properties, these hydrogels are promising materials in biomedical applications such as health monitoring devices and wearable human motion sensors. Feng and coworkers also used norbornene-modified hyaluronic acid in order to fabricate hydrogels via crosslinking using dithiothreitol (DTT) under blue light irradiation via thiol-ene chemistry in less than 10 s [83]. Rat adipose-derived stem cells (rADSCs) were encapsulated in the hydrogels showed high cell viability and proliferation around 90% at the first day of culture. The hyaluronic acid-based hydrogel loaded with less than 2 million/mL rADSCs possessed a light transmittance of 80% at the 400–800 nm spectrum. Thiol-norbornene based materials are suitable for tissue engineering and regenerative medicine applications. Bartolo, Granja and coworkers synthesized photocrosslinked pectin hydrogels via crosslinking norbornene-functionalized pectin macromers for thiol-ene reaction for the first time (Fig. 9B) [84]. Macromers are transformed into cell-instructive hydrogels in a single-step photo-click reaction using dithiol MMP degradable peptide as the crosslinker and a monothiol cell adhesive RGD peptide for integrin binding. Higher MMP-peptide amount increased the crosslinking density and the shear elastic modulus, reaching a maximum of 446.75 ± 35.66 Pa while decreasing the swelling ratio due to highly entangled and more crosslinked network. Integrating MMP-sensitive peptides into the pectin hydrogel network enables embedded fibroblasts to locally break down the matrix, a critical process that provides space for cell spreading and elongation. RGD peptide was found to increase the spreading and elongation of human neonatal dermal fibroblasts cells cultured with hydrogels. Cell-instructive hydrogels containing embedded dermal fibroblasts and overlaid with keratinocytes facilitated the *in vitro* development of full-thickness skin that closely mimics the structure and appearance of human skin. Two clearly defined regions, representing the dermal and

epidermal layers, were observed, each displaying characteristic markers linked to cell proliferation and ECM production. Overall, the study highlights the promise of 3D click-crosslinked pectin hydrogels for applications in skin tissue engineering.

Major and coworkers prepared a series of crosslinked hyaluronic acid-based hydrogels using different ratios of thiolated and methacrylated hyaluronic acid via thiol-ene reaction [85]. Thiol modification of hyaluronic acid increases the cell adhesion while introduction of thiolated hyaluronic acid in the hydrogel improves the storage modulus and decreases the compressive strength of the samples. It was observed that the degradation and biological properties of thiol-ene crosslinked hydrogel were better than methacrylated HA hydrogel. Biological studies also pointed out that the thiol-ene hydrogels had high cell viability in neuronal and glial cell lines and they can be considered for bioengineering applications.

Thiol-ene reaction was also used to prepare chondroitin sulfate-based hydrogels for cartilage regeneration [86]. Thiolated chondroitin sulfate and hyperbranched PEG were crosslinked via thiol-ene reaction. The developed hydrogels displayed rapid gelation around 3 min and possessed a storage modulus of around 3–4 kPa with a 1% (w/v) concentration of chondroitin sulfate, falling within the optimal range for promoting stem cell chondrogenesis. Furthermore, excellent cell viability and slow degradation rate, good anti-inflammatory activities as well as improved chondrogenesis pointed out the potential of the thiol-ene crosslinked chondroitin sulfate hydrogels for cartilage tissue engineering. Lin and coworkers designed cell-laden hydrogels using gelatin-norbornene-carbohydrazide which can be crosslinked with a thiol-containing macromer via thiol-ene reaction while the crosslinking density of cell-laden thiol-norbornene hydrogels can be dynamically tuned with oxidized dextran or hyaluronic acid through hydrazone click reaction, contributing to gel-stiffening [87]. The incorporation of bioactive oxidized hyaluronic acid in the hydrogels system also led to higher CD44 expression and a higher percentage of proliferating cells in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma-1 spheroids and to a more invasive cancer-associated fibroblast morphology as a result of higher expression

of HYALs and suppression of TIMP-2 secretion. Pectin nanogels were developed as a novel transcutaneous antigen delivery system using norbornene-functionalized pectin, a dithiol crosslinker, and thiolated ovalbumin (OVA) through a thiol-norbornene photo-click reaction followed by ultrasonication [88]. The bulk hydrogel studies showed that the nanogels' physical characteristics and OVA encapsulation efficiency could be tuned by adjusting the crosslinking density and the molar ratio of thiol to norbornene groups. The resulting pectin nanogels were uniform in size around 200 nm diameter and demonstrated good stability at 4 °C. When applied to the skin, OVA-loaded nanogels successfully penetrated the stratum corneum and were distributed within both the epidermis and dermis layers, whereas free OVA could not cross the skin barrier. Furthermore, dendritic cells derived from THP-1 monocytes readily internalized the nanogels, leading to the upregulation of cell maturation markers. These findings suggest that pectin nanogels are effective carriers for transdermal antigen delivery. Gramlich and Morrison formed hydrogels with interpenetrating networks from norbornene-functionalized carboxymethyl cellulose and cellulose nanofibrils (CNF), crosslinking via a UV-initiated thiol-ene reaction in the presence of thiol crosslinkers [89]. Swelling in water ranged widely, from over 150% in CNF-free formulations to less than 15% when 50% CNFs were included. Norbornene-carboxymethyl cellulose and CNFs worked together synergistically, generating hydrogels with compressive moduli between 1 and 150 kPa, matching those of various biological tissues. A novel rapid hemostatic dressing with high biocompatibility was developed using carboxymethyl chitosan modified with methacrylic anhydride and cysteamine-functionalized chondroitin sulfate which were crosslinked through thiol-ene click chemistry [90]. The relative blood clotting index of the resultant hydrogel dressing decreased by 53% and 29% compared to only chitosan-based dressings and commercial hemostatic gelatin sponge, respectively. In a rat liver bleeding model, the dressing achieved rapid hemostasis, reducing blood loss by 92% compared to the untreated control and commercial the gelatin sponge. Additionally, the chitosan/chondroitin sulfate-based dressing showed superior platelet adhesion and demonstrated good hemocompatibility and cell viability >80%. These findings suggest that the composite dressing holds strong potential as a rapid-acting hemostatic material. A chitosan hydrogel was prepared via thiol-ene reaction using chitosan methacrylate and sulfhydrated chitosan [91]. Highest swelling was observed during the first 3 h, reaching equilibrium around 7 h. The adhesive strength and compressive moduli varied between 33.4 ± 0.9 kPa to 37.3 ± 0.71 kPa and between 5.3 ± 0.3 kPa to 7.8 ± 0.1 kPa, respectively. The developed hydrogels demonstrated strong antimicrobial activity against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Additionally, the CMS hydrogels showed excellent biocompatibility, as confirmed by cytotoxicity and cell proliferation assays using L929 fibroblasts and ADSCs. In vivo studies using a full-thickness skin defect model in rats further assessed the hydrogel's therapeutic effects. The hydrogels also effectively promoted new blood vessel formation, dermal tissue repair, and epidermal regeneration, revealing their potential as wound healing biomaterials.

Preparation of gelatin methacrylamide-based hydrogels via free radical photopolymerization and photo-induced thiol-ene reaction was compared and thiol-ene systems were found to display exhibited higher stiffness and higher swelling capacity than free radical photopolymerized networks.[92] On the other hand, in vitro studies using Caco-2 cells exhibited that cell adhesion and proliferation performed better in photo-cured hydrogels than thiol-ene hydrogels. Injectable hydrogels were formed by thiol-functionalized gelatin and β -cyclodextrin-vinyl sulfone crosslinker, via thiol-ene chemistry for hydrophobic anti-inflammatory drug loading, namely, dexamethasone [93]. Studies showed that higher concentration of crosslinker resulted in faster gelation, higher stiffness, lower swelling, smaller pore size and lower degradation rate. Moreover, drug release slowed to 48% from 66% after 26 days when crosslinker ratio was decreased from 5 to 3%. Hydrogels also showed high cell viability and reduced burst release of the drug,

which makes them suitable for drug delivery. An antibacterial-antioxidative hydrogel was prepared using thiol-ene reaction between a thiolated gelatin, methacrylated silk fibroin and (-)-epigallocatechin gallate-copper ionic-carrageenan nanoparticles under UV irradiation [94]. The resultant hydrogels demonstrated good mechanical properties with a maximum stress of 16 kPa, an elastic modulus of 35.2 kPa, a maximum compressive stress of 334.1 kPa and a compressive modulus of 18.2 kPa. They also showed high cell viability, antibacterial and antioxidant properties as well as ability of metal-polyphenol catalyzing RSNOs to generate nitric oxide. Results pointed out that the incorporation of metal-polyphenol complex contributed to the wound healing rate of the hydrogels with better epithelialization and angiogenesis, making them suitable for wound healing applications. Lin and coworkers crosslinked hydrogels by orthogonal click chemistry through first creating gelatin-heparin macromer via iedDA between tetrazine groups on heparin and norbornene groups on gelatin, followed by thiol-norbornene photopolymerization using poly(ethylene glycol)-tetra-thiol or macromer-thiolated hyaluronic acid (Fig. 10).[95] The system was aimed for encapsulating and differentiating induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) and thiol-norbornene photopolymerization is preferred over iedDA for crosslinking because it shortens gelation time, which is important for maintaining the viability of delicate iPSCs. Importantly, the content of the gelatin macromer remained constant at 5 wt%, increasing PEG4SH from 0.6 wt% to 1.4 wt% raised the hydrogel's storage modulus from approximately 1.5 kPa to around 3.5 kPa. hiPSCs were successfully encapsulated in gelatin-based thiol-norbornene hydrogels, maintaining high cell viability around 86-88%. Within the hydrogels, the hiPSCs formed proliferative clusters resembling embryoid bodies and hydrogels effectively supported the differentiation of neuroectoderm, mesoderm, and definitive endoderm lineages, although they were less effective for non-neural ectoderm differentiation. Additionally, incorporating heparin into the gelatin-based hydrogels slightly reduced PAX6 expression during neuroectoderm differentiation but enhanced the development of neural rosette structures. The findings also indicate that these multifunctional gelatin-based hydrogels are especially promising for promoting definitive endoderm lineage differentiation.

Chitosan hydrogels as wound dressings were prepared via crosslinking methacrylated chitosan and 2,2'-(ethylenedioxy) diethanethiol under visible light [96]. Mechanical testing provided optimal tensile strength value of 14 kPa and elongation at break percentage of 111%. The in vitro experiments displayed good cytotoxicity and antimicrobial activity. The healing effect of the hydrogels were in vivo tested on mice wounds and it was observed that the hydrogel was almost 2 times more effective in wound healing compared to the natural-healing during the first 5 days. Thiol-ene reaction was also used to synthesize gellan gum-based hydrogels for ophthalmic delivery by Amiraghoubi and coworkers [97]. Thiolated gellan gum was reacted with PEG diacrylate using Irgacure 2959 as a photoinitiator in order to form hydrogels which were then loaded with chitosan nanoparticles containing timolol maleate. The drug release rate decreased with an increase in the PEG diacrylate amount due to decrease in porosity and pore size. The presence of chitosan nanoparticles resulted in a fast release followed by a slow release for 48 h, providing long-term ocular delivery of timolol maleate. The hydrogels showed high cell viability and ex vivo studies demonstrated that drug penetration through the cornea with hydrogels entrapped with drug-containing chitosan nanoparticle was 42% while it was 27% for drug solution in 48 h. The results indicated their suitability for ocular drug delivery. In another recent study, Chen and coworkers proposed a hybrid system composed of crosslinking methacrylated hyaluronic acid and sulfhydryl kappa-carrageenan via thiol-ene reaction followed by tannic acid loading [98]. Tannic acid significantly improved elastic and viscous properties, enhancing adhesion and wound protection. The hydrogel was subjected to stretching, twisting, bending, extrusion, and water rinsing on pig skin as well as immersing in pH 5 and pH 7.4 solutions and it remained firmly attached to the skin in all cases.

Fig. 10. Schematic illustration of A) GelNB, HepTz and the tetrazine-norbornene iedDA click hydrogel, B) Encapsulation of iPSCs, C) Immunostaining and imaging of cells in Gel, and Gel-Hep hydrogels. Adapted with permission from [95].

The hydrogel showed favorable biocompatibility and significant antibacterial property. Fibroblast migration rate increased to 66.7% from 46% of the control, while angiogenesis was also enhanced up to four times. In vivo wound healing studies showed a nearly-complete healing with complete epithelial junctions and a new epidermis formation within 14 days, pointing its suitability for the treatment of infected wounds. Very recently, an injectable nanocomposite hydrogel was developed for infected wound treatment [99]. This multifunctional system integrates immunomodulatory, antioxidant, and antibacterial properties and the hydrogel is rapidly formed through thiol-ene photoclick crosslinking between allyl glycidyl ether-grafted gelatin and cysteamine-grafted hyaluronic acid loaded with and poly (protocatechualdehyde)-coated gallium-doped (PPA@GaBG) bioactive glass. Within the hydrogel network, the core-shell PPA@GaBG nanoparticles significantly enhanced antioxidant capacity and promoted macrophage polarization toward the pro-healing M2 phenotype. Additionally, Schiff base interactions between PPA and gelatin or surrounding skin tissue improved nanoparticle dispersion, mechanical strength, and tissue adhesion, contributing to effective hemostasis. The PPA coating also mitigated the initial burst release of Ga^{3+} ions observed in GaBG-containing hydrogels, thereby improving biocompatibility while preserving strong antibacterial performance. Owing to these combined functionalities, the PGBGH hydrogel markedly stimulated angiogenesis, granulation tissue formation, and re-epithelialization, while optimizing the collagen III/I deposition ratio and enabling rapid and scarless healing of infected wounds. Overall, this injectable nanocomposite hydrogel represents a highly promising biomaterial platform for wound repair and regenerative medicine applications.

2.2.2.2. Thiol-Michael reaction-based hydrogels. The thiol-Michael addition reaction was first introduced in the 1960s by Allen, Fournier, and Humphlett [100]. This reaction occurs between thiol groups as the nucleophilic donors and electron-deficient alkenes, such as vinyl sulfone, acrylate, or maleimide where the thiol adds to the double bond, forming a thioether linkage (Fig. 8B) [101,102]. However, side reactions such as disulfide bond formation may occur, so protective groups are often used. Recognized as a highly efficient and modular click reaction, thiol-Michael addition typically proceeds under mild, solvent-free conditions and the reaction rate depends on the electron-deficiency of the alkene acceptor. The thiol-Michael reaction enables rapid and

controllable crosslinking of polymer networks and is especially suited for biomedical applications including injectable hydrogels, cell encapsulation, and tissue engineering, because it proceeds without harsh catalysts or byproducts, allowing gelation under physiological conditions. Its versatility allows tuning of mechanical properties and easy incorporation of bioactive molecules. Gelation speed and mechanical properties such as storage modulus can be improved by increasing the pH and the concentration of the thiolate anion. Additionally, varying the chemical groups involved allows for fine-tuning of gelation behavior in this reaction system.

Collagen-based crosslinked injectable hydrogels were introduced through the Michael reaction between a thiol-modified collagen and 8-arm PEG-maleimide [103]. The resultant hydrogels demonstrated shear-thinning and self-healing properties, with only 6% of swelling up to a month. The cell viability of mouse bone marrow stromal and HUVECs were more than 90% after 1 h and respectively around 80 and 70% for up to 4 days indicating their eligibility for tissue engineering and regenerative medicine applications. In a more recent study the same group proposed an injectable collagen-based hydrogel crosslinking via thiol-maleimide Michael reaction between an acetyl thiol-modified collagen and a 8-arm maleimide PEG (Fig. 11A) [104]. The fabricated hydrogels had a transmittance of 96–98%, indicating that it fulfills or even exceeds the requirements for corneal applications. The maximum loss modulus of the hydrogels reached to 184.9 ± 12.2 Pa for thiol:maleimide ratio of 1:0.5 and to 170.0 ± 8.7 Pa for thiol:maleimide ratio of 1:1. The thiol collagen hydrogels were injectable up to 72 h post-mixing of the gel components when stored at room temperature or longer when stored at 4 °C. The hydrogel's biocompatibility is validated in vitro with human corneal epithelial cells, which remain viable and continue to proliferate on the hydrogel surface for at least seven days. In addition, the hydrogel exhibits adhesion strength to soft tissue comparable to that of fibrin glue. It also functions effectively as a sealant for corneal perforations, offering a potential alternative to the off-label use of cyanoacrylate adhesives in such treatments. Overall, these findings highlight the promise of the thiol-collagen hydrogel for future applications as a prefabricated implant, injectable filler, or sealant in corneal repair and regeneration. Hyaluronic acid-based hydrogels were also introduced via a di-crosslinking strategy [105]. Thiolated and maleimide-modified hyaluronic acid were crosslinked to form a hydrogel via Michael reaction, accompanied by the secondary network via

Fig. 11. A) Schematic diagram of injectable HA-SH/HB-PEG hydrogel carrier for CPCs, B) Formation of collagen hydrogels for sealing corneal perforations, C) Hydrogel formation via thiol-Michael addition between HA-Mal, Gel-Mal, and PEGDSH. Adapted with permission from [104,106,107].

oxidation self-crosslinking among thiol groups to form disulfide linkages. The resultant hydrogels were blended with collagen I, which were found to promote cell adhesion, spreading and polyproteoglycan secretion. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments confirmed that hyaluronic acid/collagen I blend hydrogel showed good resistance to degradation, chondrocytes proliferation and matrix secretion. As a result of their cartilaginous tissue formation capability, injectable hyaluronic acid/collagen I hydrogels are promising cartilage filling biomaterials.

Wang and coworkers utilized Michael type thiol-ene reaction between thiol-functionalized hyaluronic acid and hyperbranched PEG multi-acrylate macromer in order to fabricate a hydrogel-based carrier for cartilage-derived progenitor cells (CPCs) (Fig. 11B) [106]. The CPCs were encapsulated within the hydrogels *in situ*, and gelation occurred in 2 minutes. This short gelation time is advantageous for injectable hydrogel systems, as prolonged gelation can lead to uncontrolled dispersion of the hydrogel precursors and encapsulated cells or prevent proper gel formation *in vivo*. *In vitro* studies demonstrated that the encapsulated CPCs kept high cell viability and increased proliferation in the hydrogels, which also accelerated ECM production and maintained the phenotype and function of encapsulated CPCs. These results indicate the high potential of the fabricated hydrogel system as a CPC carrier for cartilage regeneration application. Another type of Michael reaction between acrylate and phosphine groups was utilized to form chondroitin sulfate/gelatin hydrogels using an acrylate-modified chondroitin sulfate and a phosphine-modified gelatin [108]. Higher crosslinking resulted in easier gelation and contrarily less swelling of the hydrogels which possessed pore sizes ranging from 10 to 30 μm and showed high cell viability. Together with their high anti-inflammatory activity, the results suggest their potential in biomedical applications. In a more recent study, Skardal and coworkers fabricated hydrogels by crosslinking maleimide-modified hyaluronic acid and gelatin with thiolated bifunctional PEG crosslinker via Michael addition (Fig. 11C) [107]. The hydrogels displayed a protein release for 12 days, with maximum release

in the first week. Continued proliferation of human dermal fibroblasts or human epidermal keratinocytes cultured in the hydrogels referred to their biocompatibility, which is favorable for their use in tissue engineering applications.

More recently, pectin-based hydrogels were synthesized via thiol-maleimide chemistry between a thiol-modified pectin and a maleimide-modified pectin [109]. The synthesized hydrogel achieved swelling ratios between 44% and 80%, depending on the degree of crosslinking, reaching a maximum at pH 8. The material also displayed notable mechanical strength, with compressive values ranging from 20.8 to 33.2 kPa, which increased with higher crosslinking density. Ibuprofen, used as a model drug, was effectively encapsulated at concentrations up to 337 mg per gram of hydrogel and released in a controlled manner. *In vitro* studies indicated slower drug release under acidic conditions (22%-53% over 6-10 hours) and accelerated release in mildly alkaline environments, aligning with the hydrogel's pH responsive swelling characteristics. These features highlight the hydrogel's suitability for sustained drug delivery. A novel hydrogel derived from carboxymethyl guar gum (CMG) was synthesized using thiol-maleimide click chemistry using CMG-thiol and CMG-maleimide [110]. The resulting hydrogels displayed adjustable crosslinking densities, where increased density led to enhanced mechanical strength and reduced swelling. All formulations exhibited less swelling at low pH and more swelling at higher pH, enabling site-specific drug release. *In vitro* evaluations demonstrated that cell viability for all CMG-SM hydrogel extracts remained well above the acceptable threshold of 70%, even after 48 h of incubation with L929 murine fibroblast cells. Furthermore, antibacterial assays confirmed effectiveness against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Diclofenac sodium, used as a model drug, showed a controlled and sustained release profile, particularly under intestinal conditions. Overall, these results highlight CMG-based hydrogels as a promising platform for targeted and sustained gastrointestinal drug delivery. Brusatin and coworkers designed a hydrogel based on hyaluronic acid functionalized with RGD peptides and incorporating heparin, capable of

simultaneously delivering viable cells, as well as chemokines or cytokines [111]. Hydrogel was prepared via thiol-ene reaction between a thiolated hyaluronic acid, thiolated heparin and 4-arm-PEG-acrylate prefunctionalized with RGD peptide. Depending on the crosslinker ratio, three different hydrogels, namely soft, medium and stiff with storage moduli of 14, 78 and 238 Pa, respectively. The results demonstrated that heparin functionalization significantly regulated cytokine release, notably slowing the release of Interferon- γ compared to the non-heparinized control. After 48 hours, only 30% of Interferon- γ was released from the heparin-functionalized hydrogel, whereas the control released the full 100% within the same period. All hydrogels showed high cell viability with 10% reduction in 48h. The design also displayed tunable degradation rates of about 20% for the stiff hydrogel and 70% for the soft hydrogel within 48 h. This system provides a flexible and effective delivery platform, making it well-suited for therapeutic use across various diseases. An in situ forming hydrogel was composed of acrylated hyperbranched PEG and thiol-modified hyaluronic acid through Michael addition [112]. The resultant hydrogel can serve as an effective platform for the sustained and controlled release of exosomes derived from ADSCs, addressing key challenges such as dosage regulation and preservation of bioactivity in diabetic wound healing. The storage modulus of the hydrogel was around 390 Pa. Exo demonstrated a sustained release from the hydrogel over a 15-day period, with all groups reaching more than 75% cumulative release and showed a peak release at day 7. The hydrogel showed a rapid wound closure rate, which may be attributed to the quick absorption and limited retention of free exosome (Exo), combined with the continuous delivery of Exo from the hydrogel at the wound site. The suggested hydrogel is a promising therapeutic approach for diabetic wound healing. Another study investigated in situ viscoelastic hydrogels developed through thiol-ene Michael addition between thiol-functionalized hyaluronic acid and vinyl sulfone-modified β -cyclodextrin [113]. This study presents an innovative strategy to assess the hydrogel's suitability as a dual drug delivery system capable of accommodating both hydrophilic doxorubicin (DOX) and hydrophobic carvacrol (CRV). CRV was incorporated within the cyclodextrin cavity via host-guest complexation by noncovalent interaction before hydrogel preparation while DOX was added during the gelation process due to its hydrophilicity. DOX was released 100% in 46 h under tumor-like conditions, while carvacrol exhibited an initial burst followed by sustained release. The DOX/CRV-loaded hydrogel significantly reduced cell viability using MDA-MB-231 cancer cells, indicating the antitumor effect. Overall, this injectable, tumor-sensitive hydrogel platform presents a compelling strategy for minimally invasive and tailored cancer treatment.

2.2.2.3. Photoactivated thiol-yne reaction-based hydrogels. Photo-activated thiol-yne click reactions have emerged as an efficient strategy for the synthesis of hydrogels for biomedical applications. In this approach, thiol groups react with alkyne functionalities under UV or visible-light irradiation in the presence of a photoinitiator, generating thioether linkages through a step-growth radical mechanism (Fig. 8C) [114] [115]. The reaction proceeds via the formation of a vinyl sulfide intermediate, which can subsequently react with a second thiol molecule, allowing each alkyne group to participate in two addition reactions and thereby generating networks with high crosslink density and uniform structures. This feature often results in hydrogels with enhanced mechanical strength, tunable network architecture, and rapid gelation kinetics. Moreover, photo-activation enables spatiotemporal control over gel formation, making thiol-yne chemistry particularly suitable for in situ hydrogel formation, cell encapsulation, and tissue engineering applications.

Chiappone, Sangermano and colleagues proposed an alginate hydrogel obtained by a thiol-yne reaction for the first time [116]. Alginate was modified with propargyl groups and crosslinked with 1,4-dithiothreitol or poly(ethylene glycol) dithiol in the presence of a

photoinitiator under UV irradiation. Similar swelling values of around 781-791% were obtained for both crosslinkers while PEG-dithiol resulted in better mechanical properties due to the more deformable cross-linked structure of higher molecular weight PEG. More recently, Malkoch and coworkers proposed a series of hydrogels synthesized through photoactivated thiol-yne click chemistry between alkyne-functionalized hyaluronic acid and ethoxylated trimethylolpropane tris(3-mercaptopropionate) (Fig. 12) [117]. Nanohydroxyapatite was incorporated in the hydrogel precursor at concentrations varying from 10 to 30 wt% relative to the hyaluronan derivative. Gelation occurred under blue light irradiation at 405 nm within 90 s. The incorporation of nanohydroxyapatite resulted in a more regular and uniform pore distribution. The equilibrium swelling varied from 900% to 1200%. The biodegradation tests revealed that all hydrogels showed around 80% of stability which are in line with 3 weeks for the reparative phase of bone healing. The compressive strength of the hydrogels containing 10, 20, and 30% w/w nanohydroxyapatite was respectively of 151 ± 2.13 , 388 ± 1.57 , and 342 ± 10.3 kPa. The hydrogel could effectively be loaded to a cavity in a damp porcine bone model and remained stable for 28 days at 37 °C. The hydrogels also showed high cytocompatibility and calcium deposition, showing potential in bone filling and regeneration.

2.2.2.4. Nucleophilic thiol-yne reaction-based hydrogels. In hydrogel synthesis, the nucleophilic thiol-yne reaction is also used as a click chemistry approach to form covalently crosslinked networks under mild and cytocompatible conditions [118]. In this reaction, thiol groups react with alkyne-functionalized macromers in the presence of a base, forming vinyl sulfide linkages. With an excess of thiol, a second thiol can add across the resulting alkene to yield a bis-thioether, enabling efficient network formation (Fig. 8D). This step-growth mechanism allows precise control over the crosslinking density and network architecture. The reaction is often carried out in aqueous or mixed solvent systems and proceeds rapidly at room temperature without the need for external stimuli like light or heat. Due to its high specificity, fast kinetics, and compatibility with sensitive biomolecules and living cells, the nucleophilic thiol-yne reaction is particularly useful for fabricating biocompatible hydrogels for applications in tissue engineering, drug delivery, and 3D cell encapsulation. Dove and coworkers reported the application of the nucleophilic thiol-yne addition reaction between thiolated hyaluronic acid and alkyne-terminated PEG crosslinkers for hydrogel

Fig. 12. A) Preparation of the hydrogels based on photoinduced thiol-yne click chemistry. B) Cured hydrogel within the bone void. Adapted with permission from [117].

synthesis [119]. They further formed an IPN via incorporating a second more flexible network based on physically crosslinked alginate. The resulting alginate/hyaluronic acid hydrogel demonstrated improved mechanical properties under consecutive cyclic compressions. Alginate incorporation in the network facilitated the sustainment of the load

through the cooperation of both covalent and non-covalent interactions and increased the compressive strength from $17.5 \text{ kPa} \pm 1.33 \text{ kPa}$ up to $1.4 \text{ MPa} \pm 0.55 \text{ MPa}$ and the Young's modulus from $8.8 \text{ kPa} \pm 4.0 \text{ kPa}$ to $67.5 \text{ kPa} \pm 13.9 \text{ kPa}$ compared to those of thiol-yne crosslinked hyaluronic acid hydrogels. The presence of alginate also increased the cell

Fig. 13. A) A schematic illustration of ovarian follicles at developmental stages, the process of follicle isolation from a mouse ovary, and their subsequent encapsulation in thiolated chitosan-co-thiolated hyaluronic acid (CSHS) hydrogel, B) The formation and wound closure ability of alginate/PHMeDOT hydrogels, Reprinted with permission from [120,121].

viability around 4 times after 21 days of incubation in human MSCs cells, overall showing the potential of alginate/hyaluronic acid hydrogels to be used for soft tissue regeneration. Park, Lee and coworkers also designed a hyaluronic acid/chitosan hydrogel for in vitro follicle development through the thiol-yne reaction between thiolated hyaluronic acid, thiolated chitosan and alkyne modified β -cyclodextrins (Fig. 13A) [120]. The resulting hydrogel exhibited follicle survival rate of 85.7% and oocyte viability of 69.7% and maintained spherical morphology of follicle. Matured oocytes with normal appearance of meiotic spindle and chromosome alignment were visible in the hydrogel with increased expression level of folliculogenesis genes TGF β -1 and GDF-9, as well as endocrine-related genes LHCGR, and FSHR. The results suggested the hydrogel system as an alternative method to in vitro follicle culture in the long-term period. Conductive alginate-based hydrogels were introduced via crosslinking thiol-modified alginate and 3-arm alkyne-functionalized PEG through thiol-yne reaction followed by in situ chemical oxidative polymerization of poly(hydroxymethyl-3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PHMeEDOT) (Fig. 13B) [121]. The thiol-yne alginate hydrogels underwent rapid gelation within 3 minutes which is ideal for injectable use. The alginate/PHMeEDOT hydrogels possessed Young's modulus of 116 ± 10.7 kPa which resembles to those of skin tissue. Optimized in vitro experiments using Vero and HFF-1 cells exposed to electrical stimulation of 0.6 V for 20 minutes and demonstrated notable wound closure within 2 hours, suggesting that enhanced electrochemical activity played a crucial role in accelerating wound healing and the promise of the synthesized hydrogels as electrode-like wound dressings for electrically-assisted skin repair.

2.2.3. Diels-Alder (DA) reaction-based hydrogels

The Diels-Alder reaction (DA) was discovered by German scientists Otto Diels and Kurt Alder in 1928, for which they received the Nobel Prize in 1950 [122]. The reaction is a type of cycloaddition involving a conjugated diene and an alkene or alkyne known as a dienophile (Fig. 14A). The reaction occurs through the interaction of molecular orbitals specifically, the highest occupied molecular orbitals of the diene and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals of the dienophile. The driving force behind the reaction is the formation of sigma (σ) bonds, which are more energetically stable than pi (π) bonds. This [4+2] cycloaddition typically takes place between electron-rich dienes like furan derivatives and electron-deficient dienophiles such as maleimide derivatives, resulting in the formation of stable cyclohexene rings. The reaction can proceed under mild, catalyst-free conditions and is thermally reversible [123,124]. Diels-Alder reactions are highly efficient, particularly in aqueous environments, where the reaction rate can be up to 10,000 times faster than in organic solvents. It proceeds through a concerted mechanism under relatively mild conditions, often without the need for catalysts or harsh reagents. The reaction also exhibits

excellent stereoselectivity and regioselectivity, allowing chemists to predict and control the structure of the product with high precision. Additionally, the Diels-Alder reaction is highly versatile, enabling the efficient construction of complex cyclic and polycyclic compounds, which is especially useful in the synthesis of natural products, pharmaceuticals, and advanced materials. These features make the Diels-Alder reaction a fundamental and widely used tool in synthetic organic chemistry. The Diels-Alder reaction is increasingly used in the development of hydrogels due to its efficiency, specificity, and mild reaction conditions. In hydrogel synthesis, it enables covalent crosslinking between polymer chains without requiring harsh chemicals or extreme temperatures, making it ideal for biomedical applications such as drug delivery, tissue engineering, and wound healing [125,126]. The reaction is particularly attractive because it can be reversible, allowing for the creation of self-healing or stimuli-responsive hydrogels. This tunability enhances the performance and adaptability of hydrogels in dynamic biological environments. At physiological temperatures the equilibrium can slowly shift back toward the starting materials. This partial reversibility enables thermally responsive or dynamic degradation. However, maleimide hydrolysis to maleamic acid may alter long-term stability. The degradation rate can be tuned by the electron density of the substituents. Maleimide groups can also react with thiols on serum proteins if unreacted, potentially altering immune recognition. DA-crosslinked hydrogels might show mild inflammatory responses when conversion is high. The potential reversibility provides advantages for self-healing systems but may compromise mechanical stability under prolonged physiological stress. Long-term degradation products must be evaluated for immunogenicity and maleimide-containing reagents may require toxicity profiling. Thermal reversibility may complicate shelf-life validation and sterilization processes. Overall, the Diels-Alder reaction provides a powerful and biocompatible method for engineering advanced hydrogel systems as well as bioinks created for 3D printing applications, with shear-thinning behavior, excellent printability, and long-lasting shape retention.

Shoichet and coworkers aimed to fabricate ECM analog hydrogels for MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell invasion [127]. Crosslinked hydrogels were prepared via Diels-Alder reaction between a furan-modified hyaluronic acid and maleimide-containing MMP-cleavable peptides. Results demonstrated that the invasion of MDA-MB-231 cells was improved in HA/MMPx due to matrix degradation via cell-secreted MMPs. It was observed that cell invasion is driven by an MMP-dependent mechanism, which is diminished in stiffer gels with higher crosslinking density and remains unchanged with varying adhesive ligand concentrations. In softer HA/GAGx hydrogels, cell invasion is lower compared to HA/MMPx hydrogels, highlighting the crucial role of cell-mediated matrix degradation in facilitating invasion. The HA/MMPx hydrogels offer tunable properties, enabling independent control and study of mechanical, chemical, and biological factors. In another study, they replaced the furan moiety on hyaluronic acid with methyl furan and observed that the Diels-Alder reaction was accelerated at pH 7.4 [128]. Moreover, cell viability and uniform cell encapsulation was higher with methyl furan modified hyaluronic acid hydrogels compared to furan-modification. Liu and coworkers developed a hydrogel using Diels-Alder click chemistry combined with dynamic acylhydrazone bond crosslinking to address the limitations of existing chondroitin sulfate hydrogels, such as low mechanical properties and tunability [129]. The acylhydrazone bonds endow the hydrogel with self-healing and injectable properties, while the Diels-Alder click chemistry provides stable covalent crosslinking that enhances in vivo stability and allows for tuning of hydrogel properties. They found out that this dual-crosslinked hydrogel exhibits significantly improved viscoelasticity, rheological behavior, swelling, degradation, injectability, and self-repair capabilities compared to hydrogels crosslinked with only one type of bond. Additionally, the hydrogel supports higher viability and lower apoptosis rates in rat mesenchymal stem cells, and demonstrates strong tissue adhesion in vivo. The cell viability of the dual crosslinked hydrogel was

A) Diels-Alder Reaction

B) Inverse Electron Demand Diels-Alder Reaction

Fig. 14. A) Diels-Alder and B) IEDDA reactions.

80.6% \pm 2.5%, 108.5% \pm 10.1%, and 144.4% \pm 6.7% on 24 h, 48 h and 72 h, respectively. When loaded with BMP-4, the hydrogel served as an effective scaffold for repairing cranial bone defects in rats, promoting new bone formation at the injury site. Overall, this biocompatible, injectable, and self-healing hydrogel with customizable properties offers strong potential for use in cranial bone tissue engineering. Diels-Alder chemistry was also used to prepare crosslinked chitosan-based hydrogels [130]. A double crosslinked hydrogel was developed using coordination interactions and a Diels-Alder click reaction, the former providing self-healing capabilities and control over the crosslinking density while the latter improves the hydrogel's mechanical strength and help preserve its structural stability. The double crosslinked hydrogels showed higher mechanical properties compared to single coordination crosslinking. Furthermore, it was seen that a higher pH enhances the coordination effect, leading to an increased degree of crosslinking within the hydrogel and, consequently, improved mechanical properties. Gabilondo and coworkers prepared starch-based hydrogels via crosslinking furan-modified starch and a bismaleimide compound [131]. Increasing the crosslinker concentration resulted in a more robust network structure, characterized by reduced pore size and increased storage modulus of the final hydrogel. The swelling behavior was found to be primarily influenced by the hydrophilic nature of bismaleimide. To create a nanocomposite hydrogel, graphene nanosheets were incorporated. Upon the addition of 0.2wt% of graphene, storage modulus increased from 3660 \pm 352 Pa for the neat hydrogel to 5680 \pm 362 Pa for the nanocomposite. The nanocomposite also demonstrated notable antimicrobial effects, and a significant increase around ten times in electrical conductivity. They also prepared stimuli-responsive chitosan-based hydrogels via crosslinking furan modified chitosan and polyetheramine derived bismaleimide through Diels-Alder reaction [132]. The hydrogels showed reduced swelling in acidic media, which also provided the sustained delivery and release of model antibiotic Chloramphenicol in simulated gastrointestinal fluid, suggesting their use as targeted drug carriers. In another study, they used a water-soluble tetrafunctional maleimide compound instead of bismaleimide [133]. These hydrogels showed high cell viability and sustained drug release. These results highlight the potential of starch-based hydrogels suitable for diverse biomedical applications. Baharvand and coworkers aimed to design a hydrogel system that combines slow Diels-Alder chemistry and fast in situ thermoresponsive crosslinking that would enhance gelation time, mechanical properties, and the retention of live trans-planted cells [134]. An injectable fully-interpenetrated polymer network was prepared through sequential thermosensitive network formation through the hydrophobic interaction of pluronic segments followed by second covalent network through Diels-Alder reaction between the furan-modified gelatin and bismaleimide PEG chains. The resultant hydrogels possess high compressive strength, shape recovery and self-healing properties as well as cytocompatibility, thermogelling properties and high gel retention, in vivo cell retention and survival. These hydrogels are promising materials for cell therapy and tissue engineering applications. In another study by the same group, dual crosslinking of alginate hydrogels was studied via chemical crosslinking of furan-modified alginate with maleimide functionalized 4-arm PEG via Diels-Alder reaction followed by ionic crosslinking using CaCl₂ [135]. The dual crosslinking contributed to the viscoelastic properties and shape recovery of the hydrogels where ionic crosslinking helped to dissipate energy under load, while the covalent crosslinks increased the strength and prevented severe plastic deformation, even allowing a high amount of recovery in mechanical properties after complete fracture. Besides the outstanding mechanical properties, the hydrogels possessed a high cell viability over 90%, and the remaining free maleimide units are capable of binding to thiol-bearing biomolecules.

Antibacterial alginate hydrogels were introduced by Cao and coworkers via Diels-Alder reaction between a furan-functional alginate and a bismaleimide functional PEG crosslinker [136]. The formed oxynorbornene moiety was further used for the attachment of a cysteine-

terminated antimicrobial peptide through thiol-ene reaction. The hydrogels possessed a stress-at-failure up to 33.01 \pm 4.50 kPa and a compress modulus up to 52.53 \pm 3.16 kPa. The high sterilization rate around 98.5-100% and high cytocompatibility suggest the use of these hydrogels as antibacterial coating for implantable medical devices. García-Astrain and Avérous synthesized alginate-based hydrogels through crosslinking alginate with different degrees of furan substitution and a bismaleimide-containing crosslinker via Diels-Alder chemistry [137]. Higher substitution resulted in higher porosity hydrogels, which also led to higher swelling degree accordingly. The hydrogels displayed their maximum swelling around pH 12-13 because the carboxylate anions on alginate are protonated under low pH which decreases the repulsive forces between alginate chains, eventually causing shrinkage. According to the drug release studies using vanillin as a model drug, all hydrogels released high drug content while low furan-substituted hydrogels showed a burst release in the first hour, while higher furan modification caused a more steady release. The authors also investigated the effect of the crosslinker length and functionality using three different bismaleimides and trismaleimide and revealed that trismaleimide resulted in higher storage moduli values due to more junction points [138]. Previously they have also modified gelatin with furan moiety and crosslinked with a bismaleimide [139]. The resultant hydrogels possessed swelling ratios between 400-600% and mean storage moduli between 1700-2000 Pa, which are in the range of those of liver, fat, relaxed muscle and breast gland tissues. Higher swelling ratios were observed with longer crosslinkers. Shorter crosslinkers caused a burst release of vanillin while trismaleimide caused a more sustained drug release. In a more recent study, the same group prepared biocomposite hydrogels via crosslinking magnesium-doped hydroxyapatite incorporated alginate furan and bismaleimide via Diels-Alder reaction [140]. Studies showed that 5wt% of hydroxyapatite loading improved cell viability and proliferation the most, with a suitable porosity and good cell-material interactions while higher loadings had a limiting effect. Overall, all these alginate-based hydrogels are suitable for the development of biomedical platforms. Crosslinked alginate hydrogels were also fabricated via Diels-Alder reaction between a furan-modified alginate and a maleimide-modified alginate [141]. Higher degree of crosslinking resulted in less swelling, higher stiffness and higher compressive modulus, as well as higher stability. Higher drug release, namely gliclazide, was observed with less crosslinked hydrogels, in line with higher swelling and porosity.

Piazz and colleagues modified gelatin and dextran with maleimide and furan units, respectively [142]. The modified polymers were crosslinked via Diels-Alder reaction in order to create gelatin/dextran hydrogels which were then loaded with potassium diclofenac. Release studies were performed in water, PBS and HCl solutions, all showing a burst release in the first 30 min and maximum release was observed in HCl solution, which also resulted in the highest swelling of hydrogels.

A dual-crosslinking strategy was promoted for the fabrication of chondroitin sulfate/hyaluronic acid-based double network hydrogels (Fig. 15) [143]. Chondroitin sulfate functionalized with maleimide and furan-modified hyaluronic acid were reacted via Diels-Alder reaction while the aldehyde moieties on a separate batch of oxidized chondroitin sulfate was crosslinked with adipic acid dihydrazide. Mechanical tests pointed out equilibrium moduli between 0.3 and 0.5 MPa while viscoelasticity could be adjusted by varying the mass ratio of Diels-Alder and hydrazone components. The hydrogels were also found to be non-cytotoxic to mesenchymal stromal cells over 7 days, indicating their possible use in bioprinting and regenerative medicine.

Wang and colleagues created a starch-cellulose IPN hydrogels through a two-step process involving a Diels-Alder click reaction followed by photopolymerization in water and β -cyclodextrin incorporation [144]. Starch-based dienes were synthesized by modifying starch with N-maleoyl- β -alanine, and cellulose-based dienophiles were prepared by reacting cellulose with furfurylamide succinate. The synthesized starch dienes, cellulose dienophiles, polymerizable β -cyclodextrin,

Fig. 15. A) Modification of CS and HA polymers and hydrogel formulations, B) Schematic representation of the polymer networks of the hydrogels via DA and hydrazone linkages, C) Hydrogels upon in situ cross-linking at 37 °C. Adapted with permission from [143].

crosslinker, and acrylamide were dissolved in water to form a transparent solution heated in a water bath at 50 °C for 3 hours where the first network to form via a catalyst-free Diels-Alder reaction, followed by the formation of the second network through photopolymerization. Finally, 5-Fu was used as a model drug to investigate the sustained release behavior of the drug-loaded hydrogels. The release profile followed the Ritger-Peppas kinetic model, the cumulative release rate of resultant hydrogel was 58% at the first hour, reaching release equilibrium of 75% within 260 min. The cytotoxicity of the gel was also low, so these hydrogels can be a promising alternative to as drug release platform. Sanyal and coworkers prepared redox-responsive hyaluronic acid-based hydrogels using furan-modified hyaluronic acid and maleimide-disulfide-containing PEG-based crosslinker [145]. A fluorescein isothiocyanate conjugated bovine serum albumin (FITC-BSA) was encapsulated in the hydrogel and the local delivery ability of the hydrogels was investigated. At first, passive release of BSA was observed with a sustained profile, releasing 36% and 55% of the loaded protein at 6 h and 72 h, respectively. At 72 h, the gels degraded rapidly upon addition of the reducing agent DTT, releasing another 30% of the loaded BSA.

Diels-Alder crosslinked hyaluronic acid hydrogels were designed for the treatment of intrauterine adhesions [146]. Furan and maleimide-

modified hyaluronic acid were used to fabricate injectable hydrogels loaded with human umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cells. Fertility studies using rat endometrial damage model demonstrated that the hyaluronic acid based hydrogel contributed to an increase in pregnancy rates, embryo implantation ratio and a decrease in abortion rate, suggesting the healing of the damaged endometrium after treatment with UCMSCs-laden injectable hydrogel. *in vivo* experiments also proved confirmed that the resultant hydrogel efficiently enhanced macrophage recruitment and promoted the polarization to M2 phenotype. More recently, silver nanoparticle-loaded gelatin/dextran hydrogels were prepared by Lim, Park and coworkers [147]. Solutions of silver nanoparticle dispersed gelatin-maleimide and furan-modified dextran were mixed to form hydrogels crosslinked via Diels-Alder reaction. The incorporation of silver nanoparticles not only improved mechanical properties but also brought in high antibacterial efficacy. Together with their high cytocompatibility, these hydrogels can be offered as wound care materials. In another study, furan modified-carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) was crosslinked with a PEG-bismaleimide crosslinker via Diels-Alder reaction in order to form hydrogels for wound healing applications (Fig. 16) [148]. These hydrogels formed quickly under physiological conditions under 490 s and demonstrated desirable

Fig. 16. Schematic illustration of CMC-based injectable hydrogels loaded with curcumin via Diels-Alder reaction for wound dressing applications. Reprinted with permission from [148].

physical and mechanical characteristics. The loading efficiency of curcumin, which was used as a model drug reached up to 92%, while it also showed a sustained release of $\sim 80\%$ over 5 days. In vitro testing showed 100% cell viability with NIH3T3 fibroblasts and strong antibacterial effects against *E. coli*, indicating strong potential for wound healing use.

A novel pH-responsive hydrogel featuring supramolecular structures was developed using a Diels-Alder reaction and amino-maleimide chemistry, combining furan-functionalized hyaluronic acid, ϵ -polylysine and maleimide-functionalized polyrotaxane through self-assembly of PEG and α -cyclodextrin [149]. The resulting gels displayed self-healing property due to reversible hydrogen bonds and ionic bonds. The cumulative release of lidocaine from the hydrogel was 47.54% at pH 7.4, 33.56% at pH 6.5, and 10.67% at pH 1.2 over approximately 8 hours. These results indicate that hydrogel provides a consistent and controlled drug release profile while the initial burst release within the first 2 hours is likely to offer effective pain relief. The hydrogels also showed high cell viability over 80%, excellent biocompatibility, controlled degradation, making it highly promising for biomedical applications. Erdem and coworkers offered an IPN hydrogel for protein release through one-pot synthesis method combining aqueous Diels-Alder click chemistry with photopolymerization to crosslink methacrylated gelatin methacryloyl within a matrix of PEG bismaleimide and multi-furan-modified PEG [150]. The fully crosslinked IPN hydrogels showed significantly improved mechanical strength, with energy dissipation and compressive modulus values 2.5 to 3.5 times higher than those of semi-interpenetrating hydrogel network. The IPN hydrogels displayed a sustained release profile and they were stable against both hydrolytic and enzymatic degradation. Additionally, they exhibited good water uptake and excellent biocompatibility with 3T3 fibroblasts. These results support the potential of IPN hydrogels as an effective platform for drug delivery in regenerative medicine and targeted therapies.

2.2.4. Inverse electron demand diels-alder (iedDA) reaction-based hydrogels

The inverse electron demand Diels-Alder reaction, developed by Fox and colleagues in 2008, is a variation of the traditional Diels-Alder reaction. [151]. In this reaction, an electron-deficient diene, such as a tetrazine, reacts rapidly with an electron-rich dienophile like a strained alkene (e.g., norbornene or trans-cyclooctene), enabling fast and

selective crosslinking of polymer chains (Fig. 14B). One of the most notable applications of iedDA is in bioconjugation, particularly for labeling biomolecules in living systems without interfering with natural biological processes due to its high bioorthogonality [152]. The reaction is fast, selective, and biocompatible, and can occur under mild physiological conditions, which makes it ideal for use in biomedical applications [153]. Additionally, the iedDA reaction is catalyst-free and proceeds efficiently in aqueous environments, making it ideal for injectable, in situ-forming, or stimuli-responsive hydrogels. Its speed and orthogonality also allow for spatiotemporal control, enabling the design of advanced hydrogel systems for tissue engineering, drug delivery, and regenerative medicine. The formed dihydropyridazine linkages are stable and generally non-hydrolyzable under physiological conditions. Thus, degradation relies on backbone chemistry or incorporated labile spacers. iedDA is particularly favored for compatibility because it can be used to release anti-inflammatory drugs locally as the gel degrades, actively modulating the immune response.

Joshi and coworkers introduced tetrazine and norbornene moieties on alginate and prepared clickable alginate hydrogels through iedDA reaction [154]. The hydrogel was further modified with cell-adhesive RGD peptide via thiol-ene reaction. Cell studies revealed that higher viability of encapsulated 3T3 cells was observed for click alginate hydrogels compared to ionically crosslinked hydrogel both immediately after encapsulation ($93 \pm 1\%$ vs. $87 \pm 2\%$) and after 3 days of culture ($84 \pm 2\%$ vs. $79 \pm 4\%$). The mechanical properties and swelling degrees of the crosslinked hydrogels were tunable depending on the crosslinking density. In vivo testing showed that ionically crosslinked samples fragmented significantly after 1 month in vivo, resulting in cell infiltration, whereas the click alginate hydrogels remained intact during the 2 month study and were highly resistant to cell infiltration. The cytocompatibility and good cell-encapsulation ability of the hydrogels enable their possible use in tissue engineering applications. Cipitria and coworkers also aimed for hydrolytically degradable click-crosslinked alginate-based hydrogels with tunable material properties via oxidizing the polymer backbone, and crosslinking through norbornene and tetrazine functional groups present on alginate [155]. Mechanical tests revealed that unoxidized materials and materials with high norbornene content were stiffer than oxidized ones and those with lower norbornene, reaching a maximum elastic modulus of 21.2 ± 0.28 kPa. All hydrogels displayed high cell viability around 93%. Cytocompatibility was

assessed in a 3D environment by embedding cells within the hydrogel during its formation and monitoring their behavior over a 7-day period. Throughout the study, the cells maintained a rounded shape and showed no signs of proliferation. Cell viability remained at or above 82%. Increasing the crosslinking density results in slowing down degradation. Mooney and colleagues proposed incorporating Laponite nanoplatelets that were pre-adsorbed with proteins into injectable hydrogels for sustained, bioactive release of various therapeutically important proteins [156]. The hydrogels were alginate-based crosslinked with tetrazine-norbornene chemistry. They preferred cryogels over traditional injectable hydrogels as they exhibit shape memory, enabling the minimally invasive delivery of gels with specific volume, structure, and shape. The influence of Laponite on protein release from click alginate cryogels was subsequently evaluated using five immune-related proteins with different molecular size, overall charge, and immune activity. When using cryogels composed only of click alginate, all five proteins exhibited an initial burst release which is a common characteristic of diffusion-driven delivery systems. On the other hand, the addition of Laponite effectively prevented this burst release and enabled sustained,

controlled release of all proteins over a four-week period. Increasing the amount of Laponite used for pre-adsorption of proteins reduced burst release and slowed the elution of proteins over time from the gels, enabling tuning of the release rate of protein from the gels, suggesting the use of these cryogels for sustained drug delivery. In a more recent study, they formed an IPN of norbornene-tetrazine click-functionalized alginate and fibrillar collagen, embedded with heparin-coated beads loaded with interferon- γ [157]. The three-dimensional (3D) environment markedly enhanced the expression of numerous key immunomodulatory genes in primary human bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs). Incorporating interferon gamma-loaded beads extended the expression of critical licensing-related genes, such as indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase 1 and galectin-9, up to day 7. At the protein level, immunomodulatory extracellular matrix (iECM) hydrogels promoted increased secretion of galectin-9 by hMSCs, confirming successful release and diffusion of secreted factors into the hydrogel-conditioned media. Moreover, co-culturing iECM-encapsulated hMSCs with activated human T cells led to reduced T cell proliferation, demonstrating direct immunosuppressive effects. Collectively,

Fig. 17. Schematic illustration of the development and drug release mechanism of reduction responsive A) CMC-based hydrogels, B) Chitosan-based injectable hydrogels. Reprinted with permission from [159,161].

these results highlight the potential of iECM hydrogels to enhance MSC-driven immunotherapy strategies. Inverse-electron demand Diels-Alder reaction was also used for crosslinking norbornene and tetrazine-modified gelatin derivatives, leading to hydrogels with degree of modification between 5 and 15% [158]. The elastic modulus of hydrogels ranged from 0.5 kPa for low degree of modification to 5 kPa for high degree of modification. All the hydrogel formulations were cytocompatible and human dental pulp stem cells cultured in the hydrogels showed cell viability of >85%. An increase in metabolic activity and a more elongated cell morphology was detected for cells cultured in hydrogels with lower elastic modulus. The tunability of the gelatin hydrogel properties is promising for tissue engineering and in vitro modeling applications.

Reduction-responsive and biocompatible carboxymethyl cellulose based hydrogels were prepared through iedDA reaction between norbornene-functionalized carboxymethyl cellulose and a diselenide-based crosslinker with two terminal tetrazine groups (Fig. 17A) [159]. The resulting hydrogels showed tunable gelation times, high swelling ratios, soft mechanical properties with storage moduli in the range 74–160 Pa and high DOX loading efficiencies around 85%. The stimuli-responsive nature of the hydrogels allows rapid drug release and fast degradation rate at tumor intracellular mimicking environment while showed low release rate and slow degradation at simulated physiological conditions. In addition to these properties, the low cytotoxicity and anti-tumor activity indicate potential applications of these soft hydrogels in injectable drug delivery systems. In another study, they designed a multi-stimuli responsive hydrogels using a norbornene-functional hyaluronic acid and the diselenide-ditetrazine crosslinker via iedDA reaction under physiological conditions [160]. The gelation time of the hydrogels decreased from 500 s to 200 s with increasing crosslinker ratio, while mechanical strength also increased. The hydrogel showed a swelling ratio between 900–1800% depending on the crosslinking density. The drug release studies using DOX of the hydrogels revealed that they quickly broke down into linear chains when exposed to in acidic, reducing, and oxidizing medium and NIR light, resulting in an initial burst release of DOX followed by a prolonged, sustained release. In vitro tests on BT-20 cancer cells showed that DOX-loaded hydrogels had comparable anti-tumor effects to free DOX. However, hydrogels loaded with both DOX and ICG exhibited enhanced anti-tumor efficacy after NIR light exposure, indicating a combined effect of chemotherapy and photothermal therapy. Overall, the study demonstrates that the developed hyaluronic acid hydrogels hold promise as multi-responsive drug delivery systems for cancer treatment. They also developed injectable, reduction-responsive hydrogels based on chitosan, using the iedDA reaction between tetrazine-functionalized disulfide crosslinkers and norbornene-modified chitosan for the controlled release of DOX (Fig. 17B) [161]. These hydrogels possesses key properties such as swelling behavior, gelation time ranging from 90 to 500 seconds, storage moduli from 350 to 850 Pa, network structure, and high drug-loading efficiency of around 92%. In vitro DOX release studies were conducted at pH levels 7.4 and 5.0, both with and without 10 mM DTT. Biocompatibility of the unloaded hydrogels and the anticancer efficacy of DOX-loaded hydrogels were evaluated using MTT assays on HEK-293 (normal) and HT-29 (cancer) cell lines, respectively. The same group developed reduction-sensitive injectable hydrogels using the iedDA reaction between alginate modified with norbornene and a water-soluble PEG-based disulfide crosslinker terminated with tetrazine groups [162]. These hydrogels exhibited a high swelling capacity of around 20 time, porous structure, excellent drug loading efficiency around 92%, and favorable mechanical strength with storage moduli between 1500–2800 Pa. Drug release studies showed that over 90% of the encapsulated DOX was released in the presence of 10 mM glutathione, while less than 25% was released in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) after 11 days. Both the crosslinker and the hydrogels were non-toxic to fibroblast cells. However, DOX-loaded hydrogels demonstrated effective anti-cancer activity against tumor cells. These injectable, reduction-responsive

hydrogels show strong promise for use in stimuli-responsive drug delivery systems. More recently, they created innovative NIR-sensitive hydrogels using ROS-cleavable thioketal crosslinkers, which featured terminal tetrazine groups for bioorthogonal iedDA click reaction with norbornene-functionalized carboxymethyl cellulose as a promising approach for targeted cancer therapy [163]. These hydrogels formed quickly between 170 and 495 s under physiological conditions and released nitrogen gas as a by-product, resulting in a porous internal structure leading to a high swelling ratio (>5900). Indocyanine green (ICG), a NIR dye, and the chemotherapy drug DOX were co-loaded into the hydrogel matrix with a high drug loading efficiency and drug content of 95% and 4.54%, respectively. When exposed to NIR light, the hydrogels released over 96% of the DOX after 168 h due to thioketal bond cleavage triggered by ROS generated from ICG. In contrast, less than 25% of DOX was released without NIR exposure. Cytotoxicity tests showed the hydrogels were biocompatible and non-toxic to HEK-293 cells. However, when loaded with DOX and ICG and exposed to NIR light, the hydrogels significantly boosted the anti-cancer effect and suppressed Hela cell proliferation.

Norbornene-tetrazine chemistry was also used for the synthesis of a double-crosslinked hydrogel network for drug delivery, namely ketoprofen [164]. Norbornene modified chitosan oligosaccharide and tetrazine-bearing alginate were chemically crosslinked via iedDA reaction while hydrogels were also physically crosslinked via electrostatic interactions between NH_3^+ groups present on the chitosan oligosaccharide and $-\text{COO}^-$ groups present on alginate. The chemical crosslinking favoured high hydrophobic drug loading around 44% wt/wt and a sustained release. The electrostatic network provided pH responsiveness, which decreases the drug release in simulated gastric fluid to below 10% for 2 h while increasing in simulated intestinal fluids up to 84% for 24 h. The prepared hydrogel displayed a cell viability of 95% to human HEK-293 cells, suggesting a a potential approach for the delivery of hydrophobic drugs.

Lim and coworkers presented injectable hydrogels using norbornene-functionalized hyaluronic acid and a water-soluble PEG-based crosslinker modified with tetrazine groups on both ends and crosslinked via an iedDA reaction (Fig. 18) [165]. By adjusting the molar ratios of hyaluronic acid and crosslinker, tunable hydrogels with customizable porosity, gelation times, mechanical properties, and swelling capacities were achieved. These hydrogels gelled under 100 seconds, making them suitable for injectable drug delivery systems. The hydrogels showed efficient encapsulation of curcumin (~99%), which was released rapidly during the initial phase, and then a more sustained release profile was achieved. The fabricated hydrogels also exhibited high cell viability to HEK-293 cells, expressing their potential as drug delivery platforms. Lim and coworkers also introduced stimuli-responsive injectable hydrogels through crosslinking a highly biocompatible norbornene-modified cartilage acellularized matrix with a water-soluble tetrazine-modified diselenide-containing crosslinker [166]. The reaction between Nb-functionalized CAM and Tz-functionalized crosslinker generated nitrogen gas, yielding injectable hydrogels with highly porous architectures. The resulting hydrogels displayed high drug-loading efficiency up to 93%, favorable swelling behavior up to 3000%, and suitable mechanical strength. The loaded DOX was released without burst release both in simulated physiological and reductive conditions, reaching up to respectively 29.12 and 91.54% after 96 h. In the case of NIR light exposure, burst release of DOX up to 51.65% was observed from the hydrogels during the first 4 h reaching up to 96.72% after 96 h. In vitro cytocompatibility evaluations revealed that the resulting hydrogels were non-toxic to HFF-1 fibroblasts and HT-29 human colorectal adenocarcinoma cells, demonstrating their strong bioorthogonality and biocompatibility. Moreover, hydrogels loaded with DOX or co-loaded with DOX and ICG effectively reduced the metabolic activity of HT-29 cells following GSH treatment or NIR irradiation, producing anticancer effects comparable to those observed with free DOX. Collectively, these reduction-sensitive and biocompatible

Fig. 18. Graphical representation of A) Synthesis of PEG-DTz, B) Chemical structure of HA-Nb, C) Schematic diagram representing development of injectable hydrogels, and D) Mechanism of curcumin release from the porous hydrogel. Reprinted with permission from [165]

injectable hydrogels, capable of controlled, on-demand drug release under NIR stimulation, represent promising platforms for minimally invasive, localized cancer therapy.

Chondroitin sulfate-based hydrogels were also prepared through iedDA reaction between tetrazine modified-chondroitin sulfate and norbornene-modified multiarm PEG [167]. The hydrogels possessed short gelation time and high cell compatibility. The *in vivo* studies exhibited that the hydrogels were also capable of improving wound closure and blood flow. iedDA was also used for preparing hyaluronic acid-based hydrogels. Injectable *in situ* hydrogels were fabricated using tetrazine and transcyclooctene-modified hyaluronic acid and loaded with a chemical immobilized chondrogenic differentiation factor, namely cytomodulin-2 and human periodontal ligament stem cells [168]. Cytomodulin-2 allowed the hydrogels to show a better chondrogenic differentiation of the cells, which makes them promising for tissue engineering. Innovative chemically crosslinked hydrogels based on norbornene-carboxymethyl cellulose and tetrazine-alginate were demonstrated through iedDA chemistry under physiological conditions, eliminating the need for catalysts [169]. These hydrogels were engineered to produce ROS via the near-infrared dye indocyanine green, enabling combined photothermal and photodynamic therapy. The resulting injectable hydrogels demonstrated viscoelastic behavior (G' ranging from ~492 to 270 Pa), high porosity and adjustable mechanical properties. The hydrogels possessed photodynamic activity when exposed to NIR light (1–2 W for 5–15 minutes), also enabling photothermal destruction of tumor cells, particularly against HeLa cancer cells, with the temperature increase. Cytocompatibility tests indicated that hydrogels were non-toxic to HEK-293 cells. An injectable collagen-hyaluronic acid hydrogel incorporating calcium sulfate nanorods was developed using a bioorthogonal click reaction between collagen-norbornene and hyaluronic acid-tetrazine in order to initiate self-biomineralization and guide new bone formation [170]. The

resulting composite hydrogels not only support cell adhesion and proliferation but also offer a controlled calcium ion release system. The compressive tests pointed out that increasing calcium sulfate nanorods also increased the compressive strength of the composite hydrogels, reaching to about 16 kPa. These hydrogels exhibited excellent injectability, enabling easy application into complex bone defects and conforming to irregular geometries. Importantly, the presence of calcium sulfate nanorods promoted intrinsic biomineralization, rapidly generating bone-like hydroxyapatite within the hydrogel matrix. The sustained release of Ca^{2+} ions from composite hydrogels was observed for over 28 days which also encouraged preosteoblast differentiation and stimulated localized bone regeneration. Overall, this hydrogel system effectively enhances hydroxyapatite formation, and supports *in situ* bone repair through a minimally invasive approach.

A gelatin-based click hydrogel synthesized through the iedDA reaction between tetrazine and norbornene-modified gelatin provided the sustained perivascular delivery of TSP-2 siRNA to rat carotid arteries following endothelial denudation injury [171]. At 21 days post-treatment, perivascular administration of TSP-2 siRNA-loaded hydrogels markedly reduced TSP-2 gene expression, suppressed cellular proliferation, and downregulated key mediators associated with intimal hyperplasia (IH), including MMP-9 and VEGF-R2. These molecular effects translated into a significant attenuation of IH. Overall, the findings demonstrate that perivascular delivery of TSP-2 siRNA using the bioorthogonally-crosslinked gelatin hydrogel effectively limits IH after arterial injury.

2.2.5. Other click reactions

2.2.5.1. Schiff base reaction-based hydrogels. A Schiff base reaction plays a significant role in the formation of hydrogels, especially in the design of dynamic and injectable hydrogels for biomedical applications [172]

[173]. In this context, the reaction involves the condensation between aldehyde or ketone groups and amine groups on polymer chains, leading to the formation of reversible imine linkages (Fig. 19A). This cross-linking mechanism enables the hydrogel to form a three-dimensional network that can absorb and retain large amounts of water. One of the key advantages of using Schiff base chemistry in hydrogels is its reversibility and responsiveness to environmental conditions, which allows for controlled drug release, and tissue adhesion. The imine bond can hydrate and break, allowing the gel to dissolve gradually under physiological conditions or rapidly in acidic environments such as tumor sites or infected wounds. Due to its mild reaction conditions and biocompatibility, the Schiff base reaction is widely employed in the development of injectable, in situ-forming hydrogels for drug delivery, wound healing, and tissue engineering. A major advantage for long-term compatibility is their self-healing ability; these gels can reform their network after mechanical damage, reducing physical irritation to surrounding tissues. However, if toxic aldehydes like glutaraldehyde are used as crosslinkers, residual unreacted groups can cause cytotoxicity so, residual aldehyde quantification and stability control are major regulatory concerns. Batch reproducibility is also critical due to sensitivity to pH and hydration.

Yang and coworkers combined oxidized sodium alginate with a macromolecular crosslinker, hydrazide-modified PEG (PEG-DTP) to fabricate an injectable, dual-responsive, and self-healing hydrogel through a Schiff base reaction [174]. Incorporation of PEG-DTP significantly enhanced the flexibility, hydrophilicity, mechanical properties and pH responsiveness of the alginate-based hydrogel network. Owing to the presence of dynamic acylhydrazone bonds and redox-sensitive disulfide linkages present in PEG-DTP, the hydrogel exhibited dual responsiveness to both pH and redox stimuli. The degradation behavior and drug release profiles could be precisely tuned by adjusting the DTT concentration or environmental pH. Furthermore, the reversible nature of the acylhydrazone bonds enabled nearly 100% repeatable self-healing after mechanical damage. In vitro cytotoxicity assessments confirmed cell viability over 90%. Collectively, this multifunctional sodium alginate-based hydrogel, featuring injectability, multi-stimuli responsiveness, and self-healing capability, holds strong potential for applications in drug delivery, tissue engineering, and controlled three-dimensional cell culture systems.

An in situ forming composite hydrogel was designed for ocular delivery of betamethasone utilizing the Schiff base reaction between a dialdehyde starch and amine moieties of chitosan [175]. Results showed that a higher dialdehyde starch content led to quicker gel formation from 60 s to 15 s, enhanced mechanical strength with storage modulus up to 20 kPa, increased pore size, and a more favorable degradation

profiles, alongside accelerated drug release in both in vitro and ex vivo conditions. Additionally, the hydrogel demonstrated excellent biocompatibility with cell viability more than 90%. Another group prepared injectable hydrogels using aminated hyaluronic acid and aldehyde β -cyclodextrin through a Schiff base reaction also for ocular treatment [176]. Voriconazole and endophthalmitis served as the model drug and disease, respectively and the hydrogels demonstrated sustained drug release for over 60 days while cytotoxicity tests using adult retina pigment epithelial cell confirmed excellent biocompatibility, as well as in vivo tests showing no adverse effects on ocular tissues. Overall, these Schiff base-crosslinked hydrogels showed strong potential as a long-term, controlled drug delivery system for ocular disease treatment.

Nie and coworkers also used thiol-Michael reaction between dithiothreitol modified graphene oxide and aldehyde methylene sodium alginate and Schiff-base reaction between aldehyde methylene sodium alginate and amino gelatin, in order to fabricate graphene oxide-reinforced alginate/gelatin hydrogel for bone regeneration (Fig. 20) [177]. It was observed that double network hydrogels showed decreased porosity and increased compressive strength up to 13.85 MPa compared to hydrogels formed only by Schiff-base reaction. The degradation rate and cell viability of the double network hydrogels reduced while their osteogenic capacity increased compared to single network hydrogels. An in situ forming alginate/gelatin hydrogel was also introduced by Omid and coworkers using the Schiff base reaction, between the amino and aldehyde groups present in gelatin and oxidized alginate which were loaded with curcumin-loaded chitosan microspheres [178]. The composite hydrogels showed a cumulative curcumin release of 35.57%, high biocompatibility and increased calcium deposition, alkaline phosphatase activity, and elevated osteogenic gene expression in human bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells, making them promising for bone tissue regeneration.

In a study by Kim and coworkers, injectable hydrogels were prepared via injecting a precursor containing oxidized hyaluronic acid, tyramine, and calcium ions and another precursor containing carboxymethyl chitosan, horseradish peroxidase, and hydrogen peroxide using a dual-syringe system [179]. Throughout the process, several spontaneous reactions including a Schiff base click reaction, an enzymatic reaction catalyzed by HRP, and ionic interactions involving Ca^{2+} cause the liquid precursors to rapidly form a solid hydrogel. This in situ gelation allows the hydrogel to closely conform and adhere to the tissue surface. Higher tyramine content improves the stretchability of the double network hydrogel due to the increased inter-chain crosslinking while lack of horseradish peroxidase, hydrogen peroxide, and Ca^{2+} leads to a decrease in stretchability. In vivo studies on a circular wound on the dorsal skin of a rat demonstrated that the hydrogel is capable of

Fig. 19. A) Schiff base, B) Oxime, C) Hydrazone, D) Amino-yne reactions.

Fig. 20. Formation of the double network gelatin/alginate/graphene oxide hydrogel. Adapted with permission from [177].

promoting the wound recovery. Drug-loaded poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) nanoparticles or ferrimagnetic iron oxide nanocubes can also be physically incorporated into precursor of the multifunctional hydrogel prior to injection to gain additional capabilities, such as targeted drug delivery or compatibility with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Chitosan and hyaluronic acid-based hydrogels were also prepared for wound healing applications using Schiff-base reaction between oxidized hyaluronic acid and carboxymethyl chitosan with the incorporation of the active polypeptides extract of *Periplaneta Americana* [180]. The hydrogels showed high cell viability and excellent diabetic wound closure rates according to *in vivo* studies performed on mice back wounds. Another group prepared a multicrosslinked adhesive hydrogel using dopamine functionalized oxidized hyaluronic acid, carboxymethyl chitosan and thiol-modified collagen [181]. The Schiff dynamic bond between oxidized hyaluronic acid and carboxymethyl chitosan, the N–Ag–N bond between carboxymethyl chitosan and Ag ions, and the S–Ag–S dynamic bond between thiol-modified collagen and Ag ions allowed the construction of an injectable hydrogel in 150 s which can also self-heal in 10 min. *In vitro* experiments using L929 cells confirmed that this hydrogel exhibited good biocompatibility and cell proliferation. Additionally, curcumin-loaded gelatin nanoparticles were loaded in the hydrogel with an efficiency of $4.17 \pm 0.10\%$, which could respond to MMPs and controllably release Cur up to over 80% to provide wound healing. Animal experiment results proved that this curcumin-loaded hydrogel promoted wound healing, indicating its potential as a wound dressing. Li and coworkers also prepared dual network hydrogels composed of dopamine-grafted oxidized hyaluronic acid and quaternary ammonium chitosan through enzyme-catalyzed crosslinking and Schiff base reaction for wound healing applications (Fig. 21) [182]. The injectable hydrogels displayed high biocompatibility, antibacterial, and antioxidant property as well as self-healing ability while *in vivo* studies using mice modeling pointed out that hydrogels effectively seal wounds and speed up healing by increasing the expression of proteins involved in blood vessel formation and encouraging more uniform and organized collagen deposition. Both studies showed appealing potential for chronic wound healing applications.

Hyaluronic acid hydrogels were also synthesized for wound healing through the Schiff base reaction between an aldehyde-functionalized hyaluronic acid and diethylenetriamine-functionalized hyaluronic acid, which were also embedded with silver nanoparticles [183]. The formation of the imine bond results in a dynamic pH-responsive crosslinking and on-demand drug release. These injectable hydrogels demonstrated excellent cell compatibility and strong antibacterial effects against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, and increased wound healing rates. A chitosan/konjac glucomannan

hydrogel was introduced using the Schiff reaction between carboxymethyl chitosan and oxidized konjac glucomannan and further employed with tannic acid [184]. The hydrogel possessed a pH dependent tannic acid release behavior, also displaying good antioxidant, antibacterial, and anti-biofilm properties, which are suitable properties for biomedical applications.

2.2.5.2. Oxime and hydrazone reaction-based hydrogels. The oxime reaction is a chemoselective condensation between an alkoxyamine ($-\text{ONH}_2$) and an aldehyde or ketone ($-\text{CHO}/-\text{C}=\text{O}$) to form a stable oxime linkage (Fig. 19B). Oxime ligation kinetics can be modulated by pH, catalysts, and ionic strength, allowing fine control over crosslinking rates and material properties in hydrogel systems [185,186]. Imine and hydrazone linkages have been extensively utilized to prepare viscoelastic hydrogels from different polysaccharides. However, their equilibrium constants are significantly lower than that of the oxime reaction, indicating that oxime chemistry is more favorable for the rapid formation of hydrogels. Despite this advantage, aldehyde groups involved in oxime formation can also react with amino groups in the body to form Schiff bases. Therefore, oxime chemistry cannot be considered fully bioorthogonal and may present potential cytotoxic effects. In addition, the relatively limited stability of oxime bonds imposes certain constraints on their use in biomedical applications. Still, it proceeds efficiently in aqueous environments under mild, physiologically relevant conditions and is largely inert to native biological functional groups, minimizing off-target interactions. The hydrazone reaction is a reversible covalent condensation between a hydrazine derivative ($-\text{NHNH}_2$) and an aldehyde or ketone, forming a hydrazone bond ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{NH}-$) with water as a byproduct (Fig. 19C). Similar to oxime ligation, it proceeds efficiently in aqueous media under mild acidic to physiological pH, making it highly attractive for biomedical hydrogel formation. A key advantage of hydrazone linkages is their dynamic covalent nature: the imine bond can undergo reversible exchange under controlled pH conditions, enabling self-healing behavior, stress relaxation, injectability, and shear-thinning properties in hydrogels. These features are particularly valuable for minimally invasive delivery, cell encapsulation, and drug release systems. Moreover, acylhydrazone variants provide enhanced hydrolytic stability compared to simple hydrazones, allowing longer-term structural integrity in physiological conditions. Such systems have been widely investigated for tissue engineering scaffolds, 3D cell culture matrices, and stimuli-responsive drug delivery platforms.

Schmidt and coworkers prepared *in situ* crosslinking hydrogels via oxime reaction between a bis(oxoamine)-PEG and aldehyde-bearing hyaluronic acid derivatives [187]. The hydrogels showed high cell viability around 90% and compressive moduli between 2–12 kPa, which

Fig. 21. A) Schematic illustration of OHA-DA/QCS double-network hydrogel formation, B) Injectable and plastic properties of hydrogels C) Images and wound contraction diagram of healing wounds on different time using saline (control), commercial wound dressing (Tegaderm) and the synthesized OHA-DA/QCS double-network hydrogel. Adapted with permission from [182].

are in the range of soft tissues of the nervous system. An incorporation of collagen 1 in the hydrogel system also supported the adhesion of HMSCs. HA-based hydrogels crosslinked via oxime reaction were also prepared by Shoichet group [188]. They modified HA with both aldehyde and furan groups, used the aldehyde groups for crosslinking with bis (oxyamine)-PEG and the furan groups to conjugate maleimide-containing peptides via Diels-Alder reaction. These HA-based hydrogels, exhibiting an elastic modulus around 0.6 kPa and functionalized with laminin α 1-mimetic IKVAV peptides, serve as biomimetic scaffolds that support the formation of T47D and MCF-7 breast cancer cell spheroids with in vivo-like morphology. Notably, T47D spheroids cultured within the bifunctional HA hydrogels showed reduced DOX diffusion into the spheroid core along with elevated MDR1 expression,

indicating enhanced multidrug resistance and promising use of these hydrogels for predictive anticancer drug screening. The same group then introduced 3D HA hydrogels via oxime click chemistry through combining fast-reacting aldehyde-HA and slow-reacting ketone-HA with 2- and 4- armed PEG-oxyamine in order to provide a more controlled system for breast cancer cell encapsulation in 3D [189]. The stiffness of the resultant hydrogels varied between 0.3-15 kPa depending on the crosslinking density or the weight percent of HA, which is in the range of mouse mammary tumors and human breast cancer tissue. Laninin was incorporated in the system prior to gelation in order to mimic the heterogeneity of the ECM in breast cancer and enhance cell interaction with the HA-oxime hydrogels, which was found to increase the adhesion of T47D luminal A breast cancer cells two times. The HA-oxime-based

breast cancer model preserves a gene expression pattern that most closely resembles tumor xenografts, as demonstrated by a pan-cancer gene expression analysis of 730 genes across three human breast cancer subtypes and verified distinct transcriptional differences between cells cultured in HA-oxime and those grown in Matrigel or 2D systems across 12 canonical signaling pathways. Notably, breast cancer cells exhibited enhanced sensitivity to the Rac inhibitor EHT-1864 and the PI3K inhibitor AZD6482 when grown in HA-oxime hydrogel relative to Matrigel. Overall, these findings highlight the advantages of HA-based hydrogels as *in vitro* platforms for culturing both primary patient-derived breast cancer cells and established cell lines, providing a model that more faithfully recapitulates *in vivo* tumor biology. Roh and coworkers prepared dual crosslinked hydrogels via oxime reaction between alkoxyamine-modified alginate and aldehyde-containing alginate and ionic crosslinking in the presence of CaCl_2 [190]. Viscoelastic hydrogels in microbead and microthread formats were introduced innovative strategies to fabricate by leveraging the distinctive dual crosslinking mechanism of the engineered alginate system. In addition, biocompatibility was confirmed through the encapsulation and culture of 2PK-3 cells within the hydrogel beads, underscoring the strong potential of this material platform for biomedical applications that demand precisely defined, biomimetic viscoelastic microenvironments.

Xanthan-PEG hydrogels crosslinked via hydrazone linkages between oxidized xanthan, and 8-arm PEG hydrazine were designed for drug and cell delivery applications [191]. The hydrogels possess storage modulus between 194-770 Pa depending on the PEG hydrazine amount and showed instant recovery to alternating cycles of varying strains of 1 and 800% for 5 cycles, suggesting self-healing capabilities. DOX was loaded onto hydrogels and release studies were performed at pH 5.5 and 7.4. The cumulative release of DOX showed a decreasing trend from 81.06 to 41.67% at pH 5.5 and from 47.43 to 35.34% at pH 7 with increasing PEG hydrazide amount from 3 to 5% at 30 days. Live/dead staining of encapsulated NIH-3T3 cells revealed minimal cell death, indicating that the hydrogels possess excellent cytocompatibility in both 2D and 3D culture systems. Media collected from DOX-loaded hydrogels induced cytotoxic effects in A549 cells, confirming the therapeutic activity of the released drug. Collectively, these findings suggest that the developed hydrogels hold promise for applications in controlled drug delivery and 3D cell culture platforms for cell delivery purposes. Nada and colleagues oxidized starch to provide aldehyde moieties and crosslinked with adipic acid dihydrazide through hydrazone bonding [192]. Studies demonstrated that the swelling and stress values decreased with increasing crosslinker ratio. The hydrogels were loaded with diclofenac sodium and showed very low cytotoxicity of 8.9%. Drug release profiles were proportionally related to the crosslinking density, taking 4 h for the highest crosslinker concentrations. More recently, Wang and coworkers developed a dynamic, antioxidant hydrogel using aldehyde-functionalized hyaluronic acid and disulfide and hydrazide-modified chondroitin sulfate (Fig. 22) [193]. Incorporation of disulfide groups into chondroitin sulfate imparted antioxidative properties to the resulting hydrogel matrix. Meanwhile, the formation of a hydrazone-based dynamic covalent network between aldehyde and hydrazide groups endowed the system with rapid *in situ* gelation and self-healing capabilities. The degradation time of the hydrogels decreased from 75 h to 1 h in the presence of 1mM H_2O_2 , indicating ability to respond to the ROS wound microenvironment. The hydrogels showed high cell viability, and ROS protection to encapsulated rADSCs and NHDFs cells in the H_2O_2 stimulate *in vitro* oxidative damage, pointing out the potential use of the hydrogel system as antioxidative wound dressings.

Recently, Schönherr and coworkers designed a dual-crosslinked hydrogel based on covalent crosslinking through the hydrazone bond between a ketone-rich dextrin acetoacetate and alginate hydrazide, and ionic crosslinking in the presence of CaCl_2 [194]. The hydrogels showed lower swelling at pH 1.2 and higher swelling at pH 7.4, showing their pH responsiveness. *In vitro* studies showed that both mouse fibroblasts and

Fig. 22. Schematic illustration of the fabrication and application of the CS-DTP/HA-CHO hydrogel. Reprinted with permission from [193].

human pancreatic cancer cells exhibited good growth and proliferation on only chemically crosslinked and double-crosslinked hydrogels, indicating their biocompatibility and lack of cytotoxicity. However, cell viability was slightly lower on the double-crosslinked hydrogel compared to the single-crosslinked hydrogel. The ability of these hydrogels to form gels *in situ*, along with their cytocompatibility, highlights their potential for use in *in situ* biocompatible gel applications. Hettiaratchi and coworkers applied a design of experiments statistical approach to systematically optimize the physicochemical properties of a hyaluronic acid-based hydrazone hydrogel with three input variables, HA molecular weight (40 or 100 kDa), adipic acid dihydrazide-modified HA (HA-ADH) concentration (1-3% w/v), and oxidized HA (HA-Ox) concentration (1-3% w/v) [195]. The variables affected gelation time, compressive modulus, and long-term hydrogel stability and optimum conditions were found as 100 kDa HA-ADH with a concentration of 3.00% w/v combined with HA-Ox with a concentration of 2.33% w/v, exhibiting a gelation time of 3.7 minutes, a compressive modulus of 62.1 Pa, and stability over 28 days. For controlled protein delivery, BMP-2-specific affibodies were conjugated to the HA hydrogels, enabling sustained release of bone morphogenetic protein-2 (BMP-2) over a 28-day period. Overall, this study highlights the effectiveness of the DoE strategy in optimizing hydrazone-crosslinked HA hydrogels for bone regeneration-related protein delivery.

2.2.5.3. Amino-yne reaction-based hydrogels. The amino-yne reaction is a versatile and efficient click-chemistry approach used in hydrogel synthesis, involving the nucleophilic addition of amine groups to electron-deficient alkynes (Fig. 19D) [196]. This reaction proceeds under mild, catalyst-free conditions, making it highly suitable for biomedical applications where biocompatibility is essential. In hydrogel formation, multifunctional amine-containing polymers react with alkyne-functionalized crosslinkers to create a three-dimensional network, resulting in rapid gelation and tunable mechanical properties. The amino-yne reaction offers precise control over crosslinking density and functional group incorporation, enabling the design of hydrogels with tailored properties for drug delivery, tissue engineering, and cell encapsulation. Compared to triazoles or thioethers, amino-yne linkages are moderately stable but potentially cleavable in physiological environments. Metal-free and initiator-free conditions reduce acute toxicity risk.

Huang and Jiang introduced injectable hydrogels without using any catalyst or initiator under physiological conditions via amino-yne reaction between amino groups of water-soluble carboxymethyl chitosan and alkyne groups of dipropiolate ester of PEG (Fig. 23) [197]. The reaction forms enamine bonds that are pH-sensitive, allowing reversible sol-gel transitions based on acidity. The drug loading content and the

Fig. 23. Formation of chitosan-based hydrogels via amino-yne reaction. Reprinted with permission from [197].

loading efficiency of DOX in the hydrogels were 5.6 and 78.6%, respectively. The hydrogels also enabled pH-responsive release of DOX, around 8% after 45 h at pH 7.4 and 20% at pH 5 after 45 h. Both in vitro cytotoxicity tests and in vivo injection studies showed rapid gel formation and excellent biocompatibility. Ren and coworkers studied collagen-based hydrogels as corneal repair materials, which were prepared through amino-yne reaction between the amine groups on collagen and alkyne units on linear di-alkynyl poly(ethylene glycol) and branched tetra-alkynyl poly(ethylene glycol) crosslinkers [198]. In both cases, the resultant hydrogels displayed high light transmittance and good mechanical properties. Cytotoxicity studies using rabbit corneal epithelial cells pointed out the high cell viability and cell proliferation at low concentrations on the hydrogels, indicating their potential application in corneal repair.

A multifunctional hydrogel based on hyaluronic acid grafted with adipic acid dihydrazide and tannic acid was developed using a spontaneous amino-yne click reaction in order to enhance the healing of infected diabetic wounds [199]. It demonstrated several advantageous features, including customizable gelation time between 13 to 26 h, tunable mechanical strength with storage modulus reaching to 4000 Pa, pH-responsive behavior, excellent injectability, strong tissue adhesion with adhesive strength of ~ 10 kPa, and close tissue conformity. The hydrogel was further enhanced by incorporating ultrasmall silver nanoclusters and nanoparticles composed of polydopamine and hollow mesoporous manganese dioxide loaded with deferoxamine. In vivo experiments confirmed the hydrogel's ability to promote wound healing by sequentially activating antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and angiogenesis-promoting mechanisms, as well as a smart, responsive drug release profile. The hydrogel was particularly effective at mitigating local oxidative stress and hypoxia by catalyzing the breakdown of endogenous hydrogen peroxide to generate oxygen and possessed potential for treating chronically infected diabetic wounds and other inflammation-related conditions.

2.2.5.4. Enzyme-assisted click reaction-based hydrogels. Enzyme-assisted click crosslinked hydrogels represent an emerging class of biomaterials that integrate the high selectivity and orthogonality of click chemistry with the mild catalytic conditions of enzymatic reactions to enable in situ network formation under physiological environments. In these systems, enzymes such as horseradish peroxidase (HRP), transglutaminase, tyrosinase, alkaline phosphatase, or sortase A catalyze the generation or activation of reactive species that subsequently participate in click reactions. The enzymatic component allows precise modulation of gelation kinetics through control of enzyme concentration, substrate availability, and reaction conditions, while the click reaction ensures high efficiency, minimal side reactions, and well-defined network architectures. This dual strategy enables spatiotemporal control, injectability, cytocompatible encapsulation of cells and bioactive molecules, and tunable mechanical properties. Consequently, enzyme-assisted click hydrogels are particularly attractive for biomedical applications including tissue engineering, drug delivery, wound healing, and 3D cell culture, where biocompatibility, bioorthogonality, and controllable

degradation are critical. Lin and coworkers investigated the enzymatic initiation of thiol-norbornene gelation using horseradish peroxidase (HRP)/hydrogen peroxide in order to generate the thiol radicals for the first time (Fig. 24) [75]. Enzymatic thiol-norbornene gelation addresses the light attenuation limitations typically associated with photopolymerized hydrogels while maintaining the modular nature of the crosslinking process. Photochemically crosslinked hydrogels are often constrained in thickness or depth due to light attenuation in dense or opaque systems. Employing enzymes to catalyze thiol-norbornene click reactions offers additional benefits, including decoupled and modular control over gelation rate and ultimate network properties. In this study, hydrogels were fabricated using two types of norbornene-functionalized macromers: 8-arm poly(ethylene glycol)-norbornene and gelatin-norbornene (GelNB). Crosslinking was achieved with either bis-cysteine-containing peptides or PEG-tetra-thiol enabling enzymatic and orthogonal network formation. For HRP-mediated PEG-peptide hydrogel formation, incorporating tyrosine residues into the peptide crosslinkers markedly enhanced gelation efficiency. Notably, these added tyrosine groups did not generate stable dityrosine bonds during HRP-triggered gelation. Consequently, they remained reactive for subsequent tyrosinase-catalyzed secondary crosslinking, which dynamically increased the stiffness of the hydrogel network with a degree around 2-5 kPa. Live/dead staining results showed that hydrogels displayed good cytocompatibility with above 85% and 90% murine NIH/3T3 fibroblasts cell surviving the enzymatic encapsulation process without and with stiffening process, respectively. Overall, this enzymatic thiol-norbornene strategy introduces an alternative crosslinking approach for the development of modular and dynamically tunable hydrogels.

Novel bioadhesive hydrogel dressings were introduced via dual-crosslinking between oxidized HA and dopa-grafted ϵ -polylysine which were separately dissolved in H_2O_2 and HRP solutions, respectively [200]. Upon mixing, reversible acylhydrazone linkages were formed, while the dopamine moieties grafted onto ϵ -polylysine underwent crosslinking through oxidation catalyzed by oxygen radicals generated from the HRP/ H_2O_2 system. The sol-gel transition occurs within seconds via horseradish peroxidase enzymatic crosslinking and Schiff base reaction. These hydrogels possessed an adhesive strength of up to 71.2 kPa and showed self-healing and good anti-bacterial properties. Along with high cell viability, in vivo tests using rats demonstrated that the hydrogel dressing were capable of avoiding wound infection and provide the rapid healing of the wound. Thiol oxidation leading to disulfide bond formation provides a dynamic and cytocompatible covalent crosslinking mechanism, generating reversible linkages that can form and dissociate on timescales relevant to cell-driven matrix remodeling. However, achieving controlled disulfide-mediated crosslinking in thiolated polymers remains challenging. Thiol groups are prone to premature oxidation under ambient conditions, which complicates material storage, handling, and reproducibility of the final hydrogel network. More recently, Aili and coworkers developed a strategy that allows precise control over the initiation of gelation in thiolated alginate through using an enzyme-responsive thiol-protecting group, namely phenylacetamidomethyl (Phacm) which can be specifically cleaved by penicillin G acylase, generating free thiol functionalities [201]. Crosslinking can be triggered under physiological conditions, both with and without Ca^{2+} ions. The final stiffness varied from 60 to 240 Pa while self-healing was observed at room temperature in 5 h. This system was further evaluated for cell encapsulation and as a bioink component for 3D bioprinting, allowing post-printing crosslinking and functionalization via thiol-reactive molecules. By enzymatically controlling thiol deprotection, this approach overcomes the longstanding challenge of premature sulfhydryl oxidation under ambient conditions, which has limited the practical use of thiol-based chemistries in hydrogel crosslinking and modification. In a study by Zhu and coworkers a diabetic wound model was selected as a representative injury to evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of injectable hypoxia-inducing hydrogels [202]. To improve healing outcomes and expand functional versatility, the

Fig. 24. Schematic of HRP-mediated cross-linking of thiol-norbornene click reactions and hydrogels before and after stiffening. Reprinted with permission from [75].

hypoxia-responsive system was integrated with a conductive network using an innovative sequential interpenetrating strategy that combined rapid click chemistry with slower enzyme-mediated crosslinking. Specifically, hyperbranched poly(β -amino ester)-tetraaniline was cross-linked with thiolated hyaluronic acid through thiol-ene reaction, enabling rapid formation of an initial conductive network. Subsequently, vanillin-grafted gelatin and laccase, which exhibit slower crosslinking kinetics, were incorporated to establish a sustained hypoxic microenvironment. The resulting injectable hydrogels displayed appropriate electrical conductivity along with prolonged hypoxia-inducing capacity, leading to upregulation of hypoxia-inducible factor-1 α and connexin 43 in encapsulated adipose-derived stem cells. This dual functionality promoted angiogenesis and immunomodulation, facilitated the regeneration of blood vessels, hair follicles, and dermal collagen, and ultimately accelerated wound closure and functional restoration in diabetic rat skin. Overall, this approach offers a versatile platform for overcoming prolonged gelation limitations in hydrogel systems and for integrating multiple biologically active networks, thereby broadening their therapeutic potential for diabetic wounds and other complex clinical conditions.

3. Design challenges

Despite these significant advancements, several challenges remain before clinical translation can be fully realized. Bio-based matrices such as chitosan, alginate, gelatin, cellulose, and hyaluronic acid inherently exhibit variability that significantly influences their performance in click-crosslinked hydrogel systems. Unlike synthetic polymers, these materials are extracted from biological sources and therefore suffer from batch-to-batch inconsistencies in properties such as molecular weight, degree of acetylation in chitosan, mannuronic/guluronic acid ratio of alginate, bloom strength of gelatin, oxidation level of cellulose derivatives, or degree of modification. Such variations directly affect the density and accessibility of reactive functional groups which are critical for efficient click conjugation. In click crosslinking systems, reaction efficiency depends not only on stoichiometric balance but also on steric accessibility and local microenvironment. In bio-based matrices, functional groups may be partially buried within secondary structures, engaged in hydrogen bonding, or unevenly distributed along the backbone, leading to heterogeneous crosslinking. Additionally, residual impurities such as proteins, endotoxins or metal ions can interfere with catalyst-driven click reactions or enzyme-mediated click systems, altering kinetics and network uniformity. Moreover, many naturally derived polymers exhibit limited solubility in common organic solvents which restricts the range of chemistries that can be applied and often limiting to aqueous or heterogeneous reaction conditions that can reduce reaction efficiency and reproducibility. In addition, the precise determination of conjugation efficiency and degree of substitution is also challenging. Routine characterization techniques such as ¹HNMR spectroscopy are frequently complicated by the inherently broad and overlapping resonance signals of biopolymers, arising from their polydispersity and complex backbone structures. These spectral complexities

hinder accurate peak integration and quantification, often requiring complementary analytical methods to reliably assess functionalization levels. Addressing these challenges will be essential for improving reproducibility, scalability, and translational potential of modified biopolymer systems.

Another critical yet underexplored issue is degradability. Bio-based polymers undergo hydrolytic or enzymatic degradation, which changes network architecture over time. In click-crosslinked systems, this may decouple crosslink density from long-term mechanical stability, particularly when degradation occurs preferentially at backbone sites rather than at click junctions. Consequently, mechanical properties, swelling behavior, and release kinetics may evolve unpredictably.

Since most hydrogel systems are developed and produced at small pilot-plant scale during preclinical stages, compliance with current good manufacturing practices (GMP) is essential for their clinical translation, large-scale production, and successful integration as biomaterial-based platforms, ensuring overall system compatibility. Click-chemistry based crosslinking can suffer several drawbacks. The residual copper in CuAAC must be removed rigorously to meet clinical tolerances which is a major hurdle for scaling due to purification complexities. At larger production scales, controlling oxidation state, catalyst distribution, and removal extends manufacturing time and cost. SPAAC eliminates metal catalysts, however strained alkyne reagents are often synthetically complex, limiting yields and scalability. Thiol-ene reactions are attractive for scalable synthesis due to cheap raw materials and controllable initiation yet they require uniform light penetration in large batches, which is difficult without specialized reactors. DA/iedDA reactions proceed without catalysts and often produce benign byproducts, but functionalizing biopolymers with tetrazines and dienophiles at scale can be challenging due to multi-step synthesis and purification of strained dienophiles. Across all chemistries, batch-to-batch reproducibility, mixing homogeneity, reagent availability, and process control remain significant engineering challenges in moving from bench-scale to manufacturing.

Ensuring sterility in click-crosslinked biobased hydrogels remains a significant translational hurdle because many conventional sterilization techniques compromise polymer integrity, functional groups, or introduce toxic residues. Natural polymer networks such as gelatin, hyaluronic acid, and alginate are susceptible to hydrolysis, chain scission, and loss of reactive functionality when exposed to heat, γ -irradiation, or ethylene oxide, which can diminish gelation performance and mechanical properties critical for clinical performance. They often carry endotoxins and GMP workflows must include validated removal and testing. Click chemistries, while bioorthogonal, do not inherently guarantee sterility. CuAAC approaches are further complicated by the need to remove residual copper catalysts that can induce cytotoxicity and inflammatory responses even after purification, and thorough removal often fails to reach acceptable biomedical thresholds without extensive washing or chelation. Metal-free click variants such as SPAAC, thiol-ene/yne, and Diels–Alder/iedDA alleviate metal toxicity but still require that each precursor solution be sterile and remain uncontaminated until point of crosslinking, often necessitating aseptic processing

in controlled cleanrooms rather than terminal sterilization. Photo-initiated thiol-ene systems may be sensitive to UV or gamma sterilization, which can degrade functional groups and compromise crosslinking. Strain-promoted systems must avoid sterilization methods that prematurely activate strained alkyne groups. Moreover, highly viscous prepolymer formulations cannot be terminally sterilized by filtration and are prone to microbial contamination during storage unless rigorously lyophilized or manufactured under GMP-grade aseptic conditions, further complicating scale-up and regulatory approval.

Storage is another critical translational parameter. Reactive functional groups such as maleimides, norbornenes, and tetrazines can undergo hydrolysis or oxidation during storage, reducing effective functional density and altering gelation kinetics. Strained alkynes in may rearrange or react with trace nucleophiles over time. Additionally, aqueous prepolymer formulations can gel prematurely or show viscosity drift on storage. Lyophilization under inert atmosphere may extend shelf-life but requires reconstitution workflows compatible with clinical workflow. Enzyme-mediated click systems might suffer activity loss upon storage unless stabilized with excipients.

Another challenging issue is the cost of materials. CuAAC reaction usually requires lower cost reagents but high downstream purification adds an extra cost. The synthesis of cyclooctyne derivatives require a multi-step and controlled procedure which increases costs, obstructing the scalability of these reactions. Moreover, GMP-grade biopolymers are orders of magnitude more expensive than research-grade materials. Enzyme catalysts like horseradish peroxidase or Sortase A add cost and cold-chain storage needs.

Despite the growing application of click chemistry in biohydrogels, systematic analyses linking raw material variability to click reaction efficiency, network homogeneity, and long-term performance remain limited. Future studies should integrate polymer characterization (molecular weight distribution, functional group quantification, purity profiling) with click reaction kinetics and mechanical mapping to better understand structure–property relationships in bio-based click-crosslinked matrices. The large-scale, reproducible synthesis of bio-clickable polymers, long-term biostability, and the control of degradation byproducts are areas that demand continued research. Cost and accessibility of certain click reagents, especially strained alkynes used in SPAAC, can also limit widespread adoption. Moreover, while the cytocompatibility of metal-free systems is well established, in-depth studies on long-term immune responses and in vivo degradation kinetics are still limited.

4. Conclusions

The emergence of click chemistry as a modular, high-yield, and biocompatible synthetic strategy has profoundly advanced the field of hydrogel design for biomedical applications. By enabling precise covalent linkage under mild, often aqueous and catalyst-free conditions, click reactions have made it possible to develop highly tunable, multifunctional hydrogel systems that meet the complex requirements of biological environments. These chemistries including, SPAAC, thiol-ene, thiol-Michael, Diels-Alder and iedDA reactions offer unmatched versatility for constructing three-dimensional polymeric networks with controllable mechanical strength, degradability, and bioactivity.

The functional groups naturally present in the biopolymer serve as the primary determinant for choosing the click reaction type. For example, protein-based polymers such as gelatin and collagen contain abundant primary amine groups, which can readily participate in reactions such as Schiff base formation or can be modified with alkenes, alkynes, maleimides, or azides to enable thiol-ene, Diels-Alder or azide-alkyne click reactions. In contrast, polysaccharides such as hyaluronic acid, alginate, and dextran are rich in hydroxyl and carboxyl groups; therefore, they are typically first functionalized with clickable handles such as azide, thiol, furan or norbornene groups before undergoing reactions such as strain-promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition, thiol-ene

coupling, Diels-Alder or inverse electron-demand Diels-Alder reactions. The polysaccharides are also suitable for Schiff base, oxime and hydrazone reactions as they can be easily oxidized to aldehydes. The desired gelation rate is another critical parameter. For injectable biomaterials bioorthogonal reactions such as iedDA or SPAAC are usually preferred as they exhibit very fast kinetics and are therefore useful for rapid in situ hydrogel formation. The stability or reversibility of the formed linkage should also match the intended application. Highly stable linkages such as the triazole rings formed in azide-alkyne reactions provide robust and long-lasting polymer networks, which are desirable for structural biomaterials. In contrast, dynamic bonds such as Schiff base, hydrazone, or certain amino-yne linkages can undergo hydrolysis or exchange reactions under physiological conditions, enabling self-healing behavior or controlled degradation. Thermoreversible reactions such as Diels-Alder cycloadditions allow networks that can dissociate under elevated temperatures, which may be useful for stimuli-responsive systems.

In biomedical engineering, click-based hydrogels have demonstrated remarkable performance across diverse applications. In drug delivery, they enable precise control over release kinetics, protect sensitive therapeutic agents, and minimize burst release effects. Hydrogels crosslinked via SPAAC or thiol-ene chemistry are particularly advantageous for encapsulating fragile biomolecules or living cells due to their catalyst-free and cytocompatible reaction pathways. Systems integrating pH, temperature, or enzyme-responsive linkages have been designed for on-demand release, targeted delivery, and synergistic combination therapies. The introduction of cyclodextrin, graphene oxide, and metal-polyphenol complexes has further expanded the functional scope of these hydrogels, allowing co-delivery of hydrophobic drugs, antioxidants, and bioactive ions with improved efficacy and reduced toxicity. In tissue engineering and regenerative medicine and wound dressing, click chemistry provides an unprecedented level of architectural and biochemical control over hydrogel scaffolds. Hybrid hydrogels incorporating natural polymers (collagen, chitosan, gelatin, hyaluronic acid, alginate, and pectin) with synthetic counterparts via click reactions mimic the ECM while offering tunable stiffness, porosity, and degradation rates. SPAAC-, DA-, and thiol-ene-based systems have enabled the fabrication of injectable, cell-laden scaffolds for cartilage, bone, and corneal regeneration. Studies using SPAAC-crosslinked collagen or hyaluronic acid networks have shown excellent transparency, elasticity, and cytocompatibility while thiol-norbornene or thiol-Michael systems have demonstrated success in promoting chondrogenic and osteogenic differentiation in stem-cell-laden constructs. Moreover, photo-clickable hydrogels have emerged as ideal platforms for in situ tissue formation and 3D bioprinting, due to their rapid and spatially controlled crosslinking capabilities. The reversible covalent nature of Diels-Alder reaction facilitates dynamic, stimuli-responsive networks with applications in tissue engineering and soft robotics. However, the relatively slow reaction kinetics at physiological temperatures and limited aqueous solubility of some diene/dienophile pairs constrain their utility in fast-gelling or injectable applications. Click-crosslinked hydrogels incorporating cell-adhesive peptides and MMP-sensitive sequences enable dynamic cell–matrix interactions, promoting fibroblast migration, angiogenesis, and re-epithelialization. Antibacterial and antioxidative hydrogels have demonstrated enhanced healing rates in infected wounds, emphasizing the potential of multifunctional, bioactive click hydrogels as advanced wound dressings. Some qualitative results based on the hydrogel properties of the studies discussed in this review are listed in [Table 2](#).

Beyond conventional applications, click chemistry-based hydrogels have begun to impact emerging biomedical fields such as biosensing, bioimaging, and immunomodulation. Their modular nature allows incorporation of fluorescent probes, responsive motifs, or immune-active components for real-time monitoring and therapeutic feedback. The integration of bioorthogonal reactions with metabolic glycoengineering has enabled in vivo formation of cell–material hybrid networks

Table 2
Hydrogel properties of several biomaterials synthesized with different click chemistry crosslinking

Reaction	Polymer/Functional Group	Application	Gelation time	Mechanical Strength	Degradation rate	Cytotoxicity	Remarks	Year ^{REF}
CuAAC	Gelatin/alkyne	Drug carrier	NA	50–390 kPa*	NA	Good	-	2018 [51]
CuAAC	Diazide crosslinker	Cartilage tissue engineering	NA	15-42 MPa*	NA	175% (7 days)	Triple network	2018 [52]
CuAAC	HA/Azide, alkyne	Drug carrier	few minutes	NA	NA	>80 %	Chitosan-Cu complex IPN, Dual crosslinking	2025 [53]
SPAAC	Cellulose/Alkyne	Cartilage tissue engineering	NA	10 MPa*	52% (14 days)	>90 %	-	2021 [57]
SPAAC	Chitosan/Azide	Sort tissue engineering	3-16 h	< 1 kPa**	NA	High	-	2023 [58]
SPAAC	HEC/Azide, alkyne	Corneal tissue regeneration	15 min	100 Pa**	NA	>70 % (6 days)	Encapsulated keratocytes	2018 [59]
SPAAC	Alginate/cyclooctyne bis azido- PVGLIG peptide	Corneal tissue regeneration	35-60 min	1000 Pa**	NA	> 80 %	IPN, dual crosslinking Michael reaction	2020 [60]
SPAAC	Collagen/DBCO, azide	Corneal tissue regeneration	5 min	2.46 MPa*	50% (48 h)	100-125 %	PRD and HGF delivery	2024 [61]
SPAAC	Nanocluster/DBCO	Corneal tissue regeneration	5 min	1000-3000 Pa**	NA	> 100 %	Photocleavable EGF	2024 [62]
SPAAC	Collagen/Azide	Cell therapies	1-15 min	0.5-45 kPa (stiffness)	2 months	>95% (7 days)	hASCs encapsulated	2023 [65]
SPAAC	HA/DBCO	Cartilage tissue engineering	18-144 s	100-1000 Pa**	70% (28 days)	5-7 fold (7 days)	Tannic acid clustering, hNCs	2025 [66]
Thiol-ene	Gelatin/DBCO	Tissue engineering	5 min	6-20 kPa (stiffness)	Proteolytic Degradation	85-87% (14 days)	Heparin conjugation, encapsulated Huh7 cells	2015 [77]
Thiol-ene	4-arm PEG-SH	Human motion sensing	73-539 s	15-33 kPa (tensile strength)	~20-60% (20 days)	~90% (2 days)	-	2023 [82]
Thiol-ene	Graphene/thiol	Biomedical	10 s	100-1000 Pa**	NA	90 % (3 days)	-	2022 [83]
Thiol-ene	HA/Norbornene	Skin tissue engineering	20 s	70-450 Pa (shear elastic modulus)	100% enzymatic (3-5 h)	Stable for 14 days	MMP cleavable peptide	2018 [84]
Thiol-ene	Pectin/Norbornene	Cartilage tissue engineering	2-3 min	300-7000 Pa**	~50-70% (25 days)	93-98% (7 days)	-	2021 [86]
Thiol-ene	Peptide crosslinker	Hemostatic dressing	10 min	28-200 Pa**	NA	>80% (3 days)	-	2022 [90]
Thiol-ene	CS/Thiol	Wound dressing	10-15 s	4.3-7.8 kPa*	60-80% (20 days)	~200 % (7 days)	Dual crosslink with free radical	2023 [91]
Thiol-ene	Chitosan/Ene, thiol	Cell culture scaffold	10-150 s	1.8-25 kPa*	NA	~80% (14 days)	-	2023 [92]
Thiol-ene	PEG-SH	Drug release	1-5 min	100-580 Pa**	100% enzymatic (14 days)	~100% (3 days)	DEX release for 26 days	2022 [93]
Thiol-ene	Cyclodextrin/Ene	Wound healing	30 s	18-21 kPa*	11% (24 days)	Favorable	Metal–polyphenol nanoparticles	2023 [94]
Thiol-ene	Gelatin/Thiol	Ophthalmic delivery	3 min	1000-10000 Pa**	~75-90% (30 days)	85-105% (2 days)	Timolol maleate loading	2025 [97]
Thiol-ene	Silk Fibroin/Ene	Wound healing	1 min	50-110 kPa*	70-75% (14 days)	80-100% (3 days)	-	2025 [98]
Thiol-ene	Gellan gum/Thiol PEG diacrylate	Wound healing	NA	2-4 Pa*	60-70% (14 days)	125% (7 days)	Bioactive glass nanoparticles	2026 [99]
Thiol-Michael	Gelatin/Ene	Corneal regeneration	72 h	800-4400 Pa**	71% (30 days)	95 % (7 days)	-	2023 [104]
Thiol-Michael	Collagen/Thiol	Cartilage regeneration	2-6 min	2000-12000 Pa**	55-75% (77h)	>90%	Secondary self-crosslinking	2020 [105]
Thiol-Michael	8-arm PEG maleimide	Cartilage regeneration	2 min	500-1000 Pa**	95% (28 days)	>85% (1 day)	Encapsulated CPCs	2020 [106]
Thiol-Michael	HA/Thiol	Tissue engineering	22-50 min	20.8–33.2 kPa (Compressive strength)	25-45% (15 days)	NA	Ibuprofen encapsulated	2025 [109]
Thiol-Michael	HA/Maleimide	Drug delivery	25-55 min	~490 Pa*	27-43% (15 days)	78-90% (2 days)	Diclofenac sodium release	2025 [110]
Thiol-Michael	CMG/Thiol	Wound healing	3 min	390-970 Pa**	~10% (42 days)	>100% (2 days)	-	2025 [112]
Thiol-yne	PEG acrylate	Soft tissue engineering	2 min	8.8-67.5 kPa*	21-63% (34 days) enzymatic	>81% (21 days)	IPN, secondary Ca ²⁺ crosslinked alginate	2020 [119]
Thiol-yne	alkyne-PEG	Follicle development	10-15 min	31-85 Pa**	NA	~80%	-	2023 [120]
Thiol-yne	Chitosan, HA/Thiol	Wound healing	<3 min	116 kPa*	NA	>100% (7 days)	Electro-responsive	2025 [121]
Thiol-yne	Cyclodextrin/Alkyne							
Thiol-yne	Alginate/Thiol							
Thiol-yne	3-arm alkyne-PEG							

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Reaction	Polymer/Functional Group	Application	Gelation time	Mechanical Strength	Degradation rate	Cytotoxicity	Remarks	Year ^{REF}
Thiol-yne	Alginate/Yne PEG-SH, DTT	Tissue engineering	98-237 s	21-34 kPa*	NA	Favorable	-	2022 [116]
Thiol-yne	HA/Yne	Bone defect repair	90 s	>1000Pa**	80% (28 days)	100% (2 days)	-	2025 [117]
DA	HA/Furan Bismaleimide PEG	3D Cell encapsulation	~12 min	1000-1300 Pa**	NA	>80% (7 days)	-	2018 [128]
DA	CS/Furan Bismaleimide PEG	Bone tissue engineering	65-75 s	~500 Pa**	~100% (14 days)	~144% (3 days)	BMP-4 loading	2017 [129]
DA	Chitosan/Furan Bismaleimide PEG	Drug carrier	40 min	~400 Pa**	25% (28 days)		Chloramphenicol release	2018 [132]
DA	Starch/Furan Bismaleimide	Drug delivery	NA	>1000 Pa**	NA	>80% (2 days)	CNC reinforcement	2020 [133]
DA	Gelatin/Furan Bismaleimide PEG	Cell therapy	2-30 h	18-42 kPa*	NA	>95% (7 days)	f-IPN hydrogel	2018 [134]
DA	Alginate/Furan 4-arm PEG maleimide	Soft tissue engineering	15-55 min	26-35 kPa*	NA	>90% (7 days)	Dual crosslinking with Ca ²⁺	2018 [135]
DA	Alginate/Furan Alginate/Maleimide	Controlled drug release	130 min	13.5-25.3 kPa*	3-7% (14 days)		-	2023 [141]
DA	HA/Furan CS/Maleimide	Regenerative medicine	15-21 min	0.2-0.5 MPa *	NA	~100% (7 days)	Double network hydrazone linkage	2022 [143]
DA	CMC/Furan Bismaleimide PEG	Wound healing	<490 s	1000-2100 Pa**	17% (6 days)	>100%	Curcumin release	2025 [148]
DA	HA/Furan, maleimide	Fertility treatment	2-4 min	2.8-21.7 kPa*	~100% (15 days)	>250% (3 days)	Loaded with UCMSCs	2024 [146]
DA	HA/Furan PEG-CD-Maleimide	Biomedical	1 h	>1000Pa**	40% (28 days)	>80% (2 days)	Dual click polyrotaxane	2025 [149]
iedDA	Alginate/Norbornene, tetrazine	Tissue engineering	1 h	100-1000 Pa**	NA	>80%	-	2015 [154]
iedDA	Gelatin/Norbornene, tetrazine	Tissue engineering	10-70 min	0.5-5 kPa*	Enzymatic degradation (2-14 days)	>85%	-	2021 [158]
iedDA	CMC/Norbornene Ditetrazine crosslinker	Cancer therapy	1-5 min	74-160 Pa**	81% PBS (30 days), 90% GSH (2.5 days)	>95%	DOX encapsulation	2022 [159]
iedDA	HA/Norbornene Ditetrazine crosslinker	Cancer therapy	155-509 s	50-300 Pa**	40% (20 days) PBS, 95% GSH (2 days)	100% (1 day)	DOX encapsulation	2022 [160]
iedDA	Chitosan/Norbornene Ditetrazine PEG	Cancer therapy	90-500 s	350-850 Pa**	NA	>95%	DOX encapsulation	2023 [161]
iedDA	Alginate/Norbornene Ditetrazine PEG	Drug release	250 s	1500-2800 Pa**	NA	>100%	DOX encapsulation	2022 [162]
iedDA	CMC/Norbornene Ditetrazine crosslinker	Drug delivery	170-495 s	120-270 Pa**	80% PBS, 40% NIR, 20% H ₂ O ₂ (40 days)	100% (2 days)	NIR-responsive DOX encapsulation	2024 [163]
iedDA	Chitosan/Norbornene Alginate/Tetrazine	Drug delivery	24 h	600-3500 Pa**	Enzymatic (4 days)	>95% (4 days)	Dual crosslink hydrophobic interaction	2022 [164]
iedDA	HA/Tetrazine Collagen/Norbornene	Bone tissue engineering	2-4 min	112-146 Pa*	In vivo degradation in 8 weeks	Favorable	CaSO ₄ nanorods-enriched	2023 [170]
Schiff	Chitosan	Ocular drug delivery	15-60 s	0.3-20 kPa**	5-55 % 25 days	>90% (1 day)	Betamethasone release	2022 [175]
Schiff	Dialdehyde starch Aminated HA Aldehyde β-CD	Drug release	1-3 min	60-80 kPa (Compression strength)	37-52% (60 days)	>100% (3 days)	Voriconazole release	2023 [176]
Schiff	Alginate/Aldehyde Gelatin/Amine	Bone regeneration	0.5-3 min	6-15 kPa**	60-80% (124 days)	>100% (3 days)	Curcumin loading	2022 [178]
Schiff	oxidized HA-tyramine hitosan	Therapeutic Applications	1-700s	10-20 kPa (Adhesion strength)	Enzymatic (1 week)	>85%	Enzymatic reaction+ionic interaction	2022 [179]
Schiff	Oxidized HA Chitosan	Wound healing	4-20 min	7-22 kPa (Adhesion strength)	Enzymatic (9 days)	>80% (2 days)	Enzyme-catalyzed cross-linking	2024 [182]
Schiff	HA/Aldehyde HA/Triamine	Wound healing	8-22 s	700-6300 Pa**	60-90% (20 days)	>80% (2 days)	Silver nanoparticles	2024 [183]
Oxime	HA/Aldehyde PEG-diaminoxy	Soft tissue engineering	1 day	2-12 kPa*	Enzymatic 60% (25 days)	>88% (2 days)	-	2015 [187]
Oxime	HA/Aldehyde PEG-diaminoxy	Drug screening	45 min	0.6-9.6 kPa*	100% (28 days)	favorable	-	2017 [188]
Oxime	HA/Aldehyde+ketone PEG-oxyamine	Cancer therapy	25-90 min	2-5 kPa*	Enzymatic 100% (28 days)	favorable	-	2019 [189]

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Reaction	Polymer/Functional Group	Application	Gelation time	Mechanical Strength	Degradation rate	Cytotoxicity	Remarks	Year ^{REF}
Oxime	Alginate/alkoxyamine	Biomedical applications	2-23 min	1.5-5.9 kPa**	NA	>85% (3 days)	Dual ionic crosslinking	2019 [190]
Hydrazone	Alginate/Aldehyde	Wound dressing	9 s	2400 Pa**	100% (72 h)	65-100% (1 day)	ROS scavenging	2024 [193]
Amino-yne	Collagen	Corneal repair	7 h	5-7 MPa (Tensile strength)	Enzymatic (30 h)	favorable	-	2022 [198]
Amino-yne	PEG-Alkyne	Tissue engineering	7.78-20.43 min	6-25 kPa*	100% (5-25 days)	100%	DOX encapsulation	2018 [197]
Amino-yne	HA/Adipic dihydrazide	Diabetic wound healing	4-10 min	500-4000 Pa**	100% (4-7 days)	~100%	-	2022 [199]
Enzymatic Thiol-norbornene	Gelatin/Norbornene	Biomedical applications	80 s	1-3 kPa**	NA	>90%	HRP/H ₂ O ₂	2019 [75]
Enzymatic Schiff	PEG-tetrathiol	Wound dressing	10-45 s	100-1000 Pa**	54-90% (40 h)	>90% (5 days)	HRP/H ₂ O ₂	2020 [200]
Enzymatic Thiol-ene	HA/Aldehyde	Diabetic wound healing	1 min	100-1000 Pa**	7 days	>85% (2 days)	IPN, hypoxia-induced Gel-Val-Laccase	2020 [202]
	ε-polylysine/DOPA							
	HA/Thiol hyperbranched poly(β-amino ester)-tetraaniline							

CS: Chondroitin sulfate * =Elastic modulus ** =Storage modulus

that enhance tissue integration and guide cell differentiation. Such systems bridge synthetic materials with biological processes, moving toward next-generation biohybrid constructs capable of active participation in healing and regeneration.

Future research should focus on integrating multi-click and orthogonal chemistries to construct hydrogels with hierarchical architectures and multiple biofunctions. Combining click reactions with emerging fabrication technologies such as 3D bioprinting, microfluidics, and organ-on-chip systems can yield hydrogels that better emulate tissue microenvironments and allow dynamic cellular communication. Additionally, coupling click hydrogels with stimuli-responsive or self-healing components will enable adaptive materials capable of responding to physiological cues.

In conclusion, click chemistry has emerged as a transformative platform in hydrogel science, offering simplicity, modularity, and precision for creating biomimetic and multifunctional materials. By bridging the gap between chemistry, biology, and medicine, these “clickable” hydrogels are poised to drive major advances in regenerative therapies, targeted drug delivery, and personalized medicine. Continued interdisciplinary collaboration will be key to unlocking their full clinical potential, paving the way toward a new generation of intelligent, patient-specific biomaterials for the future of healthcare.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ozlem Ipek Kalaoglu-Altan: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.
Marco Sangermano: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests.

Ozlem Ipek Kalaoglu Altan reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No [101105270].

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- Z. Ahmad, S. Salman, S.A. Khan, A. Amin, Z.U. Rahman, Y.O. Al-ghamdi, K. Akhtar, E.M. Bakhsh, S.B. Khan, Versatility of hydrogels: From synthetic strategies, classification, and properties to biomedical applications, *Gels* 8 (2022) 167, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels8030167>.
- T. Ho, C. Chang, H. Chan, T. Chung, C. Shu, K.-P. Chuang, T.-H. Duh, M.-H. Yang, Y.-C. Tyan, Hydrogels: Properties and applications in biomedicine, *Molecules* 27 (2022) 2902, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27092902>.
- O. Wichterle, D. Lim, Hydrophilic gels for biological use, *Nat. Publ. Gr.* 185 (1960) 117–118.
- S. Khan, A. Figueiras, Tailored polymeric hydrogels for regenerative medicine and drug delivery: From material design to clinical applications, *Int. J. Pharm.* 681 (2025) 125818, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2025.125818>.
- S. Pablo, M. Jimenez-Rosado, A. Romero, V. Perez-Puyana, Novel trends in hydrogel development for biomedical applications: A review, *Polymers (Basel)* 14 (2022) 3023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14153023>.
- Z. Liu, X. Ma, J. Liu, H. Zhang, D. Fu, Advances in the application of natural/synthetic hybrid hydrogels in tissue engineering and delivery systems: A comprehensive review, *Int. J. Pharm.* 672 (2025) 125323, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2025.125323>.
- I.M. Tayler, R.S. Stowers, Engineering hydrogels for personalized disease modeling and regenerative medicine, *Acta Biomater.* 132 (2021) 4–22, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2021.04.020>.
- M.U.A. Khan, G.M. Stojanovic, F.M. Bin Abdullah, A. Dolatshahi-Pirouz, H. E. Marei, N. Ashammakhi, A. Hasan, Fundamental properties of smart hydrogels for tissue engineering applications: A review, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 254 (2024) 127882, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.127882>.
- X. Wang, J. Zeng, D. Gan, K. Ling, M. He, J. Li, Y. Lu, Recent strategies and advances in hydrogel-based delivery platforms for bone regeneration, *Nano Micro Lett.* 17 (2025) 73, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40820-024-01557-4>.
- M. Umar, A. Khan, M. Azhar, M. Faizal, B. Abdullah, W.S. Al-arjan, G. M. Stojanovic, A. Hasan, Hydrogels: Classifications, fundamental properties, applications, and scopes in recent advances in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine—A comprehensive review, *Arab. J. Chem.* 17 (2024) 105968, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2024.105968>.
- Z. Zhang, C. He, X. Chen, Designing hydrogels for immunomodulation in cancer therapy and regenerative medicine, *Adv. Mater.* 36 (2024) 2308894, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202308894>.
- N.H. Thang, T.B. Chien, D.X. Cuong, Polymer-based hydrogels applied in drug delivery: An overview, *Gels* 9 (2023) 523, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels9070523>.
- T. Vermonden, R. Censi, W.E. Hennink, Hydrogels for protein delivery, *Chem. Rev.* 112 (2012) 2853–2888, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr200157d>.
- S. Salehi, S.M. Naghib, H.R. Garshasbi, S. Ghorbanzadeh, W. Zhang, Smart stimuli-responsive injectable gels and hydrogels for drug delivery and tissue engineering applications: A review, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 11 (2023) 1104126, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2023.1104126>.
- S. Chander, G.T. Kulkarni, N. Dhiman, H. Kharkwal, Protein-based nanohydrogels for bioactive delivery, *Front. Chem.* 9 (2021) 573748, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fchem.2021.573748>.
- B. Liu, K. Chen, Advances in Hydrogel-Based Drug Delivery Systems, *Gels* 10 (2024) 262, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels10040262>.

- [17] D.-M. Radulescu, I.A. Neacsu, A.M. Grumezescu, E. Andronescu, New insights of scaffolds based on hydrogels in tissue engineering, *Polymers (Basel)*. 14 (2022) 799, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14040799>.
- [18] A. Sun, X. He, X. Ji, D. Hu, M. Pan, L. Zhang, Z. Qian, Current research progress of photopolymerized hydrogels in tissue engineering, *Chin. Chem. Lett.* 32 (2021) 2117–2126, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccl.2021.01.048>.
- [19] R. Hama, A. Ulziibayar, J.W. Reinhardt, T. Watanabe, J. Kelly, T. Shinoka, Recent developments in biopolymer-based hydrogels for tissue engineering applications, *Biomolecules* 13 (2023) 280, <https://doi.org/10.3390/biom13020280>.
- [20] W. Zhang, L. Liu, H. Cheng, J. Zhu, X. Li, S. Ye, X. Li, Hydrogel-based dressings designed to facilitate wound healing, *Mater. Adv.* 5 (2023) 1364–1394, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3ma00682d>.
- [21] H. Nakajima, P. Dijkstra, K. Loos, The recent developments in biobased polymers toward general and engineering applications: Polymers that are upgraded from biodegradable polymers, analogous to petroleum-derived polymers, and newly developed, *Polymers (Basel)*. 9 (2017) 523, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym9100523>.
- [22] A. Segneanu, L.E. Bejenaru, C. Bejenaru, A. Blendea, G.D. Mogoşanu, A. Bită, E. R. Boia, Advancements in hydrogels: A comprehensive review of natural and synthetic innovations for biomedical applications, *Polymers (Basel)*. 17 (2025) 2026, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym17152026>.
- [23] F. Sepe, A. Valentino, L. Marcolongo, O. Pettillo, A. Calarco, S. Margarucci, G. Peluso, R. Conte, Polysaccharide hydrogels as delivery platforms for natural bioactive molecules: From tissue regeneration to infection control, *Gels* 11 (2025) 198, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels11030198>.
- [24] B.F. Far, M.R. Naimi-jamal, M. Safaei, K. Zarei, M. Moradi, H.Y. Nezhad, A review on biomedical application of polysaccharide-based hydrogels with a focus on drug delivery systems, *Polymers (Basel)*. 14 (2022) 5432, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14245432>.
- [25] Q. Zhang, Y. Liu, G. Yang, H. Kong, L. Guo, G. Wei, Recent advances in protein hydrogels: From design, structural and functional regulations to healthcare applications, *Chem. Eng. J.* 451 (2023) 138494, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.138494>.
- [26] G. Katona, B. Sipos, I. Csoka, Advancements in the field of protein-based hydrogels: Main types, characteristics, and their applications, *Gels* 11 (2025) 306, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels11050306>.
- [27] M. Rana, H. De, H. Siegler, Evolution of hybrid hydrogels: Next-generation biomaterials for drug delivery and tissue engineering, *Gels* 10 (2024) 216, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels10040216>.
- [28] B. Shan, F. Wu, Hydrogel-based growth factor delivery platforms: Strategies and recent advances, *Adv. Mater.* 36 (2024) 2210707, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202210707>.
- [29] W.E. Hennink, C.F. Van Nostrum, Novel crosslinking methods to design hydrogels, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 64 (2012) 223–236, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2012.09.009>.
- [30] X. Xue, Y. Hu, S. Wang, X. Chen, Y. Jiang, J. Su, Bioactive Materials Fabrication of physical and chemical crosslinked hydrogels for bone tissue engineering, *Bioact. Mater.* 12 (2022) 327–339, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioactmat.2021.10.029>.
- [31] J. Yang, Y. Chen, L. Zhao, J. Zhang, H. Luo, Constructions and properties of physically cross-linked hydrogels based on natural polymers, *Polym. Rev.* 63 (2023) 574–612, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15583724.2022.2137525>.
- [32] V.G. Muir, J.A. Burdick, Chemically modified biopolymers for the formation of biomedical hydrogels, *Chem. Rev.* 121 (2020) 10908–10949, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.0c00923>.
- [33] M. Sajjadi, R. Jamali, T. Kiyani, Z. Mohamadnia, A.R. Moradi, Characterization of Schiff base self-healing hydrogels by dynamic speckle pattern analysis, *Sci. Rep.* 14 (2024) 27950, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-79499-5>.
- [34] S. Almawash, S.K. Osman, G. Mustafa, M.A. El Hamd, Current and future prospective of injectable hydrogels-Design challenges and limitations, *Pharmaceuticals* 15 (2022) 371.
- [35] H.C. Kolb, M.G. Finn, K.B. Sharpless, Click chemistry: Diverse chemical function from a few good reactions, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 40 (2001) 2004–2021, [https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-3773\(20010601\)40:11<2004:AID-ANIE2004>3.0.CO;2-5](https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-3773(20010601)40:11<2004:AID-ANIE2004>3.0.CO;2-5).
- [36] S. Yigit, R. Sanyal, A. Sanyal, Fabrication and functionalization of hydrogels through “click” chemistry, *Chem. - An Asian J.* 6 (2011) 2648–2659, <https://doi.org/10.1002/asia.201100440>.
- [37] J. Gopinathan, I. Noh, Click chemistry-based injectable hydrogels and bioprinting inks for tissue engineering applications, *Tissue Eng. Regen. Med.* 15 (2018) 531, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13770-018-0152-8>.
- [38] X. Li, Y. Xiong, Application of “click” chemistry in biomedical hydrogels, *ACS Omega* 7 (2022) 36918–36928, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c03931>.
- [39] M. Malkoch, R. Vestberg, N. Gupta, L. Mespouille, P. Dubois, A.F. Mason, J. L. Hedrick, Q. Liao, C.W. Frank, K. Kingsbury, C.J. Hawker, Synthesis of well-defined hydrogel networks using Click chemistry, *Chem. Commun.* (2006) 2774–2776, <https://doi.org/10.1039/b603438a>.
- [40] D.A. Ossipov, J. Hilborn, Poly(vinyl alcohol)-based hydrogels formed by “click chemistry”, *Macromolecules* 39 (2006) 1709–1718.
- [41] L.M. Gaetke, C.K. Chow, Copper toxicity, oxidative stress, and antioxidant nutrients, *Toxicology* 189 (2003) 147–163, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0300-483X\(03\)00159-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0300-483X(03)00159-8).
- [42] C. Remzi Becer, R. Hoogenboom, U.S. Schubert, Click chemistry beyond metal-catalyzed cycloaddition, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 48 (2009) 4900–4908, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.200900755>.
- [43] D.M. Patterson, J.A. Prescher, Orthogonal bioorthogonal chemistries, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* 28 (2015) 141–149, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpa.2015.07.006>.
- [44] R.E. Bird, S.A. Lemmel, X. Yu, Q.A. Zhou, Bioorthogonal chemistry and its applications, *Bioconjug. Chem.* 32 (2021) 2457–2479, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.bioconjugchem.1c00461>.
- [45] A. Degimenci, R. Sanyal, A. Sanyal, Metal-free click-chemistry: A powerful tool for fabricating hydrogels for biomedical applications, *Bioconjug. Chem.* 35 (2024) 433–452, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.bioconjugchem.4c00003>.
- [46] D. Wu, K. Yang, Z. Zhang, Y. Feng, L. Rao, X. Chen, G. Yu, Metal-free bioorthogonal click chemistry in cancer theranostics, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 51 (2022) 1336–1376, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1CS00451D>.
- [47] A. Battigelli, B. Almeida, A. Shukla, Recent advances in bioorthogonal click chemistry for biomedical applications, *Bioconjug. Chem.* 33 (2022) 263–271, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.bioconjugchem.1c00564>.
- [48] H.Y. Yoon, D. Lee, D.K. Lim, H. Koo, K. Kim, Copper-free click chemistry: Applications in drug delivery, cell tracking, and tissue engineering, *Adv. Mater.* 34 (2022) 2107192, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202107192>.
- [49] M. Meldal, C.W. Tomøe, Cu-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition, *Chem. Rev.* 108 (2008) 2952–3015, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr0783479>.
- [50] E. Haldón, M.C. Nicasio, P.J. Pérez, Copper-catalysed azide-alkyne cycloadditions (CuAAC): an update, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* 13 (2015) 9528–9550, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5OB01457C>.
- [51] S. Piluso, R. Vukićević, U. Nöchel, S. Braune, A. Lendlein, A.T. Neffe, Sequential alkyne-azide cycloadditions for functionalized gelatin hydrogel formation, *Eur. Polym. J.* 100 (2018) 77–85, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2018.01.017>.
- [52] V. Engkagul, A. Sereemaspan, S. Chirachanchai, One pot preparation of chitosan/hyaluronic acid-based triple network hydrogel via in situ click reaction, metal coordination and polyion complexation in water, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 200 (2018) 616–623, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.07.090>.
- [53] B. Zhang, C. Hu, M. Wang, H. Wei, S. Li, H. Yu, Y. Wu, G. Wang, T. Guo, H. Chen, Facile fabrication of a thermal/pH responsive IPN hydrogel drug carrier based on cellulose and chitosan through simultaneous dual-click strategy, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 678 (2025) 827–841, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2024.08.208>.
- [54] J.A. Prescher, C.R. Bertozzi, Chemistry in Living Systems, *Nat. Chem. Biol.* 1 (2005) 13–21, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nchembio0605-13>.
- [55] Y. Shen, A.M. Esper, I. Ghiviriga, K.A. Abboud, K.S. Schanze, C. Ehm, A.S. Veige, SPAAC iClick: Progress towards a bioorthogonal reaction in-corporating metal ions, *Dalton Trans.* 50 (2021) 12681–12691, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1dt02626g>.
- [56] R. Upadhyay, S. Rastogi, A.K. Mishra, S. Yadav, A.K. Yadav, S.K. Maurya, Progress in strain promoted azide-alkyne cycloaddition (SPAAC) reaction and their applications, *Asian J. Org. Chem.* 14 (2025) e05055, <https://doi.org/10.1002/AJOC.202500505>.
- [57] M. Nouri-Felekari, N. Nezafati, M. Moraveji, S. Hesaraki, T. Ramezani, Bioorthogonal hydroxyethyl cellulose-based scaffold crosslinked via click chemistry for cartilage tissue engineering applications, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 183 (2021) 2030–2043, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2021.06.005>.
- [58] M.I. Neves, M.V. Magalhães, S.J. Bidarra, L. Moroni, C.C. Barrias, Versatile click alginate hydrogels with protease-sensitive domains as cell responsive/instructive 3D microenvironments, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 320 (2023) 121226, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2023.121226>.
- [59] H.J. Lee, G.M. Fernandes-Cunha, K.-S. Na, S.M. Hull, D. Myung, Bio-orthogonally crosslinked, in situ forming corneal stromal tissue substitute, *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* 7 (2018) 1800560, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adhm.201800560>.
- [60] F. Chen, P. Le, K. Lai, G.M. Fernandes-Cunha, D. Myung, Simultaneous interpenetrating polymer network of collagen and hyaluronic acid as an in situ-forming corneal defect filler, *Chem. Mater.* 32 (2020) 5208–5216, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.0c01307>.
- [61] N.W. Kang, K. Jang, E. Song, U. Han, Y.A. Seo, F. Chen, T. Wungcharoen, S. C. Heilshorn, D. Myung, In situ-forming, bioorthogonally cross-linked, nanocluster-reinforced hydrogel for the regeneration of corneal defects, *ACS Nano* 18 (2024) 21925–21938, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.4c02345>.
- [62] N.W. Kang, Y.A. Seo, K.J. Jackson, K. Jang, E. Song, U. Han, F. Chen, S. C. Heilshorn, D. Myung, Photoactivated growth factor release from bio-orthogonally crosslinked hydrogels for the regeneration of corneal defects, *Bioact. Mater.* 40 (2024) 417–429, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioactmat.2024.05.045>.
- [63] N. Ueda, S. Sawada, F. Yuasa, K. Kato, K. Nagahama, Covalent stem cell-combining injectable materials with enhanced stemness and controlled differentiation in vivo, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 14 (2022) 52618–52633, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.2c12918>.
- [64] F. Chen, U. Han, T. Wungcharoen, Y.A. Seo, P. Le, L. Jiang, N.W. Kang, E. Song, K. Jang, D. Mundy, G.M. Fernandes-Cunha, S. Heilshorn, D. Myung, Bio-orthogonal crosslinking and hyaluronan facilitate transparent healing after treatment of deep corneal injuries with in situ-forming hydrogels, *npj Regen. Med.* 10 (2025) 8, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41536-024-00385-9>.
- [65] N. Lagneau, P. Tournier, B. Halgand, F. Loll, Y. Maugars, J. Guicheux, C. Le Visage, V. Delplace, Click and bioorthogonal hyaluronic acid hydrogels as an ultra-tunable platform for the investigation of cell-material interactions, *Bioact. Mater.* 24 (2023) 438–449, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioactmat.2022.12.022>.
- [66] J.H. Jeon, S.Y. Cheon, S.H. Park, H. Lee, S.Y. Yoo, M.Y. Ahn, D. Lee, M.S. Kim, J. H. Park, S.J. Hollister, H. Koo, S.W. Kim, Lacuna-mimic human-derived nasal septal chondrocyte clusters encapsulated in click chemistry-based hydrogel for in vivo cartilage regeneration, *Chem. Eng. J.* 520 (2025) 165965, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.165965>.
- [67] L.G. Brunel, C.M. Long, F. Christakopoulos, B. Cai, P.K. Johansson, D. Singhal, A. Enejder, D. Myung, S.C. Heilshorn, Interpenetrating networks of fibrillar and amorphous collagen promote cell spreading and hydrogel stability, *Acta Biomater.* 193 (2025) 128–142, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2025.01.009>.

- [68] L.G. Brunel, C.M. Long, F. Christakopoulos, B. Cai, N. de Paiva Narciso, P. K. Johansson, D. Singhal, N.J. Baugh, D. Zhang, A. Enejder, D. Myung, S. C. Heilshorn, Reinforcement of fibrillar collagen hydrogels with bioorthogonal covalent crosslinks, *Biomacromolecules* 26 (2025) 4404–4418, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.5c00398>.
- [69] C.E. Hoyle, C.N. Bowman, Thiol-ene click chemistry, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 49 (2010) 1540–1573, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.200903924>.
- [70] A.B. Lowe, Thiol-ene “click” reactions and recent applications in polymer and materials synthesis, *Polym. Chem.* 1 (2010) 17–36, <https://doi.org/10.1039/b9py00216b>.
- [71] C.E. Hoyle, A.B. Lowe, C.N. Bowman, Thiol-click chemistry: a multifaceted toolbox for small molecule and polymer synthesis, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 39 (2010) 1355–1387, <https://doi.org/10.1039/b901979k>.
- [72] P.M. Kharkar, M.S. Rehmann, K.M. Skeens, E. Maverakis, A.M. Kloxin, Thiol-ene click hydrogels for therapeutic delivery, *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* 2 (2016) 165–179, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbomaterials.5b00420>.
- [73] S. Summonte, G.F. Racaniello, A. Lopodota, N. Denora, A. Bernkop-Schnürch, Thiolated polymeric hydrogels for biomedical application: Cross-linking mechanisms, *J. Control. Release* 330 (2021) 470–482, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2020.12.037>.
- [74] C.C. Lin, C.S. Ki, H. Shih, Thiol-norbornene photoclick hydrogels for tissue engineering applications, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 132 (2015) 41563, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.41563>.
- [75] H.D. Nguyen, H.Y. Liu, B.N. Hudson, C.C. Lin, Enzymatic cross-linking of dynamic thiol-norbornene click hydrogels, *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* 5 (2019) 1247–1256, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbomaterials.8b01607>.
- [76] T.E. Brown, K.S. Anseth, Spatiotemporal hydrogel biomaterials for regenerative medicine, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 46 (2017) 6532–6552, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7cs00445a>.
- [77] T. Greene, C.C. Lin, Modular cross-linking of gelatin-based thiol-norbornene hydrogels for in vitro 3D culture of hepatocellular carcinoma cells, *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* 1 (2015) 1314–1323, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbomaterials.5b00436>.
- [78] H.Y. Liu, M. Korc, C.C. Lin, Biomimetic and enzyme-responsive dynamic hydrogels for studying cell-matrix interactions in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma, *Biomaterials* 160 (2018) 24–36, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2018.01.012>.
- [79] M.H. Kim, H. Nguyen, C.Y. Chang, C.C. Lin, Dual functionalization of gelatin for orthogonal and dynamic hydrogel cross-linking, *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* 7 (2021) 4196–4208, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbomaterials.1c00709>.
- [80] L. Maleki, U. Edlund, A.C. Albertsson, Synthesis of full interpenetrating hemicellulose hydrogel networks, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 170 (2017) 254–263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2017.04.091>.
- [81] Y. Li, Y. Tan, K. Xu, C. Lu, P. Wang, A biodegradable starch hydrogel synthesized via thiol-ene click chemistry, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 137 (2017) 75–82, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2016.07.015>.
- [82] N. Salimiyan, M. Gholami, R. Sedghi, Preparation of degradable, biocompatible, conductive and multifunctional chitosan/thiol-functionalized graphene nanocomposite hydrogel via click chemistry for human motion sensing, *Chem. Eng. J.* 471 (2023) 144648, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.144648>.
- [83] X. Xiao, Z. Huang, X. Jiang, Y. Yang, L. Yang, S. Yang, C. Niu, Y. Xu, L. Feng, Facile synthesis of norbornene-hyaluronic acid to form hydrogel via thiol-norbornene reaction for biomedical application, *Polymer (Guildf)*. 245 (2022) 124696, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2022.124696>.
- [84] R.F. Pereira, C.C. Barrias, P.J. Bártolo, P.L. Granja, Cell-instructive pectin hydrogels crosslinked via thiol-norbornene photo-click chemistry for skin tissue engineering, *Acta Biomater.* 66 (2018) 282–293, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2017.11.016>.
- [85] C. Buckley, T.R. Montgomery, T. Szank, B.A. Murray, C. Quigley, I. Major, Modification of hyaluronic acid to enable click chemistry photo-crosslinking of hydrogels with tailorable degradation profiles, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 240 (2023) 124459, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.124459>.
- [86] X. Li, Q. Xu, M. Johnson, X. Wang, J. Lyu, Y. Li, S. McMahon, O. Greiser, A. Sigen, W. Wang, A chondroitin sulfate based injectable hydrogel for delivery of stem cells in cartilage regeneration, *Biomater. Sci.* 9 (2021) 4139–4148, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1bm00482d>.
- [87] C.Y. Chang, H.C. Johnson, O. Babb, M.L. Fishel, C.C. Lin, Biomimetic stiffening of cell-laden hydrogels via sequential thiol-ene and hydrazine click reactions, *Acta Biomater.* 130 (2021) 161–171, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2021.05.054>.
- [88] S. Lee, C. Woo, C.S. Ki, Pectin nanogel formation via thiol-norbornene photo-click chemistry for transcutaneous antigen delivery, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 108 (2022) 159–169, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2021.12.038>.
- [89] T.X. Morrison, W.M. Gramlich, Tunable, thiol-ene, interpenetrating network hydrogels of norbornene-modified carboxymethyl cellulose and cellulose nanofibrils, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 319 (2023) 121173, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2023.121173>.
- [90] S. Wang, X. Ji, S. Chen, C. Zhang, Y. Wang, H. Lin, L. Zhao, Study of double-bonded carboxymethyl chitosan/cysteamine-modified chondroitin sulfate composite dressing for hemostatic application, *Eur. Polym. J.* 162 (2022) 110875, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2021.110875>.
- [91] F. Liu, L. Wang, X. Zhai, S. Ji, J. Ye, Z. Zhu, C. Teng, W. Dong, W. Wei, A multi-functional double cross-linked chitosan hydrogel with tunable mechanical and antibacterial properties for skin wound dressing, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 322 (2023) 121344, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2023.121344>.
- [92] R. Pamplona, S. González-Lana, P. Romero, I. Ochoa, R. Martín-Rapún, C. Sánchez-Somolinos, Tuning of mechanical properties in photopolymerizable gelatin-based hydrogels for in vitro cell culture systems, *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* 5 (2023) 1487–1498, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscpm.2c01980>.
- [93] P. Le Thi, T.Y.N. Tran, H.C. Luu, D.L. Tran, T.T.H. Thi, D.H. Nguyen, In situ forming gelatin: Cyclodextrin hydrogels prepared by “click chemistry” to improve the sustained release of hydrophobic drugs, *J. Bioact. Compat. Polym.* 37 (2022) 252–266, <https://doi.org/10.1177/08839115221098058>.
- [94] Z. Zeng, J. Guo, G. Shen, C. Guo, D. Pei, D. Lu, Z. Geng, J. Huang, S. Yu, Antibacterial-antioxidative thiolated gelatin/methacrylated silk fibroin hydrogels with nitric oxide release catalyzed by metal-polyphenol nanoparticles for MRSA-infected wound healing, *Biomacromolecules* 24 (2023) 5116–5131, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.3c00696>.
- [95] M.R. Arkenberg, K. Koehler, C.C. Lin, Heparinized gelatin-based hydrogels for differentiation of induced pluripotent stem cells, *Biomacromolecules* 23 (2022) 4141–4152, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.2c00585>.
- [96] M.M. Fares, Z.H. Jabani, L.A. Abu-Haniyi, Synthesis of novel bioadhesive hydrogels via facile thiol-ene click chemistry for wound healing applications, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 270 (2024) 132501, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.132501>.
- [97] G. Shajari, H. Erfan-Niya, M. Fathi, N. Amiraghoubi, Thiolated gellan gum/polyethylene glycol diacrylate hydrogels containing timolol maleate-loaded chitosan nanoparticles for ophthalmic delivery, *Biomater. Mater.* 20 (2025) 025029, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-605X/adb555>.
- [98] Z. Zheng, N. Wang, H. Yang, X. Gong, J. Zheng, Y. Bai, P. Tang, S. Chen, W. Chen, Click chemistry-driven adhesive hydrogel for efficient healing of infected wounds through multistage comprehensive management, *J. Mater. Chem. B* 13 (2025) 11582–11596, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d5tb01743b>.
- [99] X. Jian, D. Liu, X. Liu, X. Zhao, Y. Zhu, S. Xia, E. Peng, M. Zhao, J. Yi, G. Jiang, D. Xu, K. Cheng, W. Weng, Z. Zhu, B. Shi, B. Tang, Thiol-ene photoclick hydrogels reinforced with poly(protocatechualdehyde)-coated gallium doped bioactive glass nanoparticles for scarless healing of infected wound, *Biomaterials* 324 (2026) 123469, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2025.123469>.
- [100] C.F.H. Allen, J.O. Fournier, W.J. Humphlett, The thermal reversibility of the Michael reaction: IV. Thiol adduct, *Can. J. Chem.* 42 (1964) 641–649, <https://doi.org/10.1139/v64-094>.
- [101] R.J. Pounder, M.J. Stanford, P. Brooks, S.P. Richards, A.P. Dove, Metal free thiol-maleimide “click” reaction as a mild functionalisation strategy for degradable polymers, *Chem. Commun.* 41 (2008) 5158–5160, <https://doi.org/10.1039/b809167f>.
- [102] D.P. Nair, M. Podgórski, S. Chatani, T. Gong, W. Xi, C.R. Fenoli, C.N. Bowman, The Thiol-Michael addition click reaction: A powerful and widely used tool in materials chemistry, *Chem. Mater.* 26 (2014) 724–744, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm402180t>.
- [103] J. Pupkaite, J. Rosenquist, J. Hilborn, A. Samanta, Injectable shape-holding collagen hydrogel for cell encapsulation and delivery cross-linked using thiol-Michael addition click reaction, *Biomacromolecules* 20 (2019) 3475–3484, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.9b00769>.
- [104] J. Rosenquist, M. Folkesson, L. Höglund, J. Pupkaite, J. Hilborn, A. Samanta, An injectable, shape-retaining collagen hydrogel cross-linked using thiol-maleimide click chemistry for sealing corneal perforations, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15 (2023) 34407–34418, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscami.3c03963>.
- [105] Y. Yao, P. Wang, X. Li, Y. Xu, G. Lu, Q. Jiang, Y. Sun, Y. Fan, X. Zhang, A di-self-crosslinking hyaluronan-based hydrogel combined with type I collagen to construct a biomimetic injectable cartilage-filling scaffold, *Acta Biomater.* 111 (2020) 197–207, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2020.05.007>.
- [106] X. Li, A. Sigen, Q. Xu, F. Alshehri, M. Zeng, D. Zhou, J. Li, G. Zhou, W. Wang, Cartilage-derived progenitor cell-laden injectable hydrogel-An approach for cartilage tissue regeneration, *ACS Appl. Bio Mater.* 3 (2020) 4756–4765, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscabm.0c00294>.
- [107] K.M. Yoo, S.V. Murphy, A. Skardal, A rapid crosslinkable maleimide-modified hyaluronic acid and gelatin hydrogel delivery system for regenerative applications, *Gels* 7 (2021) 13, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels7010013>.
- [108] S. Bang, U.W. Jung, I. Noh, Synthesis and biocompatibility characterizations of in situ chondroitin sulfate-gelatin hydrogel for tissue engineering, *Tissue Eng. Regen. Med.* 15 (2018) 25–35, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13770-017-0089-3>.
- [109] H.Y. Alharbi, R.B. Alnoman, M.S. Aljohani, M. Monier, Synthesis of functional pectin-based hydrogels via thiol-maleimide click reaction for enhanced drug encapsulation and release, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 142 (2025) e56837, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.56837>.
- [110] R.B. Alnoman, H.Y. Alharbi, M.S. Aljohani, K.B. Alomari, M. Monier, Development of a thiol-maleimide crosslinked carboxymethyl guar gum hydrogel for sustained drug delivery, *J. Drug Delivery Sci. Technol.* 105 (2025) 106633, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2025.106633>.
- [111] V. Torresan, A. Gandin, P. Contessotto, F. Zanconato, G. Brusatin, Injectable hyaluronic acid-based hydrogel niches to create localized and time-controlled therapy delivery, *Mater. Today Bio* 31 (2025) 101510, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtbio.2025.101510>.
- [112] Y. Wang, G. Zhao, A. Sigen, Q. Xu, X. Wu, W.-X. Wang, Y. Rui, In situ forming hypoxia-induced exosome-loaded hydrogel for enhanced diabetic wound healing, *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* 310 (2025) 2400402, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mame.202400402>.
- [113] L. Sathi Devi, M.R. Gigliobianco, S. Gabrielli, D. Agas, M.G. Sabbieti, M. B. Morelli, C. Amantini, C. Casadidio, P. Di Martino, R. Censi, Localized cancer treatment using thiol-ene hydrogels for dual drug delivery, *Biomacromolecules* 26 (2025) 3234–3254, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.5c00387>.

- [114] A.B. Lowe, C.E. Hoyle, C.N. Bowman, Thiol-yne click chemistry: A powerful and versatile methodology for materials synthesis, *J. Mater. Chem.* 20 (2010) 4745–4750, <https://doi.org/10.1039/b917102a>.
- [115] A.B. Lowe, Thiol-yne 'click' coupling chemistry and recent applications in polymer and materials synthesis and modification, *Polymer (Guildf)*. 55 (2014) 5517–5549, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2014.08.015>.
- [116] M. Zanon, L. Montalvillo-Jiménez, P. Bosch, R. Cue-López, E. Martínez-Campos, M. Sangermano, A. Chiappone, Photocurable thiol-yne alginate hydrogels for regenerative medicine purposes, *Polymers (Basel)*. 14 (2022) 4709, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14214709>.
- [117] A. Lo Re, Y. Fan, G. Pitarresi, F.S. Palumbo, G. Biscari, M. Malkoch, C. Fiorica, Thiol-yne crosslinked nanocomposite hyaluronic acid hydrogels as in situ-forming bone grafts for the treatment of irregular bone defects, *Chem. Mater.* 37 (2025) 9440–9450, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.5c01899>.
- [118] A. Sradha, L. George Sariga, A. Varghese, Advancements in thiol-yne click chemistry: Recent trends and applications in polymer synthesis and functionalization, *Mater. Today Chem.* 38 (2024) 102112, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtchem.2024.102112>.
- [119] M.M. Pérez-Madriral, J.E. Shaw, M.C. Arno, J.A. Hoyland, S.M. Richardson, A. P. Dove, Robust alginate/hyaluronic acid thiol-yne click-hydrogel scaffolds with superior mechanical performance and stability for load-bearing soft tissue engineering, *Biomater. Sci.* 8 (2020) 405–412, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9bm01494b>.
- [120] S. Khunmanee, J. Yoo, J.R. Lee, J. Lee, H. Park, Thiol-yne click crosslink hyaluronic acid/chitosan hydrogel for three-dimensional in vitro follicle development, *Mater. Today Bio* 23 (2023) 100867, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtbio.2023.100867>.
- [121] M.D. Ramírez-Alba, L. Resina, J. García-Torres, R. Macovez, C. Alemán, M. M. Pérez-Madriral, Thiol-yne crosslinked alginate click-hydrogel for the electrical stimulation of skin wound healing, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 322 (2025) 146880, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.146880>.
- [122] O. Diels, K. Alder, Synthesen in der hydroaromatischei, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.* 460 (1928) 98–122, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jlac.19284600106>.
- [123] A. Sanyal, Diels-alder cycloaddition-cycloreversion: A powerful combo in materials design, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* 211 (2010) 1417–1425, <https://doi.org/10.1002/macp.201000108>.
- [124] M.A. Tasdelen, Diels–Alder “click” reactions: Recent applications in polymer and material science, *Polym. Chem.* 2 (2011) 2133, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c1py00041a>.
- [125] F. Cadamuro, L. Russo, F. Nicotra, Biomedical hydrogels fabricated using Diels–Alder crosslinking, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* 2021 (2001) 374–382, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejoc.202001042>.
- [126] T.J. Yeingst, A.M. Helton, D.J. Hayes, Applications of Diels–Alder chemistry in biomaterials and drug delivery, *Macromol. Biosci.* 24 (2024) 2400274, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mabi.202400274>.
- [127] S.A. Fisher, P.N. Anandakumaran, S.C. Owen, M.S. Shoichet, Tuning the microenvironment: Click-crosslinked hyaluronic acid-based hydrogels provide a platform for studying breast cancer cell invasion, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 25 (2015) 7163–7172, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201502778>.
- [128] L.J. Smith, S.M. Taimoory, R.Y. Tam, A.E.G. Baker, N. Binth Mohammad, J. F. Trant, M.S. Shoichet, Diels–Alder click-cross-linked hydrogels with increased reactivity enable 3D cell encapsulation, *Biomacromolecules* 19 (2018) 926–935, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.7b01715>.
- [129] S. Liu, X. Bai, H. Liu, P. Ning, Z. Wang, C. Gao, B. Ni, M. Liu, An injectable and self-healing hydrogel with covalent cross-linking: In vivo for cranial bone repair, *J. Mater. Chem. B* 5 (2017) 3739–3748, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7tb00776k>.
- [130] S. Li, L. Wang, X. Yu, C. Wang, Z. Wang, Synthesis and characterization of a novel double cross-linked hydrogel based on Diels–Alder click reaction and coordination bonding, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* 82 (2018) 299–309, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2017.08.031>.
- [131] K. González, C. García-Astrain, A. Santamaria-Echart, L. Ugarte, L. Avérous, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, Starch/graphene hydrogels via click chemistry with relevant electrical and antibacterial properties, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 202 (2018) 372–381, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.09.007>.
- [132] O. Guaresti, C. García-Astrain, R.H. Aguirresarobe, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, Synthesis of stimuli-responsive chitosan-based hydrogels by Diels–Alder cross-linking 'click' reaction as potential carriers for drug administration, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 183 (2018) 278–286, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2017.12.034>.
- [133] K. González, O. Guaresti, T. Palomares, A. Alonso-Varona, A. Eceiza, N. Gabilondo, The role of cellulose nanocrystals in biocompatible starch-based clicked nanocomposite hydrogels, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 143 (2020) 265–272, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.12.050>.
- [134] H.S. Abandansari, M.H. Ghanian, F. Varzideh, E. Mahmoudi, S. Rajabi, P. Taheri, M.R. Nabid, H. Baharvand, In situ formation of interpenetrating polymer network using sequential thermal and click crosslinking for enhanced retention of transplanted cells, *Biomaterials* 170 (2018) 12–25, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2018.04.007>.
- [135] M.H. Ghanian, H. Mirzadeh, H. Baharvand, In situ forming, cytocompatible, and self-recoverable tough hydrogels based on dual ionic and click cross-linked alginate, *Biomacromolecules* 19 (2018) 1646–1662, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.8b00140>.
- [136] G. Wang, J. Zhu, X. Chen, H. Dong, Q. Li, L. Zeng, X. Cao, Alginate based antimicrobial hydrogels formed by integrating Diels–Alder “click chemistry” and the thiol-ene reaction, *RSC Adv.* 8 (2018) 11036–11042, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA00668G>.
- [137] C. García-Astrain, L. Avérous, Synthesis and evaluation of functional alginate hydrogels based on click chemistry for drug delivery applications, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 190 (2018) 271–280, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2018.02.086>.
- [138] C. García-Astrain, L. Avérous, Synthesis and behavior of click cross-linked alginate hydrogels: Effect of cross-linker length and functionality, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 137 (2019) 612–619, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2019.07.010>.
- [139] C. García-Astrain, A. Gandini, C. Peña, I. Algar, A. Eceiza, M. Corcuera, N. Gabilondo, Diels–Alder “click” chemistry for the cross-linking of furfuryl-gelatin-polyetheramine hydrogels, *RSC Adv.* 4 (2014) 35578–35587, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4ra06122e>.
- [140] C. Ocando, S. Dinescu, I. Samoila, C. Daniela Ghitulica, A. Cucuruz, M. Costache, L. Averous, Fabrication and properties of alginate-hydroxyapatite biocomposites as efficient biomaterials for bone regeneration, *Eur. Polym. J.* 151 (2021) 110444, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2021.110444>.
- [141] A.S. Alhawiti, N.H. Elsayed, F.M. Almutairi, F.A. Alotaibi, M. Monier, G.J. E. Alatwi, Construction of a biocompatible alginate-based hydrogel cross-linked by Diels–Alder chemistry for controlled drug release, *React. Funct. Polym.* 187 (2023) 105578, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reactfunctpolym.2023.105578>.
- [142] R. Debone Piazza, J.V. Brandt, C. Carvalho dos Santos, R. Fernando Costa Marques, M. Jafellici Junior, Gelatin/dextran-based hydrogel cross-linked by Diels–Alder click chemistry: The swelling and potassium diclofenac releasing, *Med. Devices Sensors* 4 (2021) e10151, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds3.10151>.
- [143] M. Mihajlovic, M. Rikkers, M. Mihajlovic, M. Viola, G. Schuiringa, B. C. Ilochonwu, R. Masereeuw, L. Vonk, J. Malda, K. Ito, T. Vermonden, Viscoelastic chondroitin sulfate and hyaluronic acid double-network hydrogels with reversible cross-links, *Biomacromolecules* 23 (2022) 1350–1365, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.1c01583>.
- [144] H. Wei, S. Li, Z. Liu, H. Chen, Y. Liu, W. Li, G. Wang, Preparation and characterization of starch-cellulose interpenetrating network hydrogels based on sequential Diels–Alder click reaction and photopolymerization, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 194 (2022) 962–973, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2021.11.154>.
- [145] Y. Bas, R. Sanyal, A. Sanyal, Hyaluronic-acid based redox-responsive hydrogels using the Diels–Alder reaction for on-demand release of biomacromolecules, *J. Macromol. Sci. Part A, Pure Appl. Chem.* 60 (2023) 246–254, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10601325.2023.2190357>.
- [146] S. Hu, Y. Dai, L. Xin, X. Zheng, Z. Ye, S. Zhang, L. Ma, Minimally invasive delivery of human umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cells by an injectable hydrogel via Diels–Alder click reaction for the treatment of intraterrine adhesions, *Acta Biomater.* 177 (2024) 77–90, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2024.02.001>.
- [147] I. Gholamali, S.-H. Jo, W. Han, J. Lim, A. Rizwan, S.-H. Park, K.T. Lim, The Diels–Alder cross-linked gelatin/dextran nanocomposite hydrogels with silver nanoparticles for wound healing applications: Synthesis, characterization, and in vitro evaluation, *Gels* 10 (2024) 408, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels10060408>.
- [148] I. Ali, U. Shahid, S. Kim, S. Ramamoorthy, W. Han, M. Kim, CMC-based injectable hydrogels crosslinked by Diels–Alder chemistry for wound healing applications, *Gels* 11 (2025) 674, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels11090674>.
- [149] S. Qin, M. Wang, H. Wei, Y. Ren, G. Wang, T. Guo, Q. Zhang, M. Yan, H. Chen, Self-healing hyaluronic acid/polylysine hydrogel prepared by dual-click chemistry from polyrotaxane slidable crosslinkers, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 680 (2025) 157–172, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2024.11.083>.
- [150] F. Segujija, G. Duruksu, E.B. Eren, A. İsayeva, Y. Yazır, A. Erdem, Diels–Alder-based IPN hydrogels with tunable mechanical and protein release properties for tissue engineering, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 306 (2025) 141779, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.141779>.
- [151] M.L. Blackman, M. Royzen, J.M. Fox, Tetrazine ligation: Fast bioconjugation based on inverse-electron-demand Diels–Alder reactivity, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 130 (2008) 13518–13519, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja8053805>.
- [152] B.L. Oliveira, Z. Guo, G.J.L. Bernardes, Inverse electron demand Diels–Alder reactions in chemical biology, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 46 (2017) 4895–4950, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7cs00184c>.
- [153] L. Yan, Z. Zhao, Y. Liu, S.H. Hosseini, C. Li, Y. Huang, M.R. Saeb, H. Xiao, F. Seidi, The inverse electron demand diels-alder (IEDDA): A facile bioorthogonal click reaction for development of injectable polysaccharide-based hydrogels for biomedical applications, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 352 (2025) 123142, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2024.123142>.
- [154] R.M. Desai, S.T. Koshy, S.A. Hilderbrand, D.J. Mooney, N.S. Joshi, Versatile click alginate hydrogels crosslinked via tetrazine-norbornene chemistry, *Biomaterials* 50 (2015) 30–37, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2015.01.048>.
- [155] A. Lueckgen, D.S. Garske, A. Ellinghaus, R.M. Desai, A.G. Stafford, D.J. Mooney, G.N. Duda, A. Cipitria, Hydrolytically-degradable click-crosslinked alginate hydrogels, *Biomaterials* 181 (2018) 189–198, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2018.07.031>.
- [156] S.T. Koshy, D.K.Y. Zhang, J.M. Grolman, A.G. Stafford, D.J. Mooney, Injectable nanocomposite cryogels for versatile protein drug delivery, *Acta Biomater.* 65 (2018) 36–43, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2017.11.024>.
- [157] A. Gonzalez-Pujana, K.H. Vining, D.K.Y. Zhang, E. Santos-Vizcaino, M. Igartua, R. M. Hernandez, D.J. Mooney, Multifunctional biomimetic hydrogel systems to boost the immunomodulatory potential of mesenchymal stromal cells, *Biomaterials* 257 (2020) 120266, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2020.120266>.
- [158] N.C. Negrini, A.A. Volponi, P.T. Sharpe, A.D. Celiz, Tunable cross-linking and adhesion of gelatin hydrogels via bioorthogonal click chemistry, *ACS Biomater.*

- Sci. Eng. 7 (2021) 4330–4346, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbomaterials.1c00136>.
- [159] I. Ali, M. Gulfam, S.H. Jo, J.W. Seo, A. Rizwan, S.H. Park, K.T. Lim, Reduction-responsive and bioorthogonal carboxymethyl cellulose based soft hydrogels cross-linked via IEDDA click chemistry for cancer therapy application, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 219 (2022) 109–120, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2022.07.229>.
- [160] Y.J. Jo, M. Gulfam, S.H. Jo, Y.S. Gal, C.W. Oh, S.H. Park, K.T. Lim, Multi-stimuli responsive hydrogels derived from hyaluronic acid for cancer therapy application, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 286 (2022) 119303, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2022.119303>.
- [161] T.T. Vu, S. Yadav, O.S. Reddy, S.H. Jo, S. Bin Joo, B.K. Kim, E.J. Park, S.H. Park, K.T. Lim, Reduction-responsive chitosan-based injectable hydrogels for enhanced anticancer therapy, *Pharmaceuticals* 16 (2023) 841, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph16060841>.
- [162] T.T. Vu, M. Gulfam, S.H. Jo, S.H. Park, K.T. Lim, Injectable and biocompatible alginate-derived porous hydrogels cross-linked by IEDDA click chemistry for reduction-responsive drug release application, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 278 (2022) 118964, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2021.118964>.
- [163] I. Ali, A. Rizwan, T.T. Vu, S.H. Jo, C.W. Oh, Y.H. Kim, S.H. Park, K.T. Lim, NIR-responsive carboxymethyl-cellulose hydrogels containing thioether-linkages for on-demand drug delivery system, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 260 (2024) 129549, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.129549>.
- [164] H.T. Hoang, T.T. Vu, V. Karthika, S.H. Jo, Y.J. Jo, J.W. Seo, C.W. Oh, S.H. Park, K.T. Lim, Dual cross-linked chitosan/alginate hydrogels prepared by Nb-Tz 'click' reaction for pH responsive drug delivery, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 288 (2022) 119389, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2022.119389>.
- [165] S. Bin Joo, M. Gulfam, S.H. Jo, Y.J. Jo, T.T. Vu, S.H. Park, Y.S. Gal, K.T. Lim, Fast absorbent and highly bioorthogonal hydrogels developed by IEDDA click reaction for drug delivery application, *Materials (Basel)*. 15 (2022) 7128, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma15207128>.
- [166] M. Gulfam, S.-H. Jo, S.-W. Jo, T. Thang Vu, S.-H. Park, K.T. Lim, Highly porous and injectable hydrogels derived from cartilage acellularized matrix exhibit reduction and NIR light dual-responsive drug release properties for application in antitumor therapy, *NPG Asia Mater.* 14 (2022) 8, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41427-021-00354-4>.
- [167] G.F. Sousa, S. Afewerki, D. Dittz, F.E.P. Santos, D.O. Gontijo, S.R.A. Scalzo, A.L. C. Santos, L.C. Guimaraes, E.M. Pereira, L.S. Barcelos, S.J.H. Do Monte, P.P. G. Guimaraes, F.R. Marciano, A.O. Lobo, Catalyst-free click chemistry for engineering chondroitin sulfate-multiarmed PEG hydrogels for skin tissue engineering, *J. Funct. Biomater.* 13 (2022) 45, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jfb13020045>.
- [168] S.H. Park, J.Y. Seo, J.Y. Park, Y.B. Ji, K. Kim, H.S. Choi, S. Choi, J.H. Kim, B. H. Min, M.S. Kim, An injectable, click-crosslinked, cytomodulin-modified hyaluronic acid hydrogel for cartilage tissue engineering, *NPG Asia Mater.* 11 (2019) 30, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41427-019-0130-1>.
- [169] A. Rizwan, I. Ali, S.H. Jo, T.T. Vu, Y.S. Gal, Y.H. Kim, S.H. Park, K.T. Lim, Facile fabrication of NIR-responsive alginate/CMC hydrogels derived through IEDDA click chemistry for photothermal-photodynamic anti-tumor therapy, *Gels* 9 (2023) 961, <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels9120961>.
- [170] X. Liu, Y. Zhang, Z. Hussain, P. Zheng, M. Xu, H. Zhao, Y. Liu, Y. Cao, I. Ullah, A. Osaka, R. Pei, Self-biomimetic in situ injectable CaSO₄ nanorods-enriched collagen-hyaluronic acid composite hydrogels for biomimetic bone reconstruction in a minimally invasive manner, *Appl. Mater. Today* 30 (2023) 101693, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2022.101693>.
- [171] L. Mota, M. Zhu, J. Li, M. Contreras, T. Aridi, J.N. Tomeo, A. Stafford, D. J. Mooney, L. Pradhan-Nabzdyk, C. Ferran, F.W. LoGerfo, P. Liang, Perivascular CLICK-gelatin delivery of thrombospondin-2 small interfering RNA decreases development of intimal hyperplasia after arterial injury, *FASEB J.* 38 (2024) e23321, <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.202301359R>.
- [172] J. Xu, Y. Liu, S. Hsu, Hydrogels based on Schiff base linkages for biomedical applications, *Molecules* 24 (2019) 3005.
- [173] F. Hakimi, L. Maeso, A. Dehghan, A. Dolatshahi-Pirouz, G.M. Stojanovic, M. Nadimifar, Z. Ahmadian, G. Orive, Schiff base polysaccharide hydrogels: A promising biomaterial for wound dressings, *ChemistrySelect* 10 (2025) e05175, <https://doi.org/10.1002/slct.202405175>.
- [174] L. Wang, W. Zhou, Q. Wang, C. Xu, Q. Tang, H. Yang, An injectable, dual responsive, and self-healing hydrogel based on oxidized sodium alginate and hydrazide-modified poly (ethylene glycol), *Molecules* 23 (2018) 546, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules23030546>.
- [175] S. Aslzad, P. Savadi, E.D. Abdolahinia, Y. Omid, M. Fathi, J. Barar, Chitosan/dialdehyde starch hybrid in situ forming hydrogel for ocular delivery of betamethasone, *Mater. Today Commun.* 33 (2022) 104873, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2022.104873>.
- [176] W. Wang, D. Shi, Y. Zhang, W. Li, F. Li, H. Feng, L. Ma, C. Yang, Z. Peng, G. Song, H. Zeng, L. Xie, An injectable hydrogel based on hyaluronic acid prepared by Schiff base for long-term controlled drug release, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 245 (2023) 125341, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.125341>.
- [177] P. Ding, O.V. Okoro, Y. Sun, L. Wang, X. Wei, S. Liu, Y. Deng, L. Fan, G. Jiang, L. Wang, A. Shavandi, L. Nie, Graphene oxide-reinforced alginate/gelatin hydrogel via Schiff-base bond and thiol-Michael addition for bone regeneration, *Mater. Today Commun.* 33 (2022) 104904, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2022.104904>.
- [178] N. Amiraghoubi, M. Fathi, A. Safary, Y. Javadzadeh, Y. Omid, In situ forming alginate/gelatin hydrogel scaffold through Schiff base reaction embedded with curcumin-loaded chitosan microspheres for bone tissue regeneration, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 256 (2024) 128335, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.128335>.
- [179] G.D. Cha, W.H. Lee, S.H. Sunwoo, D. Kang, T. Kang, K.W. Cho, M. Kim, O.K. Park, D. Jung, J. Lee, S.H. Choi, T. Hyeon, D.H. Kim, Multifunctional injectable hydrogel for in vivo diagnostic and therapeutic applications, *ACS Nano* 16 (2022) 554–567, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.1c07649>.
- [180] F. Guo, Y. Liu, S. Chen, Y. Lin, Y. Yue, A Schiff base hydrogel dressing loading extracts from *Periplaneta Americana* for diabetic wound healing, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 230 (2023) 123256, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.123256>.
- [181] L. Zhang, B. Luo, Z. An, P. Zheng, Y. Liu, H. Zhao, Z. Zhang, T. Gao, Y. Cao, Y. Zhang, R. Pei, MMP-responsive nanoparticle-loaded, injectable, adhesive, self-healing hydrogel wound dressing based on dynamic covalent bonds, *Biomacromolecules* 24 (2023) 5769–5779, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.3c00773>.
- [182] J. Li, J. Su, J. Liang, K. Zhang, M. Xie, B. Cai, J. Li, A hyaluronic acid/chitosan composite functionalized hydrogel based on enzyme-catalyzed and Schiff base reaction for promoting wound healing, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 255 (2024) 128284, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.128284>.
- [183] A. Martorana, M. Lenzuni, M. Contardi, F.S. Palumbo, S. Cataldo, A. Pettignano, V. Catania, D. Schillaci, M. Summa, A. Athanassiou, C. Fiorica, R. Bertorelli, G. Pitarresi, Schiff base-based hydrogel embedded with in situ generated silver nanoparticles capped by a hyaluronic acid-diethylenetriamine derivative for wound healing application, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 16 (2024) 20186–20201, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.4c00657>.
- [184] Y. Wu, W. Xu, J. Li, Z. Zhong, L. Huang, S. Li, H. Tan, Influence of tannic acid post-treatment on the degradation and drug release behavior of Schiff base crosslinked konjac glucomannan/chitosan hydrogel, *Eur. Polym. J.* 202 (2024) 112592, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2023.112592>.
- [185] J. Collins, Z. Xiao, M. Müllner, L.A. Connal, The emergence of oxime click chemistry and its utility in polymer science, *Polym. Chem.* 7 (2016) 3812–3826, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6py00635c>.
- [186] D.K. Kölmel, E.T. Kool, Oximes and Hydrazones in Bioconjugation: Mechanism and Catalysis, *Chem. Rev.* 117 (2017) 10358–10376, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.7b00090>.
- [187] J.G. Hardy, P. Lin, C.E. Schmidt, Biodegradable hydrogels composed of oxime crosslinked poly(ethylene glycol), hyaluronic acid and collagen: A tunable platform for soft tissue engineering, *J. Biomater. Sci. Polym. Ed.* 26 (2015) 143–161, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09205063.2014.975393>.
- [188] A.E.G. Baker, R.Y. Tam, M.S. Shoichet, Independently tuning the biochemical and mechanical properties of 3D hyaluronan-based hydrogels with oxime and Diels-Alder chemistry to culture breast cancer spheroids, *Biomacromolecules* 18 (2017) 4373–4384, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.7b01422>.
- [189] A.E.G. Baker, L.C. Bahlmann, R.Y. Tam, J.C. Liu, A.N. Ganesh, N. Mitrousis, R. Marcellus, M. Spears, J.M.S. Bartlett, D.W. Cescon, G.D. Bader, M.S. Shoichet, Benchmarking to the gold standard: Hyaluronan-oxime hydrogels recapitulate xenograft models with in vitro breast cancer spheroid culture, *Adv. Mater.* 31 (2019) 1901166, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201901166>.
- [190] H. Sánchez-Morán, A. Ahmadi, B. Vogler, K.H. Roh, Oxime cross-linked alginate hydrogels with tunable stress relaxation, *Biomacromolecules* 20 (2019) 4419–4429, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biomac.9b01100>.
- [191] P.K. Sharma, S. Taneja, Y. Singh, Hydrazone-linkage-based self-healing and injectable xanthan-poly(ethylene glycol) hydrogels for controlled drug release and 3D cell culture, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (2018) 30936–30945, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.8b07310>.
- [192] A.A. Nada, A.A.F. Soliman, A.A. Aly, A. Abou-Okeil, Stimuli-free and biocompatible hydrogel via hydrazone chemistry: Synthesis, characterization, and bioassessment, *Starch* 71 (2019) 1800243, <https://doi.org/10.1002/star.201800243>.
- [193] M. Johnson, R. Song, Y. Li, C. Milne, Z. Li, J. Lyu, A. Sigen, W. Wang, An injectable, self-healing, polysaccharide-based antioxidative hydrogel for wound healing, *RSC Appl. Polym.* 3 (2024) 238–246, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4ap00337c>.
- [194] D. Das, A. Awan, K. Kaur, M. Müller, H. Schönherr, Design, characterization, and biocompatibility of modular biopolymer-based single- and double-cross-linked networks hydrogels, *ACS Appl. Mater. Mater.* 6 (2024) 13158–13170, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaam.4c02357>.
- [195] E.A. Mozipo, A.N. Galindo, J.D. Khachatourian, C.G. Harris, J. Dorigin, V. R. Spaulding, M.R. Ford, M. Singhal, K.C. Fogg, M.H. Hettiaratchi, Statistical optimization of hydrazone-crosslinked hyaluronic acid hydrogels for protein delivery, *J. Mater. Chem. B* 12 (2024) 2523–2536, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3tb01588b>.
- [196] J. Zhang, Z. Zhang, J. Wang, Q. Zang, J.Z. Sun, B.Z. Tang, Recent progress in the applications of amino-yne click chemistry, *Polym. Chem.* 12 (2021) 2978–2986, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1py00113b>.
- [197] J. Huang, X. Jiang, Injectable and degradable pH-responsive hydrogels via spontaneous amino-yne click reaction, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (2018) 361–370, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.7b18141>.
- [198] H.-C. Li, X.-M. Sun, Y.-R. Huang, Y.-H. Peng, J. Liu, L. Ren, Synthetic crosslinker based on amino-yne click to enhance the suture tension of collagen-based corneal repair materials, *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* 4 (2022) 4495–4507, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaam.2c00472>.
- [199] M. Deng, Y. Wu, Y. Ren, H. Song, L. Zheng, G. Lin, X. Wen, Y. Tao, Q. Kong, Y. Wang, Clickable and smart drug delivery vehicles accelerate the healing of infected diabetic wounds, *J. Control. Release* 350 (2022) 613–629, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2022.08.053>.

- [200] S. Liu, X. Liu, Y. Ren, P. Wang, Y. Pu, R. Yang, X. Wang, X. Tan, Z. Ye, V. Maurizot, B. Chi, Mussel-inspired dual-cross-linking hyaluronic acid/ε-polylysine hydrogel with self-healing and antibacterial properties for wound healing, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 12 (2020) 27876–27888, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c00782>.
- [201] S. Naeimipour, F. Rasti Boroojeni, R. Selegård, D. Aili, Enzymatically triggered deprotection and cross-linking of thiolated alginate-based bioinks, *Chem. Mater.* 34 (2022) 9536–9545, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.2c02037>.
- [202] X. Jin, Y. Shang, Y. Zou, M. Xiao, H. Huang, S. Zhu, N. Liu, J. Li, W. Wang, P. Zhu, Injectable hypoxia-induced conductive hydrogel to promote diabetic wound healing, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 12 (2020) 56681–56691, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c13197>.